

VALKYRIES

D2.2 Terminology and Semantics

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1. Executive Summary

The deliverable D2.2 is framed into the task T2.2. (Terminology and Semantic Interoperability) of the work package WP2 (Design Principles and harmonization Tactics) of the VALKYRIES project.

This document provides a unified glossary and map of joint terminologies and semantic representations focused on the particularities of the cross-sector, cross-border and cross-hierarchy action against European multi-victim disasters.

It aims to give harmonized semantics and a joint terminology, supporting the harmonization, pre-standardization and standardization efforts of the first responders to disasters.

This deliverable D2.2 has been the result of the collaborative work of the editor, the consultants and, in general, the researchers involved in the VALKYRIES project. It has been based on the proposal, debate, discussion and consensus of the different terms, supported by a work web application designed specifically for this purpose.

As a result of this collaborative effort, a total of 1,644 terms have been incorporated into the glossary, all of them based on consensus among researchers, and more than 90% of them supported by at least one reference bibliographic or documentary source.

This deliverable is written in Month 6 (March 2022) of the project and is intended to be a “live” document, open to adapt to the development of the project and available to researchers throughout the life cycle of the project.

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: Terminology and Semantics

Deliverable Id: D2.2

Deliverable Title Abbreviation: D2.2

Name of lead participant: TASSICA

Name of Contributors: INDRA, PARTICLE, UMU, NOVOTEC, HESE, USN, HRT, SSA, KEM. AREU

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Details: This specification applies to the project VALKYRIES: Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated procedures for First Aid Vehicles deployment on European multi-victim Disasters funded under the SU-DRS03-2018-2019-2020 (IA), subtopic 3 Grant Agreement of the Horizon 2020 (H2020) tendering conditions. Deliverable D2.2 is framed into the project task T2.2. The document D2.2 presents a unified glossary and map of joint terminologies and semantic representations focused on the particularities of the cross-sector, cross-border and cross-hierarchy action against European multi-victim disasters.

3. Project and document scope

3.1. VALKYRIES Project overview

Mass casualty incidents (MCI) and multi-victim disasters, in which the number of casualties vastly exceeds the local resources and capabilities, are events that overwhelms the local healthcare system, at least over a period of time.

Emergency medical systems (EMS) EMS first aid response to these events often reveals insufficient resources (rescue personnel, healthcare providers, facilities, etc.), communication difficulties, and organizational interoperability issues, more serious in cross-border, intersectoral and trans-hierarchical actions.

Although the EU has evolved towards bringing strong capabilities for joint coordination and cross-sectorial cooperation between Member States (MS), studies like the EU Mandate M/487 to Establish EU Security Standards reveal significant open issues and gaps concerning the standardization and harmonization of common procedures focalized at semantic, planning, resilience and organizational interoperability aspects.

Echoed by these needs, the project VALKYRIES (Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated Procedures for First Aid Vehicles Deployment on European Multi-victim Disasters) aims to analyse, improve and demonstrate infrastructures, protocols and data exchange standards to increase efficiency during the deployment, intervention and local/remote coordination of first aid responders in multi-victim disasters.

In support to the need for harmonising the emerging technological, procedural and collaborative opportunities growing in the EU research, innovation and commercialisation ecosystem concerning the operation of first aid vehicles at cross-frontier disaster response, VALKYRIES establishes 9 specific objectives among which are:

- **OBJ-3 (Sustainable Pre-standardisation and Standardisation): Research and analyse the pre-standardisation opportunities concerning the first aid response enablers, resulting in recommendations, common requirements, guidelines and enforcement tools towards constituting a novel and sustainable reference model, being implemented at new standardisation actions.** At the proposal stage of the VALKYRIES project, the partners have identified several areas that require at least revision (in compliance with the ISO/IEC Guide 2:2004), and among them is terminology (glossaries, symbols, language).
- **OBJ-7 (Cross-sectorial collaboration, civilian protection, volunteering and military assistance): Research, analyse and expand the harmonisation framework towards facilitating, guiding and enhancing the cooperation between vehicular first aid responders with other disaster management actors, among them firefighters, law enforcement agencies, civilian protection, military or heterogeneous volunteering.** Existing shortcomings manifest from the basis of collaboration, and include the need to share a common cross-border definition of commonly used terms (extending ISO 22300) between organisations and between countries.
- **OBJ-8 (Reference integration and interoperation): Reference integration and interoperation of the harmonised technological, procedural and collaborative solutions based on the common requirements and gap mitigations prioritised by the committed end-users and practitioners.** As highlighted by the EC in the final communication concerning the implementation strategy of the European

Interoperability framework, the interoperability depicts a key factor in making a digital transformation possible, including legal, organisational, data/semantic and technical aspects to be covered. The theoretical and abstract conceptualisations, models and framework introduced by VALKYRIES will be reference integrated for facilitating their verification and supporting demonstration, resulting in the SIGRUN Platform which shall explore the identified opportunities towards bringing cognitive communications and resource federation for C&C at first aid responses in MCI.

- **OBJ-9 (Large EU scale cross-border demonstrations): Evaluation and demonstration of the interoperability and enhancements derived from harmonising vehicular first aid related enablers at four cross-border and cross-sectorial scenarios: Spain-Portugal, Slovakia-Austria, Bulgaria-Greece and Norway-Netherlands.** As part of the VALKYRIES project, four large-scale pan-European demonstrators will be conducted. Scheduled at the later stages of the project, the demonstrators will present to the audience, among others, the outcomes of the certification, regulation, standardisation and harmonisation activities.

3.2. WP2 Work package overview

VALKYRIES work has been split into seven work packages (WP). Two of them (WP2 and WP3) will embrace the design principles and guidance for the expected normalization actions.

The WP2, Design Principles and harmonization Tactics, will provide the design, specifications and requirements to take into account by the rest of the project life cycle. It establishes, among others, the joint terminology and semantics of the SIGRUN platform.

3.3. T2.2 Terminology and Semantic Interoperability task scope

Aimed at first aid vehicles and operations, this task reviews preliminary efforts with the ultimate goal of providing joint terminologies and semantic representations, concluding with a unified glossary and a map that extends those standardized in ISO 22300.

This action focuses on the particularities of cross-sectoral, cross-border and cross-hierarchical aspects inherent in the performance of legacy and novel first aid vehicles, and its results will be adopted in the next harmonization methodologies and actions.

3.4. D2.2 Joint Terminology and Semantics deliverable scope

VALKYRIES aims to have continuous participation in various standardization activities in the widest possible sense.

Among the contributions towards the expected impacts of the Work Program, such as medium-term contribution towards the Call expected impact: “Standards for an effective deployment of resources to respond to major crisis”, and such as concrete material for further pre-standardization, standardization and harmonization, among others, VALKYRIES will provide the deliverable D2.2 Joint Terminology and Semantics.

D2.2. deliverable will give harmonized semantics and a joint terminology able to assist cross-sector, cross-border and cross-hierarchical normalizations, fulfilling an established base requirement: REQ_BASE_T2.2_1: Unified glossary and map of Joint terminologies and semantic representations:

- **Description:** A common semantic model related to reconnaissance procedures, triage, care practices and crisis response planning in mass casualty incidents and disasters, MUST be produced to facilitate further related standardisation activities.
- **Details:** It at least MUST extend those standardized at ISO 22300 (Security and resilience vocabulary).
- **Rationale:** This unified glossary and map of joint terminologies and semantic representations should be written in English. It may include the local equivalences related with each term of the glossary.

4. Key reference documents

ISO 22300:2021 Security and resilience – Vocabulary. Third edition 2021-02.

5. T2.2 and D2.2 work roadmap

The works of T2.2 task development and D2.2 document preparation began in October 2021, when the VALKYRIES project started (M1), and ended in March 2022, month 6 (M6) of the project.

The following work plan was approved:

1. Definition of the categories of the glossary: the categorization of the terms in thematic areas aims to facilitate their filtering and management throughout the life cycle of the project.
2. Development of a web application to support D2.2 works: in order to facilitate collaborative work between the participants, and to facilitate the subsequent use of the glossary throughout the entire life cycle of the project.
3. Identification and review of preliminary efforts and documentary references.
4. Collaborative development of the glossary:
 - 4.1. Proposal of terms (by all the participants).
 - 4.2. Comments and contributions on terms proposed by others partners (all the participants).
5. Final definition of terms:
 - 5.1. Review of proposed terms and modifications by the editor and contributors.
 - 5.2. Approval of the final glossary by the editor and contributors.
6. D2.2. drafting, edition, reviewing and close.

6. Terms categorization

The following structure of categories and subcategories of terms, similar to the structure of the work packages and tasks of the VALKYRIES project, was agreed upon by the participants:

1. Ethical, legal & societal aspects
2. Equipment and ICT enablers for first aid responses
 - 2.1. First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units
 - 2.2. Communication
 - 2.3. Mobile command and control and operational coordination technologies
 - 2.4. First aid digitalization
 - 2.5. Instrumentation and health support wearable devices
3. Common Practices, and operational procedures for First Aid Responses
 - 3.1. Hazards
 - 3.2. Planning of crisis response
 - 3.3. Communication: notification, alert, request assistance and exchange of information
 - 3.4. Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response
 - 3.5. Maintenance, logistics and deployment
 - 3.6. Command and control, and support to operational decision-making
 - 3.7. Common operational picture
 - 3.8. Warning
4. Cooperation, education and training for first aid responses
 - 4.1. Education and training for first aid responders
 - 4.2. Cooperation for first aid responders
 - 4.3. Civil-military cooperation
 - 4.4. Civil protection
 - 4.5. Aid volunteerism
5. Others

7. VALKYRIES TASSICA D2.2 Webapp

TASSICA, leader of T2.2 task and D2.2 deliverable, developed a web application to support the collaborative work of the participants in the mentioned VALKYRIES task T2.2. and deliverable D2.2.

Through a username and password, each participant can access and use the web application through any browser.

For the use of the application, a tutorial was developed, and credentials were delivered for its use by the different partners.

7.1. Webapp functionalities

7.1.1. Add a new term / graphic representation

This option allows to enter a new term or graphic representation in the glossary.

To guarantee the technical and scientific quality of the information collected, as well as to standardize it, some fields were established as mandatory to fill in in order to register a term/graph in the glossary.

The fields available to introduce and characterize the term are the following:

- Term
- Definition / graphic representation
- Notes to entry
- Categorization

IMPORTANT:
Information must be entered in English.
Before entering a new term, check if it already exists in the list.
If it already exists, any suggestion of modification or extension will have to be made through: "Comments" or "Add Equiv." or "Add Doc".

NEW: ADD A TERM OR GRAPH.

VALKYRIES D2.2 / T2.2 Web App

Comments	Type	Term	Graph rep Text	Definition	User	Created at	Subcategories	Term Equivalences	Term Doc Sources	Status	Action
0 comments	term	access		ability of the rights holders to use or benefit from a certain service or product	TAS	23/12/2021 12:52:14		0 equivalences	1 doc sources	pending	!
0 comments	term	activity		set of one or more tasks with a defined output	TAS	23/12/2021 12:52:14		0 equivalences	1 doc sources	pending	!
0 comments	term	adhesive		glue; chemical mixture that bonds two materials together	TAS	23/12/2021 12:52:14		0 equivalences	1 doc sources	pending	!
0 comments	term	affected area		location that has been impacted by a disruptive event (incident, accident, disaster)	TAS	23/12/2021 12:52:14		0 equivalences	1 doc sources	pending	!
0 comments	term	after-action report		final exercise report, document that records, describes and analyses the actual disruption or exercise, drawing on debriefs and reports from observers, and derives lessons from it.	TAS	23/12/2021 12:52:14		0 equivalences	1 doc sources	pending	!
0 comments	term	alert		part of public warning that captures attention of first responders and people at risk in a developing emergency situation	TAS	23/12/2021 12:52:14		0 equivalences	1 doc sources	pending	!

Figure 1 - Add a term in VALKYRIES TASSICA D2.2 Webapp

7.1.2. Display of terms / graphical representations

This functionality allows viewing the list of terms to consult or work on it, with the following functionalities:

- View the list of terms / graphs

- Filter the list of terms by text or by category
- Sort the list of terms by type (term / graph), by user (who entered it), by date of entry or by category.
- Show an existing term / graph.

Figure 2 - Filter terms in VALKYRIES TASSICA D2.2 Webapp

7.1.3. Comments on existing terms / graphical representations

This option allows to add comments, extensions, criticism, nuances, etc, on an existing term in the glossary.

The objective is to facilitate discussion and consensus on the definition of the different terms.

7.1.4. Add documentary reference

This functionality allows to associate, to an existing term, as many documentary sources as desired, as well as entering the access url or uploading the document in digital format.

To guarantee the technical and scientific quality of the information collected, as well as to standardize it, some fields were established as mandatory to fill in in order to add a documentary reference in the glossary.

The fields available to characterize the reference documentary source are the following:

- Country
- Language
- Institution
- Department
- Year of publication
- Title of the article/document
- Title translation
- Author/Authors
- Publication name
- Edition number

- Volumen number
- Chapter number
- Initial page number
- Final page number
- DOI / ISSN
- Url (to access the document)
- Date of URL query

7.1.5. Add local equivalence

This option allows to associate, to an existing term, as many equivalent terms in the local language as desired, identifying the country, region, locality or agency in which it is used. The fields available to characterize the local equivalence are the following:

- Local equivalence of the term
- Country
- Region
- Location
- Agency
- Language
- Notes

IMPORTANT: provide a documentary reference when registering a term or adding an equivalence...

Add COMMENT / EQUIVALENCE / DOCUMENT ON A TERM

Comments	Type	Term	Graph rep	Text	Definition	User	Created at	Subcategories	Term Equivalences	Term Doc Sources	Status	Action
0 comments	term	access			ability of the rights holders to use or benefit from a certain service or product	TAS	23/12/2021 12:52:14		0 equivalences	1 doc sources	pending	Show
0 comments	term	activity			set of one or more tasks with a defined output	TAS	23/12/2021 12:52:14		0 equivalences	1 doc sources	pending	Comment
0 comments	term	adhesive			glue; chemical mixture that bonds two materials together	TAS	23/12/2021 12:52:14		0 equivalences	1 doc sources	pending	Add Equiv.
0 comments	term	affected area			location that has been impacted by a disruptive event (incident, accident, disaster)	TAS	23/12/2021 12:52:14		0 equivalences	1 doc sources	pending	Add Doc.
0 comments	term	after-action report			final exercise report, document that records, describes and analyses the actual disruption or exercise, drawing on debriefs and reports from observers, and derives lessons from it	TAS	23/12/2021 12:52:14		0 equivalences	1 doc sources	pending	
0 comments	term	alert			part of public warning that captures attention of first responders and people at risk in a developing emergency situation	TAS	23/12/2021 12:52:14		0 equivalences	1 doc sources	pending	

VALKYRIES TASSICA D2.2 / T2.2 Web App

Figure 3 - Add a comment / equivalence / reference in VALKYRIES TASSICA D2.2 Webapp

7.1.6. Dashboard

The dashboard shows the last terms and the last comments entered, to facilitate the task of monitoring the evolution of the glossary and reviewing its terms.

VALKYRIES

DASHBOARD: SHOW RECENTLY ADDED TERMS.

Dashboard

Recently added Terms

term	date add	user add	comments	equivalences	doc. sources	
HARCH	09/03/22 20:25:44	Administrator	0 comments	0 equivalences	1 doc. sources	Show Term
XABCE	09/03/22 20:10:45	Administrator	0 comments	0 equivalences	1 doc. sources	Show Term
emergency data exchange language- common alerting protocol (EDIL-CAP)	09/03/22 11:49:01	TASS	0 comments	0 equivalences	1 doc. sources	Show Term
emergency data exchange language- tracking of emergency patients (EDIL-TEP)	09/03/22 11:47:11	TASS	0 comments	0 equivalences	1 doc. sources	Show Term
emergency data exchange language- situation reporting (EDIL-SitRep)	09/03/22 11:45:05	TASS	0 comments	0 equivalences	1 doc. sources	Show Term

Recent comments

term	comment	user	date	
minimum data set (MDS)	Extended the definition related to Sigurn.	Administrator	04/03/22 12:42:13	Show Term
authorization	The term may be changed for: System authorization	NOV	03/03/22 09:05:50	Show Term
quality assurance programme	Quality assurance programme does not necessarily have to be linked to training	NOV	03/03/22 08:59:21	Show Term

VALKYRIES D2.2 / T2.2 Web App

Figure 4 - Dashboard of VALKYRIES TASSICA D2.2 Webapp

8. Future evolution of the glossary

All the standards assumed in the design stages of the VALKYRIES project will be monitored throughout the project life cycle in search of modifications or discards that may affect the expected results of the project. Besides, it will closely follow all regulatory and standardisation developments related to this subject within European Standardisation Organisations (ESOs) and promote their impact outside the Union.

Therefore, the glossary of terms and semantic representations, developed in task T2.2 and embodied in deliverable D2.2, will remain accessible, alive and dynamic throughout the entire life cycle of the project and even after it, supporting the harmonization, pre-standardization and standardization efforts of the first responders to disasters.

9. Glossary characterization: map of terms

After completing the work time established for the preparation of the glossary, a total of 1.644 terms were included. The nature and distribution of these terms are described below.

9.1. Distribution by categories

Code	Category	Terms	%
1	Ethical, Legal & societal aspects	81	3,70%
2	Equipment and ICT enablers for First Aid Responses	549	25,08%
3	Common Practices, and operational procedures for First Aid Responses	1053	48,10%
4	Cooperation, Education and Training for First Aid Responses	303	13,84%
5	Others	203	9,27%

Table 1 - Glossary: distribution of the terms by categories

9.2. Distribution by subcategories

Code	Subcategory	Terms	%
1.1	Ethical, Legal & societal aspects	81	2,24%
2.1	First aid vehicles and supportive autonomous units	85	2,35%
2.2	Communication	438	12,10%
2.3	Mobile Command and Control and Operational Coordination technologies	192	5,30%
2.4	First aid digitalization	87	2,40%
2.5	Instrumentation and health support wearable devices	63	1,74%
3.1	Hazards	319	8,81%
3.2	Planning of crisis response	369	10,19%
3.3	Communication (Notification, alert, request assistance and exchange of information)	230	6,35%
3.4	Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response	314	8,67%
3.5	Maintenance, logistics and Deployment	201	5,55%
3.6	Command and Control, and support to operational decision-making	269	7,43%
3.7	Common Operational Picture	178	4,92%
3.8	Warning	137	3,78%
4.1	Education and Training for First Aid Responders	73	2,02%
4.2	Cooperation for First Aid Responders	175	4,83%
4.3	Civil-Military cooperation	97	2,68%

Code	Subcategory	Terms	%
4.4	Civil Protection	174	4,81%
4.5	Aid Volunteerism	138	3,81%

Table 2 - Glossary: distribution of the terms by subcategories

9.3. Distribution by documentary reference

Documentary references	Terms	%
Total terms with documentary reference	1481	90,09%
Total terms without documentary reference	163	9,91%

Table 3 - Glossary: distribution of the terms with / without documentary references

9.4. Distribution of documentary references origin by country

Documentary references origin by country	Terms	%
International Organisation other than within the EU	1110	63,98%
Non-EU country	356	20,52%
International Organisation within the EU	267	15,39%
EU country	2	0,12%

Table 4 - Glossary: distribution of the documentary references by country

9.5. Distribution of documentary references origin by institution

Documentary references origin by institution	Terms	%
World Health Organization	654	37,74%
International Organization for Standardization (ISO)	323	18,64%
European Emergency Number Association (EENA)	202	11,66%
USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA)	201	11,60%
International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm	123	7,10%
Integrated Research on Disaster Risk	62	3,58%
European Parliament and the Council of the European Union	43	2,48%
International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO)	29	1,67%
United Nations	22	1,27%
NENA (USA National Emergency Number Association)	20	1,15%
Rescue 3 Europe Ltd	12	0,69%
European Commission	10	0,58%
OASIS Open	8	0,46%
Jawahar Institute of Mountaineering & Winter Sport	6	0,35%
European Union	4	0,23%
Avalanche Canada	3	0,17%

Documentary references origin by institution	Terms	%
European Avalanche Warning Services (EAWS)	2	0,12%
Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services (CMS)	1	0,06%
ENAC	1	0,06%
European Association for Injury Prevention and Safety Promotion (EuroSafe)	1	0,06%
National Association of Emergency Medical Technicians (NAEMT)	1	0,06%
U.S. Army	1	0,06%
European Council	1	0,06%
European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA)	1	0,06%
European Space Agency (ESA)	1	0,06%
International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies	1	0,06%

Table 5 - Glossary: distribution of the documentary references by institution

10. Terms information format

Style unification: the style of the texts has been unified as follows:

- Terms: only proper names and acronyms have been written in capital letters.
- Definition and entry notes: The usual rules of spelling in the English language have been used.
- References: have been listed for each term following the Vancouver style guidelines for citations of online sources.

Term structure: the information related to each of the terms in the glossary is structured as follows:

- **Term** (term name)
- Definition (definition of the term)
- *Notes to entry* (Annotations, extensions, clarifications, examples, etc. that complement the definition of the term)
- *Related categories* (Categories, among those established in the glossary, with which the term is related)
- *References* (Documentary and bibliographic references consulted for the definition of the term and its notes to entry)

11. Joint Terminology and Semantics: Glossary of terms

112

112 is the single European emergency phone number, available everywhere in the EU, free of charge.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.3, 3.6, 3.8

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

112 system

The set of network, data base and customer premises equipment components required to provide 112 service.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.3, 3.6, 3.8

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

5G technology

Fifth generation wireless transmission. Up to 100 times faster than 4G. 5G is creating opportunities in IoT scenarios, interconnecting people and businesses. This technology offers faster connectivity speeds, ultra-low latency and higher bandwidth, significantly improving everyday experiences.

This is why its use in e-health, connected vehicles and real-time communication, among other possible scenarios, is very interesting.

Related categories: 2.2

7p framework

Framework to help identify relevant stakeholders: (1) patients and the public; (2) providers; (3) purchasers; (4) payers; (5) policy makers; (6) product makers; and (7) principal investigators.

Related categories: 2.3, 2.4, 2.5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

ABCDE

Mnemonic acronym for Airway, Breathing, Circulation, Disability, Exposure. A primary extended but rapid survey in case of grave multiple injury to be performed in no more than 2–5 min.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

absolute human right

A right that exists at all times, stays asserted under all circumstances, cannot be restricted or derogated.

Related categories: 1.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

acceptable risk

The extent to which a disaster risk is deemed acceptable or tolerable depends on existing social, economic, political, cultural, technical and environmental conditions.

In engineering terms, acceptable risk is also used to assess and define the structural and non-structural measures that are needed in order to reduce possible harm to people, property, services and systems to a chosen tolerated level, according to codes or “accepted practice”, which are based on known probabilities of hazards and other factors.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

access

Ability of the rights holders to use or benefit from a certain service or product

Restrictions can be caused by distance to the source (e.g. water supply network does not reach a certain neighbourhood) or unaffordability (e.g. service is too costly for a certain household or group of people), among other reasons.

Related categories: 1.1, 2.2, 2.3, 3.3, 3.6, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

access provider

An access provider is any organisation that arranges for an individual or an organization to have access to the Internet.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

accessibility

1. Meaning that people with disabilities having access, on an equal basis with others, to the physical environment, transportation, information and communications technologies and systems (ICT), and other facilities and services. 2. Aspects of the structure of health services or health facilities that enhance the ability of people to reach a health care practitioner, in terms of location, time, and ease of approach.

Related categories: 1.1, 2.2, 2.3

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

accident

A sudden, unforeseen event that can cause varying degrees of harm and/or destruction, from mild damage to serious injury or death.

It is more serious than incident, although these two terms are often misused interchangeably in emergency management. Accident requires greater attention and response, whence accident prevention, accident departments in hospitals, accident legislation, emergency services.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

accident site

In disaster medicine, the place where the rescue team is in operation to extricate and relieve the victims.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.7

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

accountability

The result of the process which ensures that health actors take responsibility of what they are obliged to do and are made answerable for their actions.

Related categories: 1.1

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

accreditation

Formal process by which a recognized body, usually a non-governmental organization, assesses and recognizes that a health care organization meets applicable pre-determined and published standards.

Accreditation standards are usually regarded as optimal and achievable, and are designed to encourage continuous improvement efforts within accredited organizations. An accreditation decision about a specific health care organization is made following a periodic on-site evaluation by a team of peer reviewers, typically conducted every two to three years. Accreditation is often a voluntary process in which organizations choose to participate, rather than one required by law and regulation.

Related categories: 1.1, 3.5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

accumulation zone

Area of slope where snow, transported by wind, accumulates and builds

Related categories: 3.1

European Avalanche Warning Services (EAWS) . EAWS website. Available from: <https://www.avalanches.org/> (Date of consultation: 26/01/2022)

accuracy

The degree to which a measurement or an estimate based on measurements represents the true value of the attribute that is being measured.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

acid rain

Sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄) in the atmosphere, formed by the combination of sulphur trioxide with water, resulting in a relatively stable mist of acid droplets. In excessive concentrations in the air, it increases the acidity of the soil and disturbs the pH causing agricultural and ecological damage.

Related categories: 3.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

action phase/of disaster

Within the varying stages of disaster management, the actual direct action emergency response phase. In all preparedness programmes and especially to face emergencies that may occur without warning, it is essential to have an established plan for action.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.8

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

action plan

Often called an ‘incident action plan’, this is a statement of intent that is specific to an incident or event. It details the response strategies, objectives, resources to be applied and tactical actions to be taken.

In simulation exercises: a plan identifying corrective action/activities to be undertaken following the recommendations of an exercise report. The plan should include timelines for implementation, the identities of the officers responsible, and often the associated costs. This will ultimately contribute to continual improvement in response capabilities, and hence to preparedness.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

action planning

Steps, or activities, that must be taken to improve and sustain identified strategies.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

activation level

A level of readiness or emergency response describing an emergency operations centre’s activities in response to predetermined criteria related to the severity of an incident.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

active surveillance

Closely watching a patient or population but without giving any intervention unless their condition worsens.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.6, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

activities of daily living (ADL)

Things normally done in daily living, including any activity for self-care such as feeding, bathing, dressing, grooming, work, homemaking and leisure.

Related categories: 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

activity

Set of one or more tasks with a defined output

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.2, 3.3, 3.6, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

acute health emergency / acute public health event

Any event or emergency that represents an immediate threat to human health and requires prompt action, i.e. implementation of response and/or mitigation measures to protect the health of the public.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

Acute Large Emergency Response Tool (ALERT)

One of the 4 tools within the EU Emergency Toolbox. It responds to large-scale natural hazards and technological disasters where over 100,000 people or over 50% of the population are affected. Depending on the type of disaster, the aim is to allocate funds within 24-48 hours of an emergency's onset, emphasising on the swiftness of the decision-making process.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Commission, European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations ECHO. European Commission official website. Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/echo/emergency-toolbox-eu-funding-sudden-onset-humanitarian-crises_en (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

acute radiation syndrome

Acute radiation sickness

Related categories: 3.1, 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

adaptability

Ability of a person or population to change their actions, course or approach to doing things in order to suit a new situation.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

additional call data

Data that is associated with a call, a caller or a location.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

additional specialised care FMT

Another WHO foreign medical team classification. Responds to an expressed need for specialised services. Provides context specific specialist care supplementary to type 2 + 3 FMT or local hospital. Specialist services include: Burn Care, Dialysis and care for crush syndrome, Maxillofacial surgery, Orthoplastic surgery, Intensive rehabilitation, Maternal Health*, Neonatal and Paediatric, Transport and Retrieval (may be self contained).

Capacity: Embedded in and operate from type 2, 3 national hospital or health system. May for some services be self contained.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

address resolution protocol (ARP)

The address resolution protocol (ARP) is a communication protocol used for discovering the link layer address, such as a MAC address, associated with a given internet layer address, typically an IPv4 address. In IPv6, Neighbor Discovery Protocol and its extensions, such as Secure Neighbor Discovery, are normally used, rather than ARP.

Related categories: 2.2

adhesive

Glue; chemical mixture that bonds two materials together

It can be enabled by heat, pressure or chemistry.

Related categories: 2.3, 2.4, 2.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

advance life support (ALS)

Is a set of life-saving protocols and skills that extend Basic Life Support to further support the circulation and provide an open airway and adequate ventilation (breathing).

Related categories: 3.4

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

advanced encryption standard (AES)

A symmetric 128-bit block data encryption technique.

Related categories: 3.3

advanced medical post (AMP)

EU Civil Protection Mechanism module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks are: 1) Perform patient profiling (triage) on the site of the disaster. 2) Stabilise the condition of and prepare the patient for transport to the most suitable health facility for final treatment.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 4.4

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

advanced medical post with surgery (AMP-S)

EU Civil Protection Mechanism module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks are: 1) Perform patient profiling (triage) on the site of the disaster. 2) Stabilise the condition of and prepare the patient for transport to the most suitable health facility for final treatment. 3) Perform damage control surgery.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 4.4

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

aerial forest fire fighting module using planes (FFFP)

EU Civil Protection Mechanism module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose task is: Contribute to the extinction of large forest and vegetal fires by performing aerial firefighting using airplanes.

Related categories: 2.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 4.4

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

aerial forest firefighting module using helicopters (FFFH)

EU Civil Protection Mechanism module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose task is: Contribute to the extinction of large forest and vegetal fires by performing aerial firefighting using helicopters.

Related categories: 2.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 4.4

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

affected

1. People who are affected, either directly or indirectly, by a hazardous event. 2. Persons, baggage, cargo, containers, conveyances, goods, postal parcels or human remains that are infected or contaminated, or carry sources of infection or contamination, to constitute a public health risk. 3. People requiring immediate assistance during a period of emergency, i.e. requiring basic survival needs such as food, water, shelter, sanitation and immediate medical assistance (Centre for Research on the Epidemiology of Disasters).

Related categories: 2.4, 3.2, 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

affected area

Location that has been impacted by a disruptive event (incident, accident, disaster)

The term is more relevant to immediate evacuations

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

after-action report (AAR)

Final exercise report, document that records, describes and analyses the actual disruption or exercise, drawing on debriefs and reports from observers, and derives lessons from it

The after-action report documents the results from the after-action review

Related categories: 1.1, 3.3, 3.6, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

after-action review

After an activation, operation or exercise has been completed, a process involving a structured facilitated discussion to review what should have happened, what actually happened, and why.

Related categories: 3.2, 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

age groups

On the basis of healthrelevant issues, life-span years are subdivided and named by categories that can vary according to country and legislation. Generally accepted groups are as follows: 1. Early childhood: from birth to 9 years Child: up to age 18 years (UN). Also minor, juvenile. 2. Adolescent: 10–19 years. 3. Youth: 15–24 years. 4. Adulthood: 20–59 years (including reproductive years 15–44). 5. Old age: 60 years and over

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

agency

A government element with a specific function offering a particular kind of assistance.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.3, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

agency representative

A person assigned by a primary, assisting, or cooperating local, state, tribal, territorial, or Federal Government agency, or nongovernmental or private organization, who has authority to make decisions affecting that agency's or organization's participation in incident management activities following appropriate consultation with that agency's leadership.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.3, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

agent-based model

Class of computational model for simulating the actions and interactions of autonomous agents (both individual or collective entities such as organizations or groups) with a view to assessing their effects on the system as a whole.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 2.4

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

aid

Support provided by countries, international agencies, institutions, non-governmental organizations or foundations, to developing countries in the form of monetary grants, loans at low interest rates, in kind, or a combination of these.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

aid effectiveness

Effectiveness of development aid in achieving economic or human development or development targets.

According to the Paris Declaration on Aid Effectiveness five principles are key to improved aid effectiveness: Ownership (partner countries exercise effective leadership over their development policies, and strategies and coordinate development actions); Alignment (donors base their overall support on partner countries' national development strategies, institutions and procedures); Harmonization (donors' actions are more harmonized, transparent and collectively effective); Managing for results (partner countries and donors shift focus to development results and results get measured); and Mutual Accountability (donors, partners and countries are accountable for development results).

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

aid-in-kind

Flows of goods and services with no payment in money or debt instruments in exchange. In some cases, 'commodity aid' goods (such as grain) are subsequently sold and the receipts are used in the budget or, more commonly through a special fund, for public expenditure.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

airburst

An explosion of a comet or meteoroid within the Earth's atmosphere without striking the ground.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgLS55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

alarm

Signal giving warning of danger

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.8

United Nations, Department of Humanitarian Affairs. Internationally agreed glossary of basic terms related to Disaster Management. Year of publication: 1992. Available from: <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/004DFD3E15B69A67C1256C4C006225C2-dha-glossary-1992.pdf>

alert

1- Part of public warning that captures attention of first responders and people at risk in a developing emergency situation.

2-The first notification that a public health event with adverse consequences may occur or may be occurring.

3- Messages or information communicated to partners, communities and the public to help inform about, prevent the spread of, or control an acute public health event.

An alert refers to a public health event that has been (i) verified and (ii) risk assessed and (iii) requires an intervention (an investigation, a re- sponse or a communication).

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699> (Date of consultation: 30/12/2021)

all clear

Message or signal that the danger is over

Related categories: 2.2, 3.1, 3.3

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

all-hazards

Naturally occurring event, human induced event (both intentional and unintentional) and technology caused event with potential impact on an organization , community or society and the environment on which it depends

Related categories: 1.1, 2.2, 2.3, 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

all-hazards approach

An integrated approach to emergency preparedness planning focusing on capacities and capabilities that are critical to preparedness, covering natural and/or man-made emergencies and/or disasters.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

alternate PSAP

A PSAP designated to receive calls when the primary PSAP is unable to do so.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3, 3.8

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

alternate routing

The capability of routing 112 calls to a designated alternate location(s) if all 112 trunks are busy or out of service. May be activated upon request or automatically, if detectable, when 112 equipment fails or the PSAP itself is disabled.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3, 3.8

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

alternate worksite

Work location, other than the primary location, to be used when the primary location is not accessible

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

Amver

A world-wide ship reporting system for search and rescue

Related categories: 3.3, 3.8, 4.5

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icsc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

analysis area

Subject matter that has been selected to be peer reviewed

EXAMPLE: Governance of risk management, assessment of risk, financial capacity, urban development, climate change adaptation and ecosystem protection, institutional capacity, community and societal capacity, economic and business continuity, infrastructure, public health, recovering and rebuilding.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.7, 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

analysis system

Set of interconnecting parts that work together to form and deliver an analysis area

Related categories: 1.1, 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

analyzing hazards

A process to determine what hazards or threats merit special attention, what actions must be planned for, and what resources are likely to be needed.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

anchor

Point where the rope is secured to the snow, ice or rock with either fixed bolts, rocks, trees or non-fixed gear to provide protection against a fall.

<https://www.jawaharinstitutepahalgam.com/mtn%20terminology1.php>

Related categories: 3.4

Jawahar Institute of Mountaineering & Winter Sport. JIM&WS website. Available from: <https://www.jawaharinstitutepahalgam.com/mtn%20terminology1.php>

anchor point

In firefighting, an advantageous point of a barrier from which a protective fire line can be constructed, especially to reduce the hazard of being outflanked by the flames.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

angle of arrival (AOA)

A terrestrial Location Determination Technology (LDT) that computes a transmitter's location based upon the angle at which the transmitter's radio signal strikes multiple receivers.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

answerable

The liability of a person, community or state called to account; responsible for acts committed.

Related categories: 1.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

antenna

Device, normally based on a metallic conductor, designed with the goal of emitting and/or receiving electromagnetic waves towards the medium.

Related categories: 2.2

anthropogenic hazards

Hazards that are induced entirely or predominantly by human activities and choices. Synonym: 'human-induced hazards'.

Anthropogenic hazards include technological, societal and socionatural hazards. In the context of the Sendai Framework, this term does not include the occurrence or risk of armed conflicts and other situations of social instability or tension which are subject to international humanitarian law and national legislation.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

anticyclone

A region where barometric pressure is high or relative to that in the surrounding regions at the same level.

Related categories: 3.1

United Nations, Department of Humanitarian Affairs. Internationally agreed glossary of basic terms related to Disaster Management. Year of publication: 1992. Available from: <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/004DFD3E15B69A67C1256C4C006225C2-dha-glossary-1992.pdf>

antidote

A chemical or medicine given to counter a specific poisoning.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

anycast

Anycast is a network addressing and routing methodology in which a single destination IP address is shared by devices (generally servers) in multiple locations. Routers direct packets addressed to this destination to the location nearest the sender, using their normal decision-making algorithms, typically the lowest number of BGP network hops.

Related categories: 2.2

APACHE scale

Acute physiology and chronic health evaluation, a numerical score to predict patient outcomes, performance and prognosis, in seriously ill patients.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

application layer security

Providing security to application layer protocols (HTTP, FTP, SMTP for example) through one of many methods that may include end-to-end privacy (PKE etc), message integrity, non repudiation, proof of submission etc

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

application programming interface (API)

Is a connection between computers or between computer programs. It is a type of software interface, offering a service to other pieces of software.

Related categories: 2.2

appropriate care

1. Care that meets the health needs of the entire population. 2. Care that is effective and based on the best available scientific evidence. 3. Interventions that are safe and that do not cause any harm or suffering; and priorities for the allocation and organization of resources that are based on equity and economic efficiency.

Related categories: 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

appropriate law enforcement and other government officials

Government and law enforcement personnel that have specific legal jurisdiction over the international supply chain or portions of it

Related categories: 1.1, 3.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

area at risk

Location that could be affected by a disruptive event (incident, accident, disaster)

The term is more relevant to preventative evacuations.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

area command

An organization that oversees the management of multiple incidents or oversees the management of a very large or evolving situation with multiple ICS organizations. See Unified Area Command.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

areal precipitation

The average amount of precipitation which has fallen over a specific area.

Related categories: 3.1

United Nations, Department of Humanitarian Affairs. Internationally agreed glossary of basic terms related to Disaster Management. Year of publication: 1992. Available from: <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/004DFD3E15B69A67C1256C4C006225C2-dha-glossary-1992.pdf>

arson

Criminal setting on fire of another's property or the intentional burning of one's own property when insured. A fire also set by an unstable individual for personal, psychopathological satisfaction.

Related categories: 3.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

artificial Intelligence

It is the combination of algorithms designed with the purpose of creating machines that have the same capabilities as human beings.

Related categories: 3.6

artificial intelligence (AI)

The use of computer systems to correctly interpret external data, to learn from it, and to use those learnings to achieve specific goals and tasks.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

ash fall

Fine (less than 4 mm in diameter) unconsolidated volcanic debris blown into the atmosphere during an eruption; can remain airborne for long periods of time and travel considerable distance from the source.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgLS5evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

assembly point

A location designated as the place for a group to meet or for people to gather in an emergency

Assembly point is a term used in cases of emergency.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.2, 3.4, 4.4

Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services (CMS), Department of Health & Human Services. Survey & Certification Group - FAQs - Emergency Preparedness Regulation, Clarifications and Definitions. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: <https://www.cms.gov/Medicare/Provider-Enrollment-and-Certification/SurveyCertEmergPrep/Downloads/FAQ-Round-Four-Definitions.pdf> (Date of consultation: 12/01/2022)

assessment

A formal process of evaluation of a process or system, preferably quantitative, but sometimes necessarily qualitative.

Related categories: 3.6, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

assessment expert

A category of expert referred in article 41 of Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014, who shall be able to provide an assessment of the situation and advise on the appropriate action to be taken and be available for missions.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

asset

Anything that has value to an organization

Assets include but are not limited to human, physical, information, intangible and environmental resources.

Related categories: 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

asset approach

A viewpoint which examines a situation, person, group or organization in terms of its (their) positive attributes or assets which could contribute to a solution. The opposite of an asset lens/approach is a deficit-oriented lens/approach which focuses on problems and limitations.

Related categories: 3.6, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

asset literacy

Consists of four components which include: 1) an understanding of what assets are; 2) the potential contribution of different assets; 3) the extent to which people know how to mobilize

or access different types of assets; and 4) possessing self-efficacy and motivation to move from awareness to taking action.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

asset mapping

Process of identifying resources and assets within a community to understand its strengths and opportunities which can contribute to resilience and community development.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

asset-based approach

An orientation toward looking at a situation or issue in terms of potential resources that can contribute to a solution, or existing systems and structures that can be built on to improve a situation or address the problem. The opposite of an asset-oriented approach is a deficit-oriented approach, which looks at situations or issues in term of vulnerabilities, limitations, problems, or liabilities.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

assigned resource

A resource that has been checked in and assigned work tasks on an incident.

Related categories: 2.3, 2.4, 3.3, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

assignment

A task given to a person or team to perform based on operational objectives defined in the IAP.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

assisting agency

An agency or organization providing personnel, services, or other resources to the agency with lead responsibility for incident management.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from:

<https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

asymmetric cryptographic key

An encryption system in which the sender and receiver of a message use different keys to encrypt and decrypt the message. Asymmetric keys can be used to establish a secure channel for symmetric key encryption.

Related categories: 3.3

atomic bomb

Atom bomb, or A-bomb, the basic nuclear weapon in which the explosive energy is derived only from fission of the atomic nuclei, liberating energy and radiation. The first atom bombs dropped in 1945 on Hiroshima and Nagasaki, Japan, were of this type.

Related categories: 3.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

attack rate

Percentage of the population that contracts the disease in an at-risk population during a specified time period.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

audit

Systematic, independent and documented process for obtaining audit evidence and evaluating it objectively to determine the extent to which the audit criteria are fulfilled.

An audit can be an internal audit (first party) or an external audit (second party or third party), and it can be a combined audit (combining two or more disciplines).

An internal audit is conducted by the organization itself, or by an external party on its behalf.

“Audit evidence” and “audit criteria” are defined in ISO 19011.

The fundamental elements of an audit include the determination of the conformity of an object according to a procedure carried out by personnel not being responsible for the object audited.

An internal audit can be for management review and other internal purposes and can form the basis for an organization’s declaration of conformity. Independence can be demonstrated by the freedom from responsibility for the activity being audited. External audits include second- and third-party audits. Second-party audits are conducted by parties having an interest in the organization, such as customers, or by other persons on their behalf. Third-party audits are conducted by external, independent auditing organizations, such as those providing certification/registration of conformity or government agencies.

This constitutes one of the common terms and core definitions of the high level structure for ISO management system standards.

Related categories: 1.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

auditor

Person who conducts an audit.

Related categories: 1.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

authentication

The act of verifying the identity that is supplied over the network by a remote user or entity, such as a program.

Related categories: 3.3

authorization

Related to a system resources: security mechanism used to determine access levels or user/client privileges including files, services, computer programs, data and application features.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.3

authorized economic operator

Party involved in the international movement of goods in whatever function that has been approved by or on behalf of a national customs administration as conforming to relevant supply chain security standards.

“Authorized economic operator” is a term defined in the World Customs Organization (WCO) Framework of Standards.

Authorized economic operators include, among others, manufacturers, importers, exporters, brokers, carriers, consolidators, intermediaries, ports, airports, terminal operators, integrated operators, warehouses and distributors.

Related categories: 1.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 4.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

automatic alarm and automatic alerting device

Any automated device which will access the 112 system for emergency services upon activation and does not provide for two-way communication. (Many countries or regions prohibit the dialling of 112 by an automated device.)

Related categories: 3.8

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

automatic call distributor (ACD)

Equipment that automatically distributes incoming calls to available PSAP attendants in the order the calls are received, or queues calls until an attendant becomes available.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 3.1

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

automatic identification system (AIS)

A system used by ships and vessel traffic services (VTS), principally for identifying and locating vessels.

Related categories: 2.3

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icsc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

automatic location identification (ALI)

The automatic display at the PSAP of the caller's telephone number, the address/location of the telephone and supplementary emergency services information of the location from which a call originates.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.8

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

automatic location identification (ALI) queries

The act of querying/retrieving the automatic display at the PSAP of the address/location of the telephone and supplementary emergency service information related to the caller's telephone number.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.8

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

automatic number identification (ANI)

Telephone number associated with the access line from which a call originates.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.8

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

available resource

A resource assigned to an incident, checked in, and available for assignment.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

avalanche

A large mass of loosened earth material, snow, or ice that slides, flows or falls rapidly down a mountainside under the force of gravity.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

avalanche airbag

An avalanche airbag is a piece of protective equipment designed to keep its wearer on or near the surface of a flowing avalanche

Related categories: 3.4, 3.5

Avalanche Canada . Avalanche Canada website. Available from: <https://www.avalanche.ca/glossary> (Date of consultation: 26/01/2022)

average

In marine insurance, means damage.

Related categories: 3.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

AVPU

Emergency acronym for Awake, Verbal response, Part response, Unresponsive. A rapid neurological assessment of a trauma patient when there is no time to do the Glasgow coma scale.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

backfire

In firefighting, a fire started intentionally by the firefighters along the inner edge of the fire-control line with the aim of consuming the fuel in the path of a forest fire, or of changing the direction of the fire's advance.

Related categories: 3.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

backup public safety

Typically a disaster recovery answering point which serves as a backup to the primary PSAP and is not co-located with the primary PSAP.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

backwater

A rise of water level in a stream caused by a natural or artificial obstruction.

Related categories: 3.1

United Nations, Department of Humanitarian Affairs. Internationally agreed glossary of basic terms related to Disaster Management. Year of publication: 1992. Available from: <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/004DFD3E15B69A67C1256C4C006225C2-dha-glossary-1992.pdf>

badging

The assignment of physical incident-specific credentials to establish legitimacy and permit access to incident sites. See Credentialing.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

bandwidth

1. In analog radio communications, it is the range of frequencies used by a system.

2. In computing, is the maximum rate of data transfer across a given communication link, also known as "band width" or "throughput"

Related categories: 2.2

base station

A base station is a fixed or modem radio installation for medium, low or high two-way communication in radio communications. It is used to communicate with mobile radios or cellular phones.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.3

basic 112

An emergency telephone system which automatically connects 112 callers to a designated answering point. Call routing is determined by originating central office only. Basic 112 may or may not support ANI and/or ALI.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3, 3.8

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

basic health care

The provision of the minimal, simplified essential health requirements in a low-income country, based on essential vaccination, essential medicaments and simple perinatal care, not necessarily integrated within the country's organized basic health services and socioeconomic needs. It should be distinguished from Primary Health Care.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

basic healthcare ERU

An IFRC Emergency Response Unit (ERU) to provide immediate basic, essential curative, preventive and community health care in emergency situations according to WHO basic protocols, where local medical facilities are insufficient or have been destroyed. Preventive mother and child care disease and nutritional surveillance with formal reporting. Community health with PHC. Optional modules available, including surgical/nursing.

Capacity: 200 people per day, 10–20 beds for overnight observation. Supplies to treat 30,000 pop. for a month.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

basic life support (BLS)

Is the basic level of medical care which is used for patients with life-threatening illnesses or injuries until the patient can be given full medical care at a hospital. It consists of a number of basic life-saving techniques of pre-hospital emergency care.

Related categories: 3.4

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

basic service set identifier (BSSID)

The BSSID, of a wireless local area network, is a unique identification name for all packets on a wireless network to identify them as part of that network. Unlike the Service Set Identifier, which can be used on multiple BSSs, the BSSID can only be used on one.

Related categories: 2.2

basic social services

Set of services delivered in education, health and social areas, as a means to fulfil basic needs

Related categories: 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 4.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

Beaufort scale

Scale of wind force, measured from 0 (calm) to 12 (hurricane force wind)

Related categories: 3.1, 3.8

United Nations, Department of Humanitarian Affairs. Internationally agreed glossary of basic terms related to Disaster Management. Year of publication: 1992. Available from: <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/004DFD3E15B69A67C1256C4C006225C2-dha-glossary-1992.pdf>

belay

The device and technique employed by a climber to safeguard the party from the effects of a fall by one of it's members.

Related categories: 3.4

Jawahar Institute of Mountaineering & Winter Sport. JIM&WS website. Available from: <https://www.jawaharinstitutepahalgam.com/mtn%20terminology1.php>

benchmark

Standard or reference value for indicator that serve as signposts to let the researcher, or other interested people such as policy makers, know what has been achieved or how severe a situation is.

Related categories: 3.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

benefit

Measurable improvement resulting from the changes introduced as a result of a peer review

Benefits can be tangible or intangible, quantifiable or non-quantifiable, and financial or non-financial.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.6, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

big data

Extremely large datasets that may be analysed to reveal patterns, trends, and associations (for example, in relation to human behaviour and interactions).

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

bilateral cooperation

Technical cooperation or assistance given by a donor country to a recipient country, through direct agreement between the two governments, without UN or other intermediary.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

biodiversity

Variability among living organisms from all sources including land, marine and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which the organisms are part.

This includes diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems. Biodiversity is thus not only the sum of all ecosystems, species and genetic material, but rather represents the variability within and among them.

Biodiversity can also be referred to as “biological diversity”.

Related categories: 3.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

bioethics

A term made of the Greek words bios (life) and ethos (ethics). In health care and life sciences, the systematic study and consideration of human conduct in relation to principles and moral values, with attention to the person and the person's humanity.

Related categories: 1.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

biological agents classification

Biological agents/weapons are usually classified (a) according to their taxonomy: fungi bacteria and viruses; (b) according to their infectivity, virulence, lethality, pathogenicity, incubation period; (c) according to their contagiousness and mechanism of transmission; and (d) according to their stability or capacity of survival. Cf. chemical agents classification, chemical weapons, biological warfare.

Related categories: 3.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

biological disaster

Disaster caused by a large-scale exposure of the biomass or living organisms to toxic substances, germs or radiation.

Related categories: 3.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

biological hazards

Hazards of organic origin or conveyed by biological vectors, including pathogenic microorganisms, toxins and bioactive substances.

Examples are bacteria, viruses or parasites, as well as venomous wildlife and insects, poisonous plants and mosquitoes carrying disease-causing agents.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNi/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

biological warfare

The intentional spread of disease in warfare through the dispersal of infective bacteria, rickettsiae, viruses, toxins or other biological weapons which cause diseases such as anthrax, plague, typhoid, brucellosis.

There is a UN Convention against biological weapons. Biological and chemical weapons are considered together (CBW) as weapons of mass destruction.

Related categories: 3.1, 4.3

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

biological weapons

Weapons that achieve their intended target effects through the infectivity of disease-causing microorganisms and other replicative entities, including viruses, infectious nucleic acids, prions.

The Biological Weapons Convention requires states parties “never in any circumstances to develop, produce, stockpile or otherwise acquire or retain (1) microbial or other biological agents or toxins ... and (2) weapons equipment or means of delivery designed to use such agents or toxins for hostile purposes or in armed conflict” – BWC.

Related categories: 3.1, 4.3

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

bioterrorism

The intentional use of microorganisms, toxins, genetic material or substances derived from living organisms to produce death or disease in humans, animals or plants.

Related categories: 3.1, 4.3

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

bit

Acronym for Binary digIT. The smallest unit of information with which a digital computer works

Related categories: 2.2

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

blizzard

A severe snow storm with winds exceeding 35 mph (56 km/h) for three or more hours, producing reduced visibility (less than .25 mile (400 m)).

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

bluetooth low energy (BLE)

Wireless personal area network technologies. It provides low power consumption in data transmissions.

Related categories: 3.3

body surface area (BSA)

Assessment of the burnt surface area of the body in a thermal injury. BSA is usually expressed in sections of 9% (the rule of 9) of the body area burnt. Less frequently, it is also expressed mathematically:

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

border gateway protocol (BGP)

Standardized exterior gateway protocol designed to exchange routing and reachability information among autonomous systems (AS) on the Internet. It makes routing decisions based on paths, network policies, or rule-sets configured by a network administrator. BGP used for routing within an autonomous system is called Interior Border Gateway Protocol, Internal BGP (iBGP). In contrast, the Internet application of the protocol is called Exterior Border Gateway Protocol, External BGP (eBGP).

Related categories: 2.2

NENA (USA National Emergency Number Association). NENA Glossary of 9-1-1 Terminology. Year of publication: 2022. Available from: https://nenawiki.org/wiki/NENA_Glossary_of_9-1-1_Terminology (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

botnet

The word “botnet” is formed from the words “robot” and “network.” Cyber criminals use special Trojan viruses to breach the security of several users’ computers, take control of each computer, and organize all the infected machines into a network of “bots” that the criminal can remotely manage.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3

bradford disaster scale

To facilitate comparison of one disaster with another, the BDS defines magnitudes by taking the logarithm (base 100) of the number of fatalities.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.3, 3.8

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

breadth of integration

Number of different functions and services provided along the continuum of care.

Related categories: 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

broadcasting

In computer networking, telecommunication and information theory, broadcast is a method of transferring a message to all recipients simultaneously.

Related categories: 2.2

brute force password attack

A method of accessing an obstructed device by attempting multiple combinations of numeric/alphanumeric passwords.

Related categories: 3.3

budgeting

The process of elaborating a detailed plan for the future showing how resources will be acquired and used during a specific time period, expressed in formal, measurable terms.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

buffer capacities

Disaster response capacities, the availability of and rapid access to which are co-financed under Article 21(2)(d) of Decision No 1313/2013/EU;

Related categories: 2.1, 3.5, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

Building Information Services and Control System (BISACS)

A computer-based system that allows access to building information such as its structural layout and/or monitors a particular building or set of buildings for alerts.

Related categories: 2.3, 2.4, 3.2, 3.4

NENA (USA National Emergency Number Association). NENA Glossary of 9-1-1 Terminology. Year of publication: 2021. Available from: https://nenawiki.org/wiki/NENA_Glossary_of_9-1-1_Terminology (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

building-block approach

A method focused on exposing participants to a cycle of training and exercises that escalates in complexity, with each exercise designed to build upon the last, in terms of scale and subject matter. For example, a building-block series of exercises may include a seminar, which leads to a tabletop exercise (TTX), which leads to a full-scale exercise (FSE).

Related categories: 4.1

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

burden of disease

Impact of a health problem on, for instance, financial cost, mortality, morbidity, or other indicators.

Related categories: 3.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

burn

Tissue damage of varying degrees caused by the heat produced from a thermal agent. Burns are classified according to the extent of body surface involved, according to the depth of tissue damage, or according to the cause, e.g. flame, steam, electric, chemical, lightning, nuclear radiation

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

burn degrees

On a burnt patient, three degrees of burns are distinguished, according to the depth of the burnt area, important in the healing process and treatment. First degree: damage limited to the outer superficial layer of the epidermis, with redness and pain, e.g. sunburn; 2nd: the burn extends through the epidermis down to dermis, but not entirely compromising the regeneration process; 3rd: full-thickness burn, killing the skin. These degrees concern the depth and not the extent of the area burnt.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

burn extent – rule of 9

In a burned person, the body's surface area (BSA) that is burnt has great importance in the outcome of the injury and treatment. For practical calculations, the body is divided into areas, each representing 9% of its surface. Thus, the head represents 9%, an arm 9%, a leg 18%, the back 18%, etc. (This assessment – of surface – is different from the degree of burn.)

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

burns centre

Particular unit and facilities in a hospital for the specialized care for all aspects of severely burned patients, including surgical, reconstructive, nursing, medico-social, rehabilitative and other ancillary facilities for a large number of patients. It also promotes burns prevention in the community and collaborates closely with the authorities in firefighting and preparedness programmes.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

business continuity

Capability of an organization to continue the delivery of products and services within acceptable time frames at predefined capacity during a disruption

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

business continuity management system (BCMS)

Part of the overall management system that establishes, implements, operates, monitors, reviews, maintains and improves business continuity

The management system includes organizational structure, policies, planning activities, responsibilities, procedures, processes and resources.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

business continuity plan

Documented information that guides an organization to respond to a disruption and resume, recover and restore the delivery of products and services consistent with its business continuity objectives

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

business continuity programme

Ongoing management and governance process supported by top management and appropriately resourced to implement and maintain business continuity management

In ISO 22301:2019, this term has been replaced by business continuity management system

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

business impact analysis

Process of analysing the impact over time of a disruption on the organization

The outcome is a statement and justification of business continuity requirements.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.2, 3.3, 3.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

business partner

Contractor, supplier or service provider with whom an organization contracts to assist the organization in its function as an organization in the supply chain

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

business recovery

A component of the Continuity of Operations (COOP) annex that describes the systems in place to continue business and administrative operations after an incident.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

busy tone

An audible signal indicating a call cannot be completed because the called access line is busy.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

call data records (CDR)

A call data record, also known as a call detail record, provides information about calls made over a phone service. A CDR report contains information related to a telephone call, such as the origin, destination, duration and network.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

call queuing

The method of selection of which calls get passed to the outgoing trunk group when there are more call originations than terminating members on the outgoing trunk.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

call taker

An agent of a PSAP who answers emergency calls

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

call transfer

The capability to redirect a call to another party.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

caller hold

The capability of the PSAP to maintain control of a 112 caller's access line, even if the caller hangs up.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

calling line identification

Signalling parameter that identifies the telephone number of the party placing a call.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

calls

A generic term used to include any type of request for emergency assistance and is not limited to voice

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

camp

A geographical site within the general incident area (separate from the Incident Base) that is equipped and staffed to provide sleeping, food, water, and sanitary services to incident personnel.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

cap message

A notification using the Common Alerting Protocol. CAP is used within the ESInet to send alerts from automated systems to PSAPs, and is also used to communicate data between agencies without a call.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3, 3.8

NENA (USA National Emergency Number Association). NENA Glossary of 9-1-1 Terminology. Year of publication: 2021. Available from: https://nenawiki.org/wiki/NENA_Glossary_of_9-1-1_Terminology (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

capabilities-based planning

Determining capabilities suitable for a wide range of threats and hazards while working within a framework that necessitates prioritization and choice. Capabilities-based planning addresses uncertainty by analyzing a wide range of scenarios to identify required capabilities.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

capability

Possessing the demonstrable ability to perform a particular task.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

capacity

Combination of all the strengths and resources available within an organization, community or society that can reduce the level of risk or the effects of a crisis

Capacity can include physical, institutional, social, or economic means as well as skilled personnel or attributes such as leadership and management.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

capacity assessment

The process by which the capacity of a group, organization or society is reviewed against desired goals, where existing capacities are identified for maintenance or strengthening, and capacity gaps are identified for further action.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

capacity development

The process by which people, organizations and society systematically stimulate and develop their capacities over time to achieve social and economic goals, including through improvement of knowledge, skills, systems and institutions.

Capacity development is a concept that extends the term of capacity-building to encompass all aspects of creating and sustaining capacity growth over time. It involves learning and various types of training, but also continuous efforts to develop institutions, political awareness, financial resources, technology systems and the wider enabling environment.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

capital expenditure

The cost for resources that last more than one year, such as building, vehicles, computers, pre-service training. Sometime a price ceiling is also defined (usually \$US 100), below which costs are considered as recurrent. The cost of capital equipment is net of depreciation. Also called investment or non-recurrent cost / expenditure.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

captain

Master of a ship or pilot-in-command of an aircraft, commanding officer of a warship, or an operator of any other vessel

Related categories: 3.6

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icssc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

cardiac arrest

The stopping of blood circulation with disappearance of blood pressure and cessation of heart function. Commonly called heart attack.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

cardiopulmonary resuscitation

The technique and manoeuvres applied to a severely injured patient in order to ensure the basic functions of the heart and lungs and to maintain such vital support until the end of the critical period.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

cardiopulmonary-cerebral resuscitation

In a severely ill or seriously injured person, providing the essential life needs for survival through manoeuvres that ensure emergency oxygenation, restoration of spontaneous blood circulation and cerebral resuscitation.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

care maps

Plans for the management of patient care that set goals for patients and provide the sequence of interventions that physicians, nurses and other professionals should carry out in order to reach the desired goals in a given time period.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

carer

Individual who provides support to a vulnerable person

Carers can be paid or unpaid providers of care.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

cargo transport unit

Road freight vehicle, railway freight wagon, freight container, road tank vehicle, railway tank wagon or portable tank

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

case

A person identified as having a particular disease, health disorder, or condition under surveillance or investigation.

Cases may be further classified as confirmed, suspect, or probable.

Related categories: 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

case definition

A set of diagnostic criteria that must be fulfilled in order to identify a case of a particular disease.

Case definitions can be based on clinical, laboratory, epidemiological, or combined clinical and laboratory criteria. When a set of criteria is standardized for purposes of identifying a particular disease, then it is referred to as 'standard case definition'. A surveillance case definition is one that is standardized and used to obtain an accurate detection of all cases of the targeted disease or condition in a given population, while excluding the detection of other similar conditions.

Related categories: 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

case management

Provision of continuous care across different services through the integration and coordination of needs and resources around the patient.

The fundamental difference with disease management is that it focuses more on individual patients and their families than on the population of patients with a certain disease. This type of management is targeted at people with a high level of risk requiring expensive care, people who are vulnerable, or have complex social and health needs. The case manager coordinates patient care throughout the entire continuum of care.

Related categories: 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

case number

Tracking number used to reference recorded incidents and events. Related nomenclature: Call Number, Report Number, Incident number, Report number.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.6, 3.7

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

casualty

Any human accessing health or medical services, including mental health services and medical forensics/mortuary care (for fatalities), as a result of a hazard impact.

The term 'casualties' may refer to the sum of the dead, missing, ill and injured.

Related categories: 2.4, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

catastrophic fire

General term for the simultaneous coalescing of multiple fires, or firestorm.

Related categories: 3.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

categorical data

Data that can take one of a limited number of values.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

CBRN detection and sampling (CBRNDET)

EU Civil Protection Mechanism module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks are: a) Carry out/confirm the initial assessment, including: a) the description of the dangers or the risks, b) the determination of the contaminated area, c) the assessment or confirmation of the protective measures already taken. 2) Perform qualified sampling. 3) Mark the contaminated area. 4) Prediction of the situation, monitoring, dynamic assessment of the risks, including recommendations for warning and other measures. 5) Provide support for immediate risk reduction.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.4, 3.5, 4.4

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

CCTV system

Surveillance system comprised of cameras, recorders, interconnections and displays that is used to monitor activities in a store, a company or more generally a specific infrastructure and/or a public place

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

CECIS user group

A user group consisting of representatives nominated by Member States shall assist the Commission in the validation, testing, and further development of the Common Emergency Communication and Information System (CECIS).

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.3, 3.6, 4.4

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

cell

The wireless telecommunications antenna serving a specific geographic area.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

cell broadcast (CB)

Cell Broadcast (CB) is a technology that has a similar user experience as SMS has: text messages are displayed on the screen of the mobile device. However, the technology that is used to send the message to the mobile phone differs between both technologies.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

cell sector

One face of a cell antenna (typically 3-sided) that operates independently of the other sectors.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

cell site

The location of a cell and related equipment.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

cellular priority access service (CPAS)

A uniform nationwide method of providing priority access to authorized wireless subscribers in the event of an emergency.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.3

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

census

A count of the target population

A register of injured people, unharmed people, etc. in emergency situations

Related categories: 2.2

central processing unit (CPU)

The part of a computer which performs the logical, computational and decision making functions.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

Centre for Research on the Epidemiology of Disasters (CRED)

A research unit of the University of Louvain, Belgium.

Related categories: 3.2, 4.2, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

certificate authority

A trusted entity that issues digital certificates. The Certificate Authority conducts a vetting process to ensure that the holder of the digital certificate is who they claim to be. Digital certificates are an essential part of secure communication and play an important part in the PKI (Public Key Infrastructure).

Related categories: 1.1

NENA (USA National Emergency Number Association). NENA Glossary of 9-1-1 Terminology. Year of publication: 2021. Available from: https://nenawiki.org/wiki/NENA_Glossary_of_9-1-1_Terminology (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

certificate authority (CA)

In cryptography, the expressions certification authority, or certifier, or certifier, or the acronyms CA or CA, indicate a trusted entity, responsible for issuing and revoking certificates, using the electronic signature in them, for which public key cryptography is used.

Related categories: 2.2

certification

The provision by an independent body of written assurance (a certificate) that the product, service or system in question meets specific requirements.

Related categories: 1.1

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

ENAC. ENAC. ¿Qué diferencias hay entre acreditación y certificación ISO 9001?. Year of publication: 2022. Available from: https://www.enac.es/web/enac/acreditacion-o-certificacion-9001?p_p_id=MensajeCookie_WAR_Gestionportlet&p_p_lifecycle=1&p_p_state=normal&p_p_mode=view&_MensajeCookie_WAR_Gestionportlet_javax.portlet.action=aceptarTodas (Date of consultation: 03/03/2022)

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO website. Year of publication: 2022. Available from: <https://www.iso.org/certification.html> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

certified client

Related to supply chain: organization whose supply chain security management system has been certified/registered by a qualified third party

Related categories: 2.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

chain of command

A series of command, control, executive, or management positions in hierarchical order of authority.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

challenge

Contextual or environmental change that has the potential to impact upon the ability and capacity of an urban system to address emerging risks and opportunities

Related categories: 2.4, 3.2, 3.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

challenge handshake authentication protocol (CHAP)

An authentication protocol that can be used to verify the identity of a caller on a PPP link. CHAP authentication uses the notion of challenge and response, where the system that receives a call challenges the caller to prove its identity.

Related categories: 3.3

channel

Physical means of transmission of the message. It can be sound (radio), tactile (Braille), or visual (television), among others. The wireless communications we use daily belong to a physical medium such as air.

Related categories: 3.3

checklist

Written (or computerized) enumeration of actions to be taken by an individual or organization meant to aid memory rather than provide detailed instruction.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

chemical accident

Accidental release occurring during the production, transportation or handling of hazardous chemical substances.

Related categories: 3.1

United Nations, Department of Humanitarian Affairs. Internationally agreed glossary of basic terms related to Disaster Management. Year of publication: 1992. Available from: <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/004DFD3E15B69A67C1256C4C006225C2-dha-glossary-1992.pdf>

chemical agents classification

Classification of harmful chemicals may take several paths: (a) according to the degree of effect, e.g. harassing, lethal or incapacitating; (b) according to the route of entry, e.g. respiratory agents, cutaneous agents; (c) according to the duration of the hazard, e.g. persistent agents, nonpersistent, temporary.

Related categories: 3.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

chemical event

A manifestation of a disease or an occurrence that creates a potential for a disease as result of exposure to or contamination by a chemical agent.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

chemical hazard

Inherent property of a chemical having the potential to cause adverse effects when an organism, system, or population is exposed to that chemical.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

chemical incident

An uncontrolled release of a chemical from its containment.

Chemical incidents may result in harm to public health and the environment. They usually trigger a public health response, including for example, assessment of risk and/or provision of advice to authorities and the public. Chemical incidents may refer to anthropogenic events such as the explosion at a factory which stores or uses chemicals, contamination of the food or water supply with a chemical, an oil spill, a leak in a storage unit during transportation, an outbreak of disease that is (likely to be) associated with chemical exposure or a deliberate event where chemicals are used to harm people.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

chemoprophylaxis

The administration of chemotherapeutic medicaments to a susceptible or contaminated person or germ carrier for the purpose of preventing the development of a clinical infection in him.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

chief

The Incident Command System title for individuals responsible for management of functional Sections: Operations, Planning, Logistics, Finance/Administration, and Intelligence/Investigations (if established as a separate Section).

Related categories: 2.3, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

child

Every person under the age of 18 years (unless under national law applicable to the child, majority is attained earlier). The age limit, below which it should not be permitted to deprive a child of his or her liberty, should be determined by law.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

circuit route

The physical path between two terminal locations.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

circuit-switched networks

Circuit-switched is a type of network in which a physical path is obtained for and dedicated to a single connection between two end- points in the network for the duration of the connection. Ordinary voice phone service is circuit-switched.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

circulatory failure

An adverse situation in a person when the cardiovascular system cannot provide sufficient oxygen and nutrients to the body's vital organs and remove the used metabolites.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

civil defence

The system of measures, usually run by a governmental agency, to protect the civilian population in wartime, to respond to disasters, and to prevent and mitigate the consequences of major emergencies in peacetime.

Related categories: 4.4

United Nations, Department of Humanitarian Affairs. Internationally agreed glossary of basic terms related to Disaster Management. Year of publication: 1992. Available from: <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/004DFD3E15B69A67C1256C4C006225C2-dha-glossary-1992.pdf>

civil disturbance

A civil unrest activity such as a demonstration, riot, or strike that disrupts a community and requires intervention to maintain public safety.

Related categories: 3.1, 4.3

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

civil protection

Measures taken and systems implemented to preserve the lives and health of citizens, their properties and their environment from undesired events

Undesired events can include accidents, emergencies and disasters.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

civil protection assistance team

EU Civil Protection Mechanism teams, experts or modules intended for civil protection, with their equipment, as well as relief materials or supplies needed to mitigate the immediate consequences of a disaster.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014 . Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

civil rights

According to international laws, it is the right of everyone, without distinction of race, colour, nationality or ethnic origin, to enjoy civil equality before the law, notably the following rights: (a) the right to equal treatment before the tribunal and justice; (b) the right to security and protection; (c) political rights; (d) other civil rights, in particular: (i) freedom of movement and residence in one's State, (ii) to leave the country and return, (iii) nationality, (iv) marriage and choice of spouse, (v) own property, (vi) to inherit, (vii) freedom of thought, conscience and religion, (viii) opinion and expression, (ix) peaceful assembly and association; (e) economic, social and cultural rights, in particular (i) choice of work and employment, (ii) form and join trade unions, (iii) housing, (iv) public health, medical care, social security and social services, (v) education and training, (vi) equal participation in cultural activities; (f) the right of access to any place or service for the general public.

Related categories: 1.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

civil society

Wide range of individuals, groups of people, networks, movements, associations and organizations that manifest and advocate for the interests of their members and others

Related categories: 3.2, 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

civil society organization (CSO)

Formal association in which society voluntarily organizes around shared interests.

It includes political, cultural, environmental and faith-based organizations, as well as non-profit and non-governmental organizations.

CSOs are institutionalized organizations, bearing some form of legal status, that represent particular groups of society and are involved in service delivery.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

class of fire

Fires can be classified according to size, according to the kind of fuel, whether natural or manmade, domestic or industrial, etc. Four classes are distinguished according to the kind of fuel and the resulting type of extinguishing, as follows: Class A: Fires started from common combustibles, such as paper, wood, which require cooling, such as with water, retardants, etc. Class B: Fires involving combustibles or inflammable liquid or gases, which require air exclusion for extinction. Class C: Fires caused by electricity. Class D: Fires due to some combustible metal, such as sodium, potassium, which are extinguishable by heat absorption.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.8

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

clear text

Communication that does not use codes. Plain Language.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

client

Entity that hires, has formerly hired, or intends to hire an organization to perform security operations on its behalf, including, as appropriate, where such an organization subcontracts with another company or local forces

A client can be internal (e.g. another division) or external to the organization.

EXAMPLE: Consumer, contractor, end-user, retailer, beneficiary, purchaser.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.3, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

climate change

A change in the state of the climate that can be identified (for example by using statistical tests) by changes in the mean and / or the variability of its properties and that persists for an extended period, typically decades or longer.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

climatological hazard

A hazard caused by long-lived, meso- to macro-scale atmospheric processes ranging from intra-seasonal to multi-decadal climate variability.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

clinical integration

The extent to which patient care is coordinated across the system's different functions, activities and operating units.

The degree of coordination of care depends primarily on the patient's condition and the decisions made by his or her health team. Clinical integration includes horizontal and vertical integration.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

clinical practice guidelines

Systematic recommendations, based on the best available scientific knowledge, to guide the decisions of both professionals and patients regarding the most appropriate, efficient health interventions for addressing a specific health-related problem given specific circumstances.

Related categories: 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

cloud computing

Cloud computing is the delivery of different services through the Internet, including data storage, servers, databases, networking, and software. Cloud-based storage makes it possible to save files to a remote database and retrieve them on demand

Related categories: 3.3

cluster

1. A group of similar things; or a natural grouping of persons. 2. Group of humanitarian organizations, both UN and non-UN, in each of the main sectors of humanitarian action (water, health, shelter, logistics, etc.).

Related categories: 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

coastal flood

Higher-than-normal water levels along the coast caused by tidal changes or thunderstorms that result in flooding, which can last from days to weeks.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgLS5evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

coastal water

Water located in sea, ocean or estuarie

Related categories: 3.1

Rescue 3 Europe Ltd. Rescue 3 International - Water and Flood Rescue Manual v6.2020. Available from: <https://www.rescue3europe.com/student-downloads/water-and-flood-rescue-manual/>

cochrane database of systematic reviews (CDSR)

Online journal / database published by Cochrane (formerly the Cochrane Collaboration) containing Cochrane Reviews and the protocols for these.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

cochrane review

Systematic review published in the Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

code

System of signals or signs used for the transmission of the message. It represents the transmission language or the specific protocol to be used for the interpretation of the messages.

Related categories: 3.3

coding grid

Otherwise known as a coding scheme, this is an organization system for grouping coding labels or categories that will be used to code qualitative data.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

cognitive bias

Systematic deviation from norm or rationality in judgment when individuals create their own 'subjective reality' from their own perceptions.

Related categories: 1.1

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

cold chain

Temperature-controlled supply chain

Related categories: 3.5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

cold debrief

A debriefing session held after a period of time has passed following an exercise or incident, in order to discuss, with the benefit of hindsight, any observations and issues that may have been overlooked during a hot debrief.

Related categories: 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

cold wave

A period of abnormally cold weather. Typically a cold wave lasts two or more days and may be aggravated by high winds.

The exact temperature criteria for what constitutes a cold wave vary by location.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgLS55evtT8jBNi/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

collaborative software

(Also referred to as groupware or work ware support systems) is software designed to help people involved in a common task achieve their goals.

Collaborative software is the basis for computer supported cooperative work.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

collapse

To fall or shrink together abruptly and completely : fall into a jumbled or flattened mass through the force of external pressure

Related categories: 3.1

collective intelligence

Shared or group intelligence that emerges from the collaboration, collective efforts, and competition of many individuals.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

colour blindness

Total or partial inability of a person to differentiate between certain hues

Related categories: 3.2, 3.3, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

colour-code

Set of colours used symbolically to represent particular meanings

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 2.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

coma

Unconsciousness.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

command

1. The act of managing, directing, ordering, or controlling by virtue of explicit statutory, regulatory, or delegated authority. 2. The common short name for 'incident command', involving making decisions, implementing plans manage an incident, and controlling their effects.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

command and control (C&C)

Activities of target-orientated decision-making, including assessing the situation, planning, implementing decisions and controlling the effects of implementation on the incident

This process is continuously repeated.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

command and control system

1. System that supports effective emergency management of all available assets in a preparation, incident response, continuity and/or recovery process. 2. Incident management software controlled by remote commands.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.2, 3.3, 3.5, 3.6, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

command staff

The staff who report directly to the Incident Commander, including the Public Information Officer, Safety Officer, Liaison Officer, and other positions as required. They may have an assistant or assistants, as needed.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

Commission Expert Group on Capacities

A group that, amongst other things, supports the development of the European Civil Protection Pool. It consists of representatives of the Member State and Participating States in the Union Civil Protection Mechanism who have specific expertise with regard to different emergency response capacities.

The Commission discusses relevant operational or technical issues within this group before feeding the conclusions into the political discussions in the Civil Protection Committee.

The group meets on average once a year. Sub-groups work on specific topics, such as the certification guidelines for resources in the European Civil Protection Pool, the guidelines for the Technical Assistance and Support Teams, as well as the re-certification process for resources in the Pool.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Union, EU Civil Protection Mechanism. EU Civil Protection Mechanism official website. Available from: <https://ercportal.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ERCC-Response/CP-Pool#/> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

commodity

An economic good ready to be exchanged or exploited within a market.

Related categories: 3.5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

common alerting protocol (CAP)

A general format for exchanging emergency alerts, primarily designed as an interoperability standard for use among warning systems and other emergency information systems.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3, 3.8

NENA (USA National Emergency Number Association). NENA Glossary of 9-1-1 Terminology. Year of publication: 2021. Available from: https://nenawiki.org/wiki/NENA_Glossary_of_9-1-1_Terminology (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

Common Emergency Communication and Information System (CECIS)

System that enables communication and sharing of information between the ERCC and the contact points of the Member States and of other participants in the context of the European Union Civil Protection Mechanism.

The CECIS shall include the following three components: (a) a network layer, connecting the competent authorities and the contact points in Member States and the ERCC; (b) an application layer, consisting of the databases and other information systems necessary for the functioning of the

Union Mechanism and in particular those needed: (i) for communicating notifications, (ii) for ensuring communication and information sharing between the ERCC and competent authorities and the contact points, (iii) for disseminating lessons learnt from interventions;

(c) a security layer, consisting of the set of systems, rules and procedures necessary for ensuring the authenticity, integrity and confidentiality of the data stored in and exchanged via the CECIS.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.2, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 4.4

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 1313/2013/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32013D1313&from=EN>

common procedures

Standardized, specific actions to take in response to a variety of hazards, threats, or incidents. Examples include evacuation, shelter-in-place, etc.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

common terminology

Standardized words and phrases used to ensure consistency while allowing diverse incident management and support organizations to work together across a wide variety of incident management functions and hazard scenarios.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.2, 3.3

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

communicable disease

An illness caused by a specific infectious agent or its toxic products and transmitted from an infected person, animal or the environment (for example through water, food, fomites) to a susceptible host. Transmission can be direct or indirect.

Related categories: 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

communication

Data transmission between a transmitter and a receiver. In the context of geolocation, it focuses on location through satellite triangulation that is represented on a cartographic map.

Related categories: 2.2

communication and consultation

Continual and iterative processes that an organization conducts to provide, share or obtain information, and to engage in dialogue with interested parties and others regarding the management of risk

The information can relate to the existence, nature, form, likelihood, severity, evaluation, acceptability, treatment or other aspects of the management of risk and security operations management.

Consultation is a two-way process of informed communication between an organization and its interested parties or others on an issue prior to making a decision or determining a direction on that issue. Consultation is:

- *A process which impacts on a decision through influence rather than power; and*
- *An input to decision-making, not joint decision-making.*

Related categories: 2.2, 3.2, 3.3, 3.5, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

communication resources

Inventory of all public and private communication facilities: police, fire, military, government, private radio, amateur (HAM) radio operators, newspapers, other news media, television, telephone and telex, Internet, social network, satellite and other facilities that can be used in time of disaster.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.2, 3.3

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

communications impaired

A person who is deaf, hearing impaired, or speech impaired that requires use of assistive telecommunications technology.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

community

Group of associated organizations, individuals and groups sharing common interests

Members of a community gain their personal and social identity by sharing common beliefs, values and norms which have been developed by the community in the past and may be modified in the future. They exhibit some awareness of their identity as a group and share common needs and a commitment to meeting them.

Impacted communities are the groups of people and associated organizations affected by the provision of security services, projects or operations.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.1, 3.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

community surveillance

Starting point for event notification at the community level, generally done by a community worker; it can be active (looking for cases) or passive (re- porting cases).

Related categories: 2.2, 3.2

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

community vulnerability

Characteristics and conditions of individuals, groups or infrastructures that put them at risk for the destructive effects of a hazard

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

community-based disaster risk management

Promotes the involvement of potentially affected communities in disaster risk management at the local level. This includes community assessments of hazards, vulnerabilities and capacities, and their involvement in planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of local action for disaster risk reduction management.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

community-based early warning system

Community-based warning system, method to communicate information to the public through established networks

The warning system can consist of risk knowledge, monitoring and warning service, dissemination and communication, and response capability to avoid, reduce risks and prepare responses against disaster.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.2, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

community-based participatory research (CBPR)

A participatory approach to research that focuses on creating social change with a community through collaborative partnerships and shared decision-making.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

community-led research (CLR)

Often used interchangeably with community-based participatory research (CBPR).

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

companion rescue

Companion rescue refers to the rescue efforts made by the members of a group involved in an avalanche incident

Related categories: 3.4

Avalanche Canada . Avalanche Canada website. Available from: <https://www.avalanche.ca/glossary> (Date of consultation: 26/01/2022)

competence

Ability to apply knowledge and skills to achieve intended results

This constitutes one of the common terms and core definitions of the high level structure for ISO management system standards.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

complex disaster/emergency

A major disaster or complicated emergency situation affecting large civilian populations, which is further aggravated by intense political and/or military interferences, including war or civil strife, resulting in serious food shortage, epidemics, population displacements, poverty, loss of human liberties and significant increase in mortality, rendering the management of the situation very complex. Breakdown of government infrastructures hampers humanitarian aid. Examples: Afghanistan, Rwanda, Somalia. (Not to be confused with compound disaster.)

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

complex emergency

A disaster complicated by civil violence, government instability, macroeconomic collapse, population migration, elusive political solutions, etc., in which any emergency response has to be conducted in a difficult political and security environment, potentially involving a multi-sectoral, international response that goes beyond the mandate or capacity of any single agency.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

complexity

Condition of an organizational system with many diverse and autonomous but interrelated and interdependent components or parts where those parts interact with each other and with external elements in multiple end non-linear ways

Complexity is the characteristic of a system where behaviour cannot be determined only as the sum of individual variables behaviours.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

compound disaster

A disaster where the concurrent occurrence of more than one kind of major emergency at the same time and place magnifies, aggravates and compounds the destructive event. Example, the 2011 disaster in Japan represented an earthquake, a tsunami, a nuclear reactor failure and

a great number of deaths, all taking place on 11 March and in the same region, compounding the seriousness and complication of the disaster. (Not to be confused with complex disaster, where the political, conflict and military elements are predominant factors.).

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

comprehensive emergency management programme

A corporate or government programme that commits resources to a range of measures to implement prevention and mitigation; preparedness; response; and recovery (also disaster (risk) management programme).

Typically, this programme includes the full range of capacities for managing risks associated with emergencies and disasters.

Related categories: 3.2

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

comprehensive health services

Health services that are managed so as to ensure that people receive a continuum of health promotion, disease prevention, diagnosis, treatment and management, rehabilitation and palliative care services, through the different levels and sites of care within the health system, and according to their needs throughout the life course.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

comprehensive preparedness guide (CPG)

A guide designed to assist jurisdictions with developing emergency operations plans. It promotes a common understanding of the fundamentals of planning and decisionmaking to help emergency planners examine a hazard and produce integrated, coordinated, and synchronized plans.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

computer aided dispatch (CAD)

A computer based system, which aids PSAP Telecommunicators by automating selected dispatching and record keeping activities.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.3

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

computer telephone integration (CTI)

Integrating telephone function into a computing device.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

computer virus

A computer virus, much like a flu virus, is designed to spread from host to host and has the ability to replicate itself

Related categories: 3.3

computer worm

It is a type of malware that spreads copies of itself from computer to computer. A worm can replicate itself without any human interaction, and it does not need to attach itself to a software program in order to cause damage.

Related categories: 3.3

computing platform

In computing, a platform is a system that serves as a basis for operating certain hardware or software modules with which it is compatible. Such a system is defined by a standard around which a hardware architecture and a software platform are determined.

Related categories: 2.2

concept harmonization

Activity leading to the establishment of a correspondence between two or more closely related or overlapping concepts having professional, technical, scientific, social, economic, linguistic, cultural or other differences, in order to eliminate or reduce minor differences between them

The purpose of concept harmonization is to improve communication.

Related categories: 3.2

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 860:2007(en) Terminology work - Harmonization of concepts and terms. Year of publication: 2007. Available from: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:860:ed-3:v1:en> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

concept note

In simulation, project document outlining the exercise purpose, scope and objectives; the exercise methodology; the composition of the exercise management team; and the evaluation strategy and format.

Related categories: 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

concept of operations

A section or statement in an agency emergency plan that identifies policies, role and responsibilities, and how the structural or functional elements of the organization will work together to produce a coherent management response.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

conceptual framework

Analytical tool with several variations and contexts, which can be applied in different categories of work where an overall picture is needed.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

conclusion stage

A period during a SAR incident when SAR facilities return to their regular location and prepare for another mission

Related categories: 3.4

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icscc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

conference transfer

The capability to bridge a third party onto an existing call. Also known as three-way calling.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

confidentiality

Confidentiality is a set of rules that limits access or places restrictions on the use of certain types of information.

In data protection law, confidentiality is a ground of analysis (together with integrity and availability) of the impact that a given personal data flow has on fundamental rights.

Related categories: 1.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

conformity

Fulfilment of a requirement

This constitutes one of the common terms and core definitions of the high level structure for ISO management system standards.

Related categories: 1.1, 2.2, 3.3, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

confounder

Source of error in interpretation, which occurs when the effect of an exposure on an outcome is affected by another exposure, which is correlated with the first exposure.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

congestion control

A method of controlling traffic when there are insufficient resources to meet demand, for example more requests for calls than there are trunks. It may be achieved by rejecting requests, and/or diverting calls.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.3

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

consensus building

The process by which different stakeholders reach an overall agreement on a policy concern.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

consent

1. General: Voluntarily giving one's agreement or permission to a proposed plan, complying with another person's expressed desire or concurring with a plan of action. 2. Health care: All treatment or experimentation must have the patient's informed consent. Forced declarations, unconsented experiments, undesired treatment or actions are not permitted.

Related categories: 1.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

consequence

1. Outcome: outcome of an event affecting objectives. 2. Loss: loss of life, damage to property or economic disruption, including disruption to transport systems, that can reasonably be expected as a result of an attack on an organization in the supply chain or by the use of the supply chain as a weapon

A consequence can be certain or uncertain and can have positive or negative direct or indirect effects on objectives.

Consequences can be expressed qualitatively or quantitatively.

Any consequence can escalate through cascading and cumulative effects.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

contact tracing

The identification and follow-up of persons who may have come into contact with an infected person or infectious materials.

Related categories: 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

container

1. A standard shipping metallic box, of steel or aluminium, with double doors at one end, in use on sea routes, for easier handling and safe transportation of cargo. There are two types: the 20-ft container, 30 m³ capacity, 18 tons load and the 40 ft, 60 m³ capacity, 30 tons load.

Discarded containers have at times been transformed and used as dwellings in disaster or refugee areas. 2. A standard unit of software that packages up code and all its dependencies so the application runs quickly and reliably from one computing environment to another.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.5

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

contamination

The presence of an infectious or toxic agent of matter on a human or animal body surface, in or on a product prepared for consumption or on other inanimate objects, including conveyances, that may constitute a public health risk.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

context

1. The situation in which the communicative act takes place allows the interpretation of the message depending on the scenario. 2. External and internal factors to be taken into account when undertaking a capability assessment.

As applied to emergency risk management, context is described by a number of factors related to the setting, circumstances and environment of risks and events. The cultural, social, political, legal, regulatory, financial, technological, economic, natural and competitive environment - whether local, national, regional or international - and those factors related to the governance, organizational structure, roles, accountabilities, policies, objectives, and strategies that are in place to achieve those objectives. They also include the capabilities of and relationships between the internal and external actors and stakeholders.

Related categories: 3.3

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

contingency

Possible future event, condition or eventuality

Related categories: 3.1, 3.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

contingency planning

A management process that analyses disaster risks and establishes arrangements in advance to enable timely, effective and appropriate responses.

Contingency planning usually refers to planning for specific scenarios or events that results in organized and coordinated courses of action with clearly identified institutional roles and resources, information processes and operational arrangements for specific actors at times of need. Based on scenarios of possible emergency conditions or hazardous events, it allows key actors to envision, anticipate and solve problems that can arise during disasters. Contingency planning is an important part of overall preparedness. Contingency plans need to be regularly updated and exercised.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

continual improvement

Recurring activity to enhance performance

This constitutes one of the common terms and core definitions of the high level structure for ISO management system standards.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

continuity

Strategic and tactical capability, pre-approved by management, of an organization to plan for and respond to conditions, situations and events in order to continue operations at an acceptable predefined level

Continuity is the more general term for operational and business continuity to ensure an organization's ability to continue operating outside of normal operating conditions. It applies not only to for-profit companies, but to organizations of all types, such as non-governmental, public interest and governmental.

Related categories: 1.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

continuity of care

A term used to indicate one or more of the following attributes of care: 1. the provision of services that are coordinated across levels of care - primary care and referral facilities, across settings and providers. 2. the provision of care throughout the life cycle. 3. care that continues uninterrupted until the resolution of an episode of disease or risk. 4. the degree to which a series of discrete health care events are experienced by people as coherent and interconnected over time, and are consistent with their health needs and preferences.

Related categories: 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

continuity of operations

The ability to continue operations during and after a major disaster.

Related categories: 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

continuous data

Data that can take any value within a range.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

control

Measure that maintains and/or modifies risk

Controls include, but are not limited to, any process, policy, device, practice, or other conditions and/or actions which maintain and/or modify risk.

Controls cannot always exert the intended or assumed modifying effect

Related categories: 3.1, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

control (command)

The application of authority, combined with the capability to manage resources, in order to achieve defined objectives.

Refers to the overall direction of the activities, agencies or individuals concerned and operates horizontally across all agencies / organizations, functions and individuals.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

control chart

Graph used to study how a process changes over time.

Related categories: 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

control room

In simulation, also known as 'facilitation room', is the dedicated space from which the exercise management team manages and stages the exercise. The control room (in an office, room, tent or other suitable venue) is separate from the exercise participants' space.

Related categories: 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

convective storm

A type of meteorological hazard generated by the heating of air and the availability of moist and unstable air masses.

Convective storms range from localised thunderstorms (with heavy rain and/or hail, lightning, high winds, tornadoes) to meso-scale, multi-day events.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNi/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

convenience sampling

Type of non-probability sampling method where the sample is taken from a group of people who are easy to contact or reach.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

conveyance

Physical instrument of international trade that transports goods from one location to another

EXAMPLE: Box, pallet, cargo transport unit (3.1.27), cargo handling equipment, truck, ship, aircraft, railcar.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

cooperating agency

An agency supplying assistance other than direct operational or support functions or resources to the incident management effort.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

cooperation

Process of working or acting together for common interests and values based on agreement

The organizations agree by contract or by other arrangements to contribute with their resources to the incident response but keep independence concerning their internal hierarchical structure.

Related categories: 3.4, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

coordination

Way in which different organizations (public or private) or parts of the same organization work or act together in order to achieve a common objective

Coordination integrates the individual response activities of involved parties (including, for example, public or private organizations and government) to achieve synergy to the extent that the incident response has a unified objective and coordinates activities through transparent information sharing regarding their respective incident response activities.

All organizations are involved in the process to agree on a common incident response objective and accept to implement the strategies by this consensus decision-making process.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.3, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

coordination expert

A category of expert referred in article 41 of Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014, may include deputy team leaders, persons responsible for logistics and communications and other personnel as necessary.

If requested, the technical experts and the assessment experts may be incorporated into the coordination team in order to assist the team leader for the whole duration of a mission.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.3, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

Copernicus

An EU programme aimed at developing European information services based on satellite Earth Observation and in situ (non space) data. Copernicus is a user driven programme and the information services provided are available to its Users, mostly public authorities, on a full, open and free-of-charge basis.

Copernicus is an EU programme aimed at developing European information services based on satellite Earth Observation and in situ (non space) data.

Copernicus is implemented by the European Commission (EC) with the support from the European Space Agency (ESA) for the Space component and the European Environment Agency (EEA) for the in situ component.

The Copernicus Programme is served by dedicated satellites (the Copernicus Sentinel families) and a set of additional Contributing Missions (satellites run by various commercial and national agencies). Since the launch of Sentinel-1A in 2014, the European Union set in motion a process to place a constellation of almost 20 more satellites in orbit before 2030. This satellite data is complemented by and validated with in situ data.

Six Copernicus Services transform the full, free and open data into value-added information by processing and analyzing the data and transforming them into services and products such as informative maps and data sets: 1) The Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service. 2) The Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service. 3) The Copernicus Land Monitoring Service. 4) The Copernicus Climate Change Service. 5) The Copernicus Emergency Management Service. 6) The Copernicus Security Service.

The objective of Copernicus is to monitor and forecast the state of the environment on land, sea and in the atmosphere, in order to support climate change mitigation and adaptation strategies, the efficient management of emergency situations and the improvement of the security of every citizen. Information provided by Copernicus improves people's safety, e.g. by providing information on natural disasters such as forest fires or floods, and thus help to prevent the loss of lives and property, and damages to the environment.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 3.1, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 4.4

European Commission. European Commission official website. Available from: <https://emergency.copernicus.eu/mapping/ems/what-copernicus> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

coping capacity

The ability of people, organizations and systems using available skills and resources, to manage adverse conditions, risk or disasters.

The capacity to cope requires continuing awareness, resources and good management, both in normal times as well as during disasters or adverse conditions. Coping capacities contribute to the reduction of disaster risks.

Related categories: 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

core outcome set

Agreed standardized set of outcomes that should be measured and reported, as a minimum, in research in a specific topic area.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

correction

Action to eliminate a detected nonconformity

Related categories: 3.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

corrective action

Action to eliminate the cause(s) of a nonconformity and to prevent recurrence

This constitutes one of the common terms and core definitions of the high level structure for ISO management system standards.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

cost-benefit analysis

A comparison of costs and achieved benefits, where both costs and benefits are expressed in monetary terms. The usual rule in cost benefit analysis is for the benefit-cost ratio (B/C) to exceed unit or for $(B-C) > 0.33$

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

cost-benefit ratio

Indicator showing the relationship between the relative costs and benefits of a proposed intervention or project.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

cost-consequence analysis

Technique used to compare costs and outcomes by placing them in discrete categories.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

cost-effectiveness analysis

Technique used to compares costs measured in monetary terms with outcomes measured in natural units.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

cost-minimization analysis

Technique used to compare interventions based on costs measured in monetary terms.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

cost-utility analysis

Technique used to compare costs measured in monetary terms with consequences measured via a measure of health gain or utility.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

counterfeit

1. Verb: simulate, reproduce or modify a material good or its packaging without authorization.
2. Good: material good imitating or copying an authentic material good

Related categories: 3.1, 3.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

countermeasure

Action taken to lower the likelihood of a security threat scenario succeeding in its objectives, or to reduce the likely consequences of a security threat scenario

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 3.6, 4.3

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

coverage

Capacity of the duty-bearer to provide a service or product

It can be influenced by financial capacity, geospatial setting, and the normative and institutional frameworks.

Related categories: 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

credentialing

Providing documentation that identifies personnel and authenticates and verifies their qualification for a particular position. See Badging.

Related categories: 1.1

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

crisis

Unstable condition involving an impending abrupt or significant change that requires urgent attention and action to protect life, assets, property or the environment

Related categories: 3.2, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

crisis management

Holistic management process that identifies potential impacts that threaten an organization and provides a framework for building resilience, with the capability for an effective response that safeguards the interests of the organization's key interested parties, reputation, brand and value-creating activities, as well as effectively restoring operational capabilities

Crisis management also involves the management of preparedness, mitigation response, and continuity or recovery in the event of an incident, as well as management of the overall programme through training, rehearsals and reviews to ensure the preparedness, response and continuity plans stay current and up to date.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

crisis management team

Group of individuals functionally responsible for directing the development and execution of the response and operational continuity plan, declaring an operational disruption or emergency / crisis situation, and providing direction during the recovery process, both pre-and post-disruptive incident

The crisis management team can include individuals from the organization as well as immediate and first responders and interested parties.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.6, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

critical appraisal

Process for carefully and systematically examining research to judge its trustworthiness, value and relevance.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

critical control point (CCP)

Point, step or process at which controls can be applied and a threat or hazard can be prevented, eliminated or reduced to acceptable levels

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

critical customer

Entity, the loss of whose business would threaten the survival of an organization

Related categories: 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

critical facility

Physical structure, network or other asset that provide services that are essential to the social and economic functioning of a community or society

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

critical indicator

Quantitative, qualitative or descriptive measure used to assess the hazard being monitored to identify the potential for the development of an incident, accident or emergency

Critical indicators provide information about the most important integral characteristics of the structural state of a facility

Related categories: 2.3, 2.4, 3.1, 3.3, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

critical infrastructure

The physical structures, facilities, networks and other assets which provide services that are essential to the social and economic functioning of a community or society.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

Critical Infrastructure Warning Information Network (CIWIN)

Is one of the measures foreseen to facilitate the implementation of the European Programme for Critical Infrastructure Protection (EPCIP)

The CIWIN network has been developed as a Commission owned protected public internet based information and communication system, offering recognised members of the EU's CIP community the opportunity to exchange and discuss CIP-related information, studies and/or good practices across all EU Member States and in all relevant sectors of economic activity. The CIWIN portal, following its prototype and pilot phases, has been up and running since mid-January 2013.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.7, 3.8, 4.4

European Commission. European Commission official website. Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/networks/critical-infrastructure-warning-information-network-ciwin_en (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

critical product and service

Resource obtained from a supplier, which, if unavailable, would disrupt an organization's critical activities and threaten its survival

Critical products or services are essential resources to support an organization's high priority activities and processes identified in its business impact analysis

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

critical supplier

Provider of critical products or services

This includes an "internal supplier", who is part of the same organization as its customer

Related categories: 3.5, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

criticality analysis

Process designed to systematically identify and evaluate an organization's assets based on the importance of its mission or function, the group of people at risk, or the significance of an undesirable event or disruption on its ability to meet expectations

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

critically

Of essential importance with respect to objectives and / or outcomes

Related categories: 3.1, 3.6, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

cross-sectional study

Observational study that analyses data from a population or a subset at a specific point in time.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

crowd creation

A form of crowdsourcing that uses large numbers of people to co-create (such as Threadless).

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

crowd processing

A form of crowdsourcing that uses large numbers of people to process information independently, which become partially aggregated for quality assurance (such as ReCAPTCHA).

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

crowdsourcing

A method to harness the knowledge, creativity, or sheer manpower of a large number of people at once and can achieve this through crowd creation, crowd processing, crowd rating, or crowd solving.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

crush syndrome

A severe, life-threatening trauma caused by an extensive compression (crushing), e.g. by entrapment under rubble in an earthquake, resulting in massive destruction of muscle and bone, bleeding, fluid loss, with release of toxins (myoglobin) in the circulation and kidney damage.

Related categories: 3.3

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

custody

Period of time where an organization in the supply chain is directly controlling the manufacturing, handling, processing and transportation of goods and their related shipping information within the supply chain

Related categories: 3.5, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

damage

Consequence during and immediately after the hazardous event or disaster.

This is usually measured in physical units (e.g. square meters of housing, kilometres of roads, etc.), and describes the total or partial destruction of physical assets, the disruption of basic services and damages to sources of livelihood in the affected area.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

damage assessment/analysis

Detailed evaluation and determination of the actual damages caused by a disaster. Sn: damage analysis

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.8

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

damage classification

Evaluation and recording of damage to the built environment, structures, objects or facilities according to categories. 1. "Severe damage": damage that precludes further use of the structure, facility or object for its intended purpose. 2. "Moderate damage": degree of damage to principal members that would preclude effective use of the structure, facility, or object for its intended use, unless major repairs were made short of complete reconstruction. 3. "Light

damage”, such as broken window, slight damage to roof and siding, interior partitions blown down and cracked walls; the damage not being severe enough to preclude use of installation for the purpose for which it was intended.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

damage mitigation

Damage control. Decisions and measures taken to attenuate or lessen the extent of damage, of hardship and of suffering caused by disaster.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.6

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

data

Facts and figures as raw material, not analysed.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

data analysis

Systematic investigation of relevant, evidence-based information obtained in monitoring the process and its flow in a real or planned system

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.1, 3.3, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

data attribute

Descriptive information about features or elements contained in a database.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.3, 3.7

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

data base

An organized collection of information, typically stored in computer systems, comprised of fields, records (data) and indexes.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.3, 3.7

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

data dictionary

Set of information describing the contents, format, and structure of a database and the relationship between its elements.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.3

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

data domain

An enumerated listing or range of valid values that may be used as an attribute. If no Data Domain is provided, then any value that meets the format criteria may be used.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.3

NENA (USA National Emergency Number Association). NENA Glossary of 9-1-1 Terminology. Year of publication: 2021. Available from: https://nenawiki.org/wiki/NENA_Glossary_of_9-1-1_Terminology (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

data encryption standard (DES)

A symmetric-key 64-bit block data encryption method standardized by ANSI as ANSI X.3.92. DES uses a 56-bit key.

Related categories: 3.3

data mining

Practice of generating new information by examining large pre-existing databases.

Related categories: 3.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

data ownership

Data ownership refers to both the possession of and responsibility for information. Ownership implies power as well as control. The control of information includes the right to determine means and purposes of data processing (ie the ability to access, create, modify, package, derive benefit from, sell or remove data, as well as to assign these access privileges to others, for given purposes)

Related categories: 1.1

datacenter

It is a physical facility that organizations use to house their critical applications and data.

Related categories: 3.3

datum

A geographic point, line, or area used as a reference in search planning

Related categories: 2.2, 3.4, 3.7

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icsc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

dead

Persons confirmed as dead and persons missing and presumed dead.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

deaf

Partially or completely lacking in the sense of hearing.

Related categories: 5

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

deaf-blind

A term used to describe a person in whom hearing loss and vision impairment combine to interfere with his/her ability to function effectively in life. S/he may have either total or partial loss of both senses, or one

Related categories: 5

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

debrief

A critical examination of a completed operation or exercise in order to evaluate actions.

Related categories: 3.4, 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

debris

Any kind of natural or manufactured debris can find its way into the water. This can pose a hazard when traveling downstream into a rescue site. Debris can become an entrapment hazard. It can also collect on bridge abutments to form a strainer hazard

Related categories: 3.1

Rescue 3 Europe Ltd. Rescue 3 International - Water and Flood Rescue Manual v6.2020. Available from: <https://www.rescue3europe.com/student-downloads/water-and-flood-rescue-manual/>

debris avalanche

The sudden and very rapid downslope movement of unsorted mass of rock and soil.

There are two general types of debris avalanches: 1.- Cold debris avalanche: usually results from an unstable slope suddenly collapsing. 2. Hot debris avalanche: results from volcanic activity leading to slope instability and collapse.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

decentralization

Political reform designed to promote local autonomy, decentralization entails changes in authority and financial responsibility for health services. Hence, decentralization can have a large impact on health service performance.

There are several forms of decentralization affecting the health sector in different ways: 1. deconcentration, which transfers authority and responsibility from the central level of the Ministry of Health to its field offices. 2. delegation, which transfers authority and responsibility from the central level of the Ministry of Health to organizations not directly under its control. 3. devolution, which transfers authority and responsibility from the central level of the Ministry of Health to lower level autonomous units of government. 4. privatization, which involves the transfer of ownership and government functions from public to private bodies, which may consist of voluntary organizations and for-profit and not-for-profit private organizations, with varying degree of government regulation.

Related categories: 1.1

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

decentralized authority

Local authorities, distinct from the state's administrative authorities, that have a degree of self-government, elaborated in the framework of the law, with their own powers, resources and capacities to meet responsibilities, and with legitimacy underpinned by representative, elected local democratic structures that determine how power is exercised and that make local authorities accountable to citizens in their jurisdiction

Related categories: 1.1, 2.2, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

declaration of disaster

Official announcement made by the competent authorities declaring a state of emergency in the wake of a disaster and the need for special measures to cope with it. Certain donor countries and organizations cannot provide assistance unless a disaster has been officially declared by the stricken country and aid requested.

Related categories: 1.1, 3.1, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

decontamination

A procedure whereby health measures are taken to eliminate an infectious or toxic agent or matter on a human or animal body surface, in or on a product prepared for consumption or on other inanimate objects, including conveyances that may constitute a public health risk.

Related categories: 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

dedicated trunk

A telephone circuit used for a single purpose; such as transmission of 112 calls.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.3

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

deductive research

Technique for testing a hypothesis based on existing theory.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

deficit-based approach

An orientation toward looking at a situation or issue in terms of vulnerabilities, limitations, problems, or liabilities. The opposite of a deficit-oriented approach is an asset-oriented approach which looks at situations or issues in terms of potential resources that can contribute to a solution or existing systems and structures that can be built on to improve a situation or address the problem.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

delay

Anything that is done to delay transmission of the packets such as protocol conversion, queuing, etc.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

delegation of authority

A statement that the agency executive delegating authority and assigning responsibility provides to the Incident Commander. The delegation of authority can include priorities, expectations, constraints, and other considerations or guidelines, as needed.

Related categories: 1.1, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

Delphi study

Technique using a panel of experts to reach a consensus.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

demand (for health services)

1. The health care expectations expressed by individuals or communities. 2. The willingness and/or ability to seek, use and, in some settings, pay for services.

May be subdivided into expressed demand (equated with use) and potential demand. May be subdivided into rational demand (demand that corresponds to need) and irrational demand (demand that does not correspond to need).

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

demobilization

The orderly, safe, and efficient return of an incident resource to its original location and status.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.3, 3.8

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

demographic data

Data to describe the characteristics of a population (such as age, gender and socio-economic status).

Related categories: 3.2, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

demurrage

In transportation and storage, the rent in railway sheds. Penalty for keeping containers longer than allowed. Penalty for immobilization of a vessel longer than allowed for loading/unloading and payable by owners of the goods.

Related categories: 3.5

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

denial of service (DoS)

It is a type of cyber attack designed to disable, shut down or disrupt a network, website or service

Related categories: 3.3

deontology

The study and application of a particular profession's ethics.

Related categories: 1.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

department operations center (DOC)

An operations or coordination center dedicated to a single, specific department or agency. The focus of a DOC is on internal agency incident management and response. DOCs are often linked to and/or physically represented in a combined agency EOC by an authorized agent(s) for the department or agency.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

dependent variable

Variable whose value depends on that of another variable.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

deputy

A fully qualified individual who, in the absence of a superior, can be delegated the authority to manage a functional operation or to perform a specific task. In some cases, a deputy can act as relief for a superior, and, therefore, should be fully qualified in the position. Deputies generally can be assigned to the Incident Commander, EOC director, General Staff, and branch directors.

Related categories: 1.1

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from:

<https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

desinventar

Tool for generating National Disaster Inventories and constructing databases of damage, losses and effects of disasters.

Related categories: 3.2, 4.2, 4.4

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

dichotomous data

Data that can take one of two values.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

Diffie-Hellman protocol (DH)

An asymmetric cryptographic key agreement protocol that enables two users to exchange a secret key over an insecure communication medium without any prior information.

Related categories: 3.3

diffraction

A term attributed to various phenomena occurs when a wave encounters an obstacle or a slit. It is defined as the deflection of waves around the corners of a block or through the slit in the region of a geometric shadow of the obstacle.

Related categories: 3.3

digital elevation model (DEM)

3D representation of terrain.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

digital signature

A digital code that is attached to an electronically transmitted message that uniquely identifies the sender.

Related categories: 3.3

dimension reduction method

Explain a multivariate dataset using a smaller number of dimensions than the original one.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

direct budget support

Method of financing a partner country's budget through a transfer of resources from an external financing agency to the partner government's national treasury. The funds thus transferred are managed in accordance with the recipient's budgetary procedures.

Funds transferred to the national treasury for financing programmes or projects managed according to different budgetary procedures from those of the partner country, with the intention of earmarking the resources for specific uses, are not part of direct budget support.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

direct channel

Encrypted radio transmission between two entities to exchange information following a defined protocol.

Related categories: 3.3

direct cost

1. Internal cost of an activity or decision including cost of labour, other goods and services, capital (usually considered as a rental value) and consumables. Direct cost excludes external costs, productivity costs, uncompensated forgone earnings and elements of cost that may be undervalued by market prices. 2. All the goods, services and other resources that are consumed in the provision of a particular service or area (e.g. hospital supplies), including medical costs (e.g. payments to providers, material) and non- medical costs (e.g. transportation to hospital).

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

direct dispatch

The performance of 112 calls answering and dispatching by personnel at the primary PSAP.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

direct economic loss

The monetary value of total or partial destruction of physical assets existing in the affected area.

For the purposes of Sendai Framework reporting, direct economic loss is nearly equivalent to physical damage. Direct economic losses usually happen during the event or within the first few hours after the event and are often assessed soon after the event to estimate recovery cost and claim insurance payments. These are tangible and relatively easy to measure. Examples of physical assets that are the basis for calculating direct economic loss include homes, schools, hospitals, commercial and governmental buildings, transport, energy, telecommunications infrastructures and other infrastructure; business assets and industrial plants; and production such as crops, livestock and production infrastructure. They may also encompass environmental assets and cultural heritage.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

directional antenna

They transmit and receive electromagnetic energy better in particular directions compared to others. This radiation pattern is similar to the light produced by a torchlight. The antenna does not add power to the signal. On the contrary, it simply redirects the energy coming from the transmitter in a particular direction according to the frequency and transmission channel.

Related categories: 2.2

directly affected

People who have suffered injury, illness or other health effects; who were evacuated, displaced or relocated or have suffered direct damage to their livelihoods, economic, physical, social, cultural and environmental assets (United Nations General Assembly 2017).

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.7, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

disability-adjusted life year (DALY)

Population metric of life years lost to disease due to both morbidity and mortality.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

disaster

Situation where widespread human, material, economic or environmental losses have occurred that exceeded the ability of the affected organization, community or society to respond and recover using its own resources

Related categories: 2.2, 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 1313/2013/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32013D1313&from=EN>

disaster assessment

Survey of real or potential disaster to estimate the actual or expected damages and to make recommendations for preparedness, mitigation and relief action.

Related categories: 2.1, 3.1, 3.2, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

disaster health emergencies assistance team (DHEAT)

Team that assist with management of the public health sector in local municipalities affected by a disaster, through information collection, integration, analysis and sharing with fieldworkers.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

disaster impact

The total effect, including negative effects (e.g. economic losses) and positive effects (e.g. economic gains), of a hazardous event or a disaster.

The term includes economic, human and environmental impacts, and may include death, injuries, disease and other negative effects on human physical, mental and social well-being.

Related categories: 2.1, 3.1, 3.7, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

disaster legislation

The body of laws that govern and designate responsibility for disaster management in the nation concerning the various phases of disaster. Attempts are currently being made to introduce international disaster legislation.

Related categories: 1.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

disaster loss database

A set of systematically collected records about hazardous event or disaster occurrence, damages, losses and impacts, compliant with the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015 - 2030 monitoring minimum requirements.

Related categories: 3.2, 4.2

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

disaster management

The organization, planning and application of measures preparing for, responding to and recovering from disasters.

Disaster management may not completely avert or eliminate the threats; it focuses on creating and implementing preparedness and other plans to decrease the impact of disasters and "build back better. Failure to create and apply a plan could lead to damage to life, assets and lost revenue.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.6, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

disaster medical assistance team (DMAT)

Specially trained medical professional teams comprising up to five members, including medical doctors, nurses and logisticians, who are able to work together using a single car.

Related categories: 3.2, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

disaster medical coordinator

Person officially assigned by a prefecture to coordinate the activities of external and internal medical assistance teams.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.4, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

disaster medicine

The study and collaborative application of various health disciplines – e.g. paediatrics, epidemiology, communicable diseases, nutrition, public health, emergency surgery, social medicine, military medicine, community care, international health – to the prevention, immediate response and rehabilitation of the health and humanitarian problems arising from disaster, in cooperation with other disciplines involved in comprehensive disaster management.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

disaster psychiatry assistance team (DPAT)

Team to assist psychiatric hospitals and support surge mental health needs in areas affected by a disaster by assessing local psychiatric needs, and collaborating with DMAT and other assistance teams and local psychiatric facilities to provide high quality psychiatric medicine.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.6, 3.7, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

disaster recovery

A specific set of procedures designed to reduce the damaging consequences of unexpected events resulting in the loss of 112 capabilities.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

Disaster Relief Emergency Fund (DREF)

One of the 4 tools within the EU Emergency Toolbox. It belongs to the International Federation of the Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC). It supports national Red Cross and Red Crescent societies in the immediate aftermath of a disaster. We contribute to this fund to a maximum of €200,000 per action.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Commission, European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations ECHO. European Commission official website. Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/echo/emergency-toolbox-eu-funding-sudden-onset-humanitarian-crises_en (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

disaster response

Emergency response. Actions taken directly before, during or immediately after a disaster in order to save lives, reduce health impacts, ensure public safety and meet the basic subsistence needs of the people affected.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.6, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

disaster risk

The potential loss of life, injury, or destroyed or damaged assets which could occur to a system, society or a community in a specific period of time, determined probabilistically as a function of hazard, exposure, vulnerability and capacity.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

disaster risk assessment

A qualitative or quantitative approach to determine the nature and extent of disaster risk by analysing potential hazards and evaluating existing conditions of exposure and vulnerability and capacity that together could harm people, property, services, livelihoods and the environment on which they depend.

Disaster risk assessments include: the identification of hazards; a review of the technical characteristics of hazards such as their location, intensity, frequency and probability; the analysis of exposure and vulnerability, including the physical, social, health, environmental and economic dimensions; and the evaluation of the effectiveness of prevailing and alternative coping capacities with respect to likely risk scenarios.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.3, 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

disaster risk governance

The system of institutions, mechanisms, policy and legal frameworks and other arrangements to guide, coordinate and oversee disaster risk reduction and related areas of policy.

Good governance needs to be transparent, inclusive, collective and efficient to reduce existing disaster risks and avoid creating new ones.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

disaster risk information

Comprehensive information on all dimensions of disaster risk, including hazards, exposure, vulnerability and capacity, related to persons, communities, organizations and countries and their assets.

Disaster risk information includes all studies, information and mapping required to understand the disaster risk drivers and underlying risk factors.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.3, 2.5, 3.1, 3.7, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

disaster risk management

The application of disaster risk reduction policies and strategies to prevent new disaster risk, reduce existing disaster risk and manage residual risk, contributing to the strengthening of resilience and reduction of disaster losses.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.1, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

disaster risk management plans

Plans that set out the goals and specific objectives for reducing disaster risks together with related actions to accomplish these objectives.

They should be guided by the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030 and other relevant global, regional and national frameworks. They should be considered and coordinated within relevant development plans, resource allocations and programme activities. National-level plans need to be specific to each level of administrative responsibility and adapted to the different social and geographical circumstances that are present. The time frame and responsibilities for implementation and the sources of funding should be specified in the plan. Linkages to sustainable development and climate change adaptation plans should be made where possible.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.3, 3.1, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

disaster risk reduction

Policy aimed at preventing new and reducing existing disaster risk and managing residual risk, all of which contribute to strengthening resilience and therefore to the achievement of sustainable development

Related categories: 2.2, 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

disaster risk reduction strategies and policies

Strategies and policies that define goals and objectives across different timescales and with concrete targets, indicators and timeframes.

In line with the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030, these should be aimed at preventing the creation of disaster risk, the reduction of existing risk and the strengthening of economic, social, health and environmental resilience.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

disasters convergence

A common phenomenon in disaster situations, people moving in many different directions but converging in mainly two different ways: (1) internal convergence: towards hospitals, casualty points, rescue centres, morgue, television stations; (2) external convergence: aid suppliers, NGOs, disaster responders, the press, etc. Proper management of these diverse movements is important.

Related categories: 3.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

discussion-based exercises

These types of exercises typically highlight existing plans, policies, mutual aid agreements, and procedures, and can be used as tools to familiarize agencies and personnel with current or expected capabilities. Discussion-based exercises include seminars, workshops, tabletops, and games.

Related categories: 4.1

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

disease

An illness or medical condition, irrespective of origin or source, that presents or could present significant harm to human.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5159fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNi/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

disease management

Coordinated information and intervention system for populations that suffer from diseases that share the value of self-care in their treatment and control. They focus on patients with specific diagnoses; they target diseases that are highly prevalent, that require intensive or high-cost care, or that represent high drug costs; and they focus on interventions whose results can be measured and for which significant variations in clinical practice have been described.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

disease prevention

Disease prevention covers measures not only to prevent the occurrence of disease, such as risk factor reduction, but also to arrest its progress and reduce its consequences once established.

Related categories: 3.2

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

dispatch

The ordered movement of a resource or resources to an assigned operational mission, or an administrative move from one location to another.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

dispersion

The effect of radiofrequency waves when they strike an object causes the initial energy to be reflected and thus spread or "scattered" in many directions. Thus, the performance of the solution will be drastically attenuated by the splitting of the energy.

Related categories: 3.3

disruption

Incident, whether anticipated or unanticipated, that causes an unplanned, negative deviation from the expected delivery of products and services according to an organization's objectives

Related categories: 2.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

disruptive event

Occurrence or change that interrupts planned activities, operations or functions, whether anticipated or unanticipated

Related categories: 3.1, 3.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

distress alert

The reporting of a distress incident to a unit which can provide or coordinate assistance

Related categories: 3.8

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icssc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

document

Information and the medium on which it is contained

The medium can be paper, magnetic, electronic or optical computer disc, photograph or master sample, or a combination thereof.

A set of documents, for example specifications and records, is frequently called "documentation".

Related categories: 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

documented information

Information required to be controlled and maintained by an organization and the medium on which it is contained

Documented information can be in any format and media, and from any source.

Documented information can refer to:

- *The management system, including related processes;*
- *Information created in order for the organization to operate (documentation);*
- *Evidence of results achieved (records).*

Note 3 to entry: This constitutes one of the common terms and core definitions of the high level structure for ISO management system standards.

Related categories: 3.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

domain name system (DNS)

Hierarchical and decentralized naming system used to identify computers, services, and other resources reachable through the Internet or other Internet Protocol (IP) networks. The resource records contained in the DNS associate domain names with other forms of information. These are most commonly used to map human-friendly domain names to the numerical IP addresses computers need to locate services and devices using the underlying network protocols, but have been extended over time to perform many other functions as well.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

downstream

Handling, processing and movement of goods when they are no longer in the custody of the organization in the supply chain

Related categories: 3.1, 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

drift

Movement of a search object caused by environmental forces

Related categories: 3.4

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icssc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

drill

Activity that practises a particular skill and often involves repeating the same thing several times

EXAMPLE: A fire drill to practise safely evacuating a building on fire.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3, 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

drone

A pilotless distance-guided military aircraft used for targeting and for reconnaissance.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.3, 2.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

drought

An extended period of unusually low precipitation that produces a shortage of water for people, animals and plants. Drought is different from most other hazards in that it develops slowly, sometimes even over years, and its onset is generally difficult to detect.

Drought is not solely a physical phenomenon because its impacts can be exacerbated by human activities and water supply demands. Drought is therefore often defined both conceptually and operationally. Operational definitions of drought, meaning the degree of precipitation reduction that constitutes a drought, vary by locality, climate and environmental sector.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

dual stack

A TCP/IP protocol stack that enables both IPv4 and IPv6 protocols to operate on the same network infrastructure without the use of tunneling mechanism.

Related categories: 2.2

duplex

A duplex communication system is a point-to-point system composed of two or more connected parties or devices that can communicate with one another in both directions.

Related categories: 2.2

dust storm

Large amount of dust carried aloft by strong winds.

A dust storm is also characterised by strong winds but carries smaller particles of dust rather than sand over an extensive area.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

duty of care

Moral or legal obligation to ensure the safety, well-being or interests of others

Related categories: 2.3, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

duty-bearer

Individual who has a particular obligation or responsibility to respect, promote and realize human rights, and to abstain from human rights violations

The term is most commonly used to refer to state actors, but non-state actors can also be considered as duty-bearers.

Depending on the context, individuals (e.g. parents), local organizations, private companies, aid donors and international institutions can also be duty-bearers.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

dynamic context

An everchanging environment in which complex adaptive systems operate.

Related categories: 3.6, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

dynamic host configuration protocol (DHCP)

Network management protocol used on Internet Protocol (IP) networks for automatically assigning IP addresses and other communication parameters to devices connected to the network using a client-server architecture. The technology eliminates the need for individually configuring network devices manually, and consists of two network components, a centrally installed network DHCP server and client instances of the protocol stack on each computer or device. When connected to the network, and periodically thereafter, a client requests a set of parameters from the DHCP server using the DHCP protocol.

Related categories: 2.2

dynamic metadata

Data associated with a digital image aside from the pixel values, which can change for each frame of a video sequence

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.4, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

dynamic reconfiguration (DR)

Dynamic reconfiguration is the process of adding, deleting, or moving resources within your network configuration without deactivating the affected major node.

Related categories: 2.2

dynamic routing

Dynamic routing, also called adaptive routing, is a process where a router can forward data via a different route for a given destination based on the current conditions of the communication circuits within a system. The term is most commonly associated with data networking to describe the capability of a network to 'route around' damage, such as loss of a node or a

connection between nodes, so long as other path choices are available. Dynamic routing allows as many routes as possible to remain valid in response to the change.

Related categories: 2.2

dyspnoea

A respiratory symptom that may indicate shortness of breath, or breathlessness, tightness in the chest, feeling of suffocation, pain on breathing or feeling of not getting enough air.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

E.164 number

E.164 is an international numbering plan for public telephone systems in which each assigned number contains a country code (CC), a national destination code (NDC), and a subscriber number (SN). There can be up to 15 digits in an E.164 number.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

early warning

Provision of information through local networks, allowing affected individuals to take action to avoid or reduce risks and to prepare responses

Related categories: 3.2, 3.3, 3.5, 3.8, 4.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 1313/2013/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32013D1313&from=EN>

early warning system

1. An integrated system of hazard monitoring, forecasting and prediction, disaster risk assessment, communication and preparedness activities systems and processes that enables individuals, communities, governments, businesses and others to take timely action to reduce disaster risks in advance of hazardous events.

2. A specific procedure in disease surveillance to detect any abnormal occurrence or departure from the usual or normally observed frequency of phenomena as early as possible.

Effective “end-to-end” and “people-centred” early warning systems may include four interrelated key elements: (1) disaster risk knowledge based on the systematic collection of data and disaster risk assessments; (2) detection, monitoring, analysis and forecasting of the hazards and possible consequences; (3) dissemination and communication, by an official source, of authoritative, timely, accurate and actionable warnings and associated information on likelihood and impact; and (4) preparedness at all levels to respond to the warnings received. These four interrelated components need to be coordinated within and across sectors and multiple levels for the system to work effectively and to include a feedback mechanism for continuous improvement. Failure in one component or a lack of coordination across them could lead to the failure of the whole system.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.3, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

early warning, alert and response system (EWARS)

The organized mechanism to detect as early as possible any abnormal occurrence or any divergence from the usual or normally observed frequency of phenomena.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.3, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

earthquake

A sudden break within the upper layers of the earth, sometimes breaking the surface, resulting in the vibration of the ground, which where strong enough will cause the collapse of buildings and destruction of life and property

Related categories: 3.1

United Nations, Department of Humanitarian Affairs. Internationally agreed glossary of basic terms related to Disaster Management. Year of publication: 1992. Available from: <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/004DFD3E15B69A67C1256C4C006225C2-dha-glossary-1992.pdf>

earthquake hypocentre

The place inside the earth where the faulting which is associated with the earthquake originated.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.7

United Nations, Department of Humanitarian Affairs. Internationally agreed glossary of basic terms related to Disaster Management. Year of publication: 1992. Available from: <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/004DFD3E15B69A67C1256C4C006225C2-dha-glossary-1992.pdf>

ecall

Emergency call generated either automatically via activation of in-vehicle sensors or manually by the vehicle occupants.

When activated it provides notification and relevant location information to the most appropriate 'Public Safety Answering Point', by means of mobile wireless communications networks, carries a defined standardised Minimum Set of Data (MSD) notifying that there has been an incident that requires response from the emergency services, and establishes an audio channel between the occupants of the vehicle and the most appropriate 'Public Safety Answering Point'.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

ecall generator

Occupant of a vehicle or equipment within a vehicle that has cause to trigger an 'eCall' transaction by automatic or manual means.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

ecall identifier

One of two information element bits (flags) included in the emergency call set-up message that may be used by the mobile network to filter and route automatically and manually initiated eCalls to a designated PSAP.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

ecall minimum set of data

Standardised data concept comprising data elements of relevant vehicle generated data essential for the performance of the 'eCall' service.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

ecall service

End-to-end emergency service to connect occupants of an affected vehicle to the most appropriate PSAP via an audio link across a PLMN together with the transfer of a 'Minimum Set of Data' to the PSAP.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

economic diversity

Extent to which economic activity of a given defined geography is distributed among a number of categories such as industries, sectors, skill levels and employment levels

Related categories: 3.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

economic evaluation

Structured way to evaluate costs and consequences of a programme or policy compared with an alternative course of action.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

economic impact study

Study that quantifies the costs and consequences of past or potential events.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

economic loss

Total economic impact that consists of direct economic loss and indirect economic loss.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

ecosystem

Dynamic complex of plant, animal and micro-organism communities and their non-living environment (e.g. soil, air, sunlight) interacting as a functioning unit of nature

Everything that lives in an ecosystem is dependent on the other species and elements that are also part of that ecological community.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

ecosystem services

Benefit people obtain from ecosystems

These include: provisioning services such as food, water, timber and fibre; regulating services that affect the climate, floods, disease, waste generation and water quality; cultural services that provide recreational, aesthetic and spiritual benefits and supporting services such as soil formation, photosynthesis and nutrient cycling.

Related categories: 3.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

effectiveness

Extent to which planned activities are realized and planned results achieved

This constitutes one of the common terms and core definitions of the high level structure for ISO management system standards.

Related categories: 2.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

efficacy

The extent to which a specific intervention, procedure, regimen or service, produces the intended result under ideal conditions.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

efficiency

The capacity to produce the maximum output for a given input.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

electrical burn

Burn damage to the tissues by passage of an electric current which is converted into thermal energy. This energy is proportional to the square of the current intensity in amperes and to the resistance of the conductor in ohms. The effects caused by electric energy depend on the type of circuit, voltage and amperage of current, resistance, route of the current and duration of contact.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

electrocution

Severe electrical burn with the strong current passing through the body, often causing death.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

electronic bibliographic databases

Online sources of scientific literature.

Related categories: 3.2, 4.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

electronic tattoo

Skin patch with technology for measuring health parameters.

Related categories: 2.5

emergency

Sudden, urgent, usually unexpected occurrence or event requiring immediate action

An emergency is usually a disruption or condition that can often be anticipated or prepared for, but seldom exactly foreseen.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.8, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Emergency Response Rramework. Year of publication: 2017. ISBN: 9789241512299. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241512299>

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

emergency alert systems

Radio or television based broadcast of emergency event information.

Related categories: 3.3, 3.8

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

emergency call

A telephone request for public safety agency emergency services which requires immediate action to save a life, to report a fire or to stop a crime. May include other situations as determined locally.

Related categories: 3.3, 3.8

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

emergency care

Health care of all age groups, with injuries or acute health care requirements. It includes the initial assessment, resuscitation, operative (and anaesthetic) care, postoperative care and rehabilitation of the injured as well as emergency care of any associated co-morbidities or illness.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.8

World Health Organization, Health Cluster. Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. Year of publication: 2013. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

emergency communications center

A set of call takers operating under common management which receives emergency calls for service and asynchronous event notifications and processes those calls and events according to a specified operational policy.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.3, 3.8

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

emergency coordination centre

A type of EOC that has no direct, tactical or operational function, but which serves as a point of control and coordination for the strategic allocation of resources and management of policy issues.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.3, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

emergency data exchange language (EDXL)

A suite of XML-based messaging standards that facilitate emergency information sharing between government entities and the full range of emergency-related organizations.

The Emergency Data Exchange Language (EDXL) is a broad initiative developed as a royalty-free standard by the OASIS International Open Standards Consortium to create an integrated framework for a wide range of emergency data exchange standards to support operations, logistics, planning and finance.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3

OASIS Open. OASIS Open website. Year of publication: 2022. Available from: https://www.oasis-open.org/committees/tc_home.php?wg_abbrev=emergency (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

emergency data exchange language - common alerting protocol (EDXL-CAP)

OASIS Standard that provides a simple but general format for exchanging all-hazard emergency alerts and public warnings over all kinds of networks.

CAP allows a consistent warning message to be disseminated simultaneously over many different warning systems, thus increasing warning effectiveness while simplifying the warning task. CAP also facilitates the detection of emerging patterns in local warnings of various kinds, such as might indicate an undetected hazard or hostile act. And CAP provides a template for effective warning messages based on best practices identified in academic research and real-world experience.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3

OASIS Open, OASIS Emergency Management Technical Committee. Common Alerting Protocol Version 1.2. Year of publication: 2010. Available from: <http://docs.oasis-open.org/emergency/cap/v1.2/CAP-v1.2-os.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

emergency data exchange language - distribution element (EDXL-DE)

OASIS standard which provides flexible message-distribution for emergency information systems' data sharing. to facilitate the routing of any properly formatted XML emergency message to recipients.

The Distribution Element may be thought of as a "container". It provides the information to route "payload" message sets (such as Alerts or Resource Messages), by including key routing information such as distribution type, geography, incident, and sender/recipient IDs.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3

OASIS Open, OASIS Emergency Management Technical Committee. Emergency Data Exchange Language (EDXL) Distribution Element, v. 1.0. Year of publication: 2006. Available from: http://docs.oasis-open.org/emergency/edxl-de/v1.0/EDXL-DE_Spec_v1.0.pdf (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

emergency data exchange language - hospital availability exchange (EDXL-HAVE)

OASIS standard message for data sharing among emergency information systems using the XML-based Emergency Data Exchange Language (EDXL) which allows a hospital's status, services, and resources (including bed capacity, emergency department status, and available service coverage) to be communicated.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3

OASIS Open, OASIS Emergency Management Technical Committee. Emergency Data Exchange Language (EDXL) Hospital Availability Exchange (HAVE) Version 1.0. Year of publication: 2007. Available from: http://docs.oasis-open.org/emergency/edxl-have/pr03/emergency_edxl_have-1.0-spec-pr03.pdf (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

emergency data exchange language - resource messaging (EDXL-RM)

OASIS standard which describes a suite of standard messages for sharing data among emergency and other information systems that deal in requesting and providing emergency equipment, supplies, people and teams.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3

OASIS Open, OASIS Emergency Management Technical Committee. Emergency Data Exchange Language Resource Messaging (EDXL-RM) 1.0. Year of publication: 2009. Available from: <http://docs.oasis-open.org/emergency/edxl-rm/v1.0/os/EDXL-RM-v1.0-OS.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

emergency data exchange language - situation reporting (EDXL-SitRep)

OASIS standard which describes a set of standard reports and elements that can be used for data sharing among emergency information systems, and that provide incident information for situation awareness on which incident command can base decisions.

The purpose of EDXL-SitRep is to guide more effective preparation, response, management and recovery through seamless summary-level information-sharing before, during and after emergencies and disasters of any scale.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3

OASIS Open, OASIS Emergency Management Technical Committee. Emergency Data Exchange Language Situation Reporting (EDXL-SitRep) Version 1.0. Year of publication: 2015. Available from: <http://docs.oasis-open.org/emergency/edxl-sitrep/v1.0/csprd03/edxl-sitrep-v1.0-csprd03.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

emergency data exchange language - tracking of emergency patients (EDXL-TEP)

OASIS XML messaging standard primarily for exchange of emergency patient and tracking information from the point of patient encounter through definitive care admission or field release.

TEP supports patient tracking across the Emergency Medical Services (EMS) care continuum, as well as hospital evacuations and patient transfers, providing real-time information to responders, Emergency Management, coordinating organizations and care facilities in the chain of care and transport.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3

OASIS Open, OASIS Emergency Management Technical Committee. Emergency Data Exchange Language (EDXL) Tracking of Emergency Patients (TEP) Version 1.1. Year of publication: 2015. Available from: <http://docs.oasis-open.org/emergency/edxl-tep/v1.1/csprd01/edxl-tep-v1.1-csprd01.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

Emergency Events Database (EM-DAT)

Emergency Events Database, which is a free, searchable database of data on disasters, produced by CRED.

Related categories: 3.2, 4.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

emergency health kit

Basic drugs and medical equipment calculated for the emergency needs of a population of 10,000 persons over three months. One pre-packaged kit contains 10 identical smaller kits, each for 1,000 persons.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.5

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

emergency life support

Urgent measures taken to keep a critically ill patient alive, usually in a hospital critical care unit.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

emergency management

Overall approach for preventing emergencies and managing those that occur

In general, emergency management utilizes a risk management approach to prevention, preparedness, response and recovery before, during and after potentially destabilizing events) and/or disruptions.

Related categories: 1.1, 3.2, 3.6, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

emergency management capability

Overall ability to effectively manage prevention, preparedness, response and recovery before, during and after potentially destabilizing or disruptive events

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.6, 3.7, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

emergency management cycle

Comprehensive approach to emergency and disaster risk management. Comprises a range of measures across prevention and mitigation; preparedness; response; and recovery.

Related categories: 3.2

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

emergency medical information system (EMIS)

System used to share real-time information among fieldworkers, headquarters and central government during a disaster.

Related categories: 3.3, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

emergency medical service (EMS)

Service, including personnel, facilities, and equipment required to ensure proper medical care for the sick and injured from the time of injury to the time of final disposition (which includes medical disposition within a hospital, temporary medical facility, or special care facility; release from the site; or being declared dead).

Related categories: 3.4

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

emergency medical system (EMS)

The aggregate of services, resources and personnel required to deliver medical care to those with an unpredicted, immediate health need outside established medical facilities.

EMS specifically includes those services immediately required to ensure proper medical care and specialized treatment for patients in a hospital and coordination of related hospital services.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

United Nations, Department of Humanitarian Affairs. Internationally agreed glossary of basic terms related to Disaster Management. Year of publication: 1992. Available from: <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/004DFD3E15B69A67C1256C4C006225C2-dha-glossary-1992.pdf>

emergency medical team (EMT)

Groups of health professionals (doctors, nurses, paramedics, etc.) that treat patients affected by an emergency or disaster.

They come from government, charities (NGOs), militaries and international organizations such as the International Red Cross/Red Crescent movement. They work to comply with the classification and minimum standards set by WHO and its partners, and come trained and self-sufficient so as not to burden the national system.

Related categories: 3.4, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

emergency notification systems

General category for any systems used to notify persons of an emergency. May include changeable message signs, sirens, telephone and other media.

Related categories: 3.3, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

emergency operations center (EOC)

Officially designated facility for the direction and coordination or all activities during the response phase a disaster. The physical location at which the coordination of information and resources to support incident management (on-scene operations) activities normally takes place.

An EOC may be a temporary facility or may be located in a more central or permanently established facility, perhaps at a higher level of organization within a jurisdiction. EOCs may be organized by major functional disciplines (e.g., fire, law enforcement, medical services), by jurisdiction (e.g., Federal, State, regional, tribal, city, county), or by some combination thereof.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

United Nations, Department of Humanitarian Affairs. Internationally agreed glossary of basic terms related to Disaster Management. Year of publication: 1992. Available from: <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/004DFD3E15B69A67C1256C4C006225C2-dha-glossary-1992.pdf>

emergency operations plan (EOP)

An ongoing plan for responding to a wide variety of potential hazards.

An EOP describes how people and property will be protected; details who is responsible for carrying out specific actions; identifies the personnel, equipment, facilities, supplies, and other resources available; and outlines how all actions will be coordinated.

Related categories: 3.2

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

emergency preparedness resource inventory

Online tool that can assess the regional supply of critical resources, prepare for incident response, identify deficiencies in services, and support resource acquisition decisions.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

emergency relief

1. Urgent aid given to relieve suffering and hardship arising from a sudden or unexpected event. 2. Immediate assistance given to persons who are deprived of the essential needs of life following a natural or man-induced disaster.

Related categories: 3.5, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC)

EU response coordination center that ensures 24/7 operational capacity, and serve the Member States and the Commission in pursuit of the objectives of the Union Mechanism.

The Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC) is the heart of the EU Civil Protection Mechanism. It coordinates the delivery of assistance to disaster-stricken countries, such as relief items, expertise, civil protection teams and specialised equipment.

The centre ensures the rapid deployment of emergency support and acts as a coordination hub between all EU Member States, the 6 additional Participating States, the affected country, and civil protection and humanitarian experts.

The ERCC operates 24/7 and can help any country inside or outside the EU affected by a major disaster upon request from the national authorities or a UN body.

Related categories: 3.3, 3.6, 3.7, 4.4

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 1313/2013/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32013D1313&from=EN>

European Union, EU Civil Protection Mechanism. EU Civil Protection Mechanism official website. Year of publication: 2022. Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/echo/what/civil-protection/emergency-response-coordination-centre-ercc_en (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

emergency response location

A location to which a 112 emergency response team may be dispatched. The location should be specific enough to provide a reasonable opportunity for the emergency response team to quickly locate a caller anywhere within it.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

emergency response personnel

First responder.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

emergency response plan

A document describing how an agency or organization will manage its responses to emergencies of various types, by providing a description of: 1. The objectives, policy and concept of operations for the response to an emergency. 2. The structure, authorities and responsibilities for a systematic, coordinated and effective response.

In this context, emergency response plans are agency- or jurisdiction-specific, and detail the resources, capacities and capabilities that the agency or organization will employ in its response. This is also referred to as an emergency or operations plan.

Related categories: 3.2

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

emergency response unit (ERU)

IFRC expert personnel and equipment to prevent and detect people's health needs, and to provide both clinical and public health response in a large-scale emergency, or when a National Society's capacity is stretched.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

World Health Organization, Health Cluster. IFRC website. Available from: <https://www.ifrc.org/emergency-health> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

emergency services ip network (ESInet)

An IP-based inter-network (network of networks) shared by all agencies which may be involved in any emergency.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

emergency telecommunications (EMTEL)

The concept of EMTEL addresses a broad spectrum of aspects related to the provisioning of telecommunications services in emergency situations.

Emergency situations may range from a narrow perspective of an individual being in a state of personal emergency (with need to make an emergency call due to sudden illness, traffic accident, outbreak of fire in the home...) to a very broad perspective of serious disruptions to the functioning of society (viz. disaster situations due to events or processes such as earthquakes, floods, large scale terrorist attacks, etc.). The concept also covers the telecommunications needs of society's dedicated resources for ensuring public safety; including police forces, fire fighting units, ambulance services and other health and medical services, as well as civil defence services. The telecommunications needs of such services have until now been satisfied by dedicated networks and equipment, often different for different services, but with modern technology it is possible to increasingly integrate such services with the public telecommunications services.

Terrestrial and satellite radio/TV broadcasting and Internet services provide means for dissemination of information to the general public, in particular in hazardous and disaster situations. Telecommunications means may also be increasingly used as parts of various community functions such as health services (e.g. remote patient monitoring to reduce need for hospitalization).

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

emergency temporary camp (ETC)

EU Civil Protection Mechanism module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks are: 1) Provide emergency temporary shelter, including staff to assemble the camp, mainly in the initial stages of a disaster in coordination with existing structures, local authorities and international organisations until handover to local authorities or humanitarian organisations, where the capacity remains necessary for longer periods. 2) Where a handover takes place, train the relevant personnel (local and/or international) before the pull out of the module.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.5, 4.4

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

emerging technologies

New technologies and network to deliver communications.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

employee assistance programme

Contracted support service provided to organizations to assist them in addressing productivity issues, and to assist employees in identifying and resolving personal concerns, including health, marital, family, financial, alcohol, drug, legal, emotional, stress or other personal issues that could affect job performance

Adapted from the International Employee Assistance Professionals Association (EAPA).

Related categories: 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

encapsulating security payload (ESP)

An extension header that provides integrity, confidentiality, and replay protection to IP datagrams.

Related categories: 3.3

encapsulation

In computer networks, encapsulation is a method of modular design of communication protocols in which the logical functions of a network are abstracted by hiding information from higher level layers.

Related categories: 2.2

endpoint Identifier (EID)

An endpoint identifier (EID) is an IPv4 or IPv6 address used to identify an endpoint on the network. These EIDs help mark endpoints, normally a gateway or H. 323 terminal, where a locator provides the information about the topological location of the endpoint.

Related categories: 2.2

enhanced 112

A telephone system which includes network switching, data base and Public Safety Answering Point premise elements capable of providing automatic location identification data, selective routing, selective transfer, fixed transfer, and a call back number.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

entity

Something that has a separate and distinct existence and that can be identified within context

An entity can be a human, organization, physical object, class of objects or intangible object.

Related categories: 1.1, 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

environmental hazards

1. Hazards that may include chemical, natural and biological hazards. They can be created by environmental degradation or physical or chemical pollution in the air, water and soil.
2. A chemical or physical agent capable of causing harm to the ecosystem or natural resources.

Many of the processes and phenomena that fall into this category may be termed drivers of hazard and risk rather than hazards in themselves, such as soil degradation, deforestation, loss of biodiversity, salinization and sea-level rise.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

environmental health

Comprises those aspects of human health, including quality of life, that are determined by physical, chemical, biological, social, and psychosocial factors in the environment.

Environmental health also refers to the theory and practice of assessing, correcting, controlling, and preventing those factors in the environment that can potentially affect adversely the health of present and future generations.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

epidemic

1. The occurrence in a community or region of cases of an illness, specific health-related behaviour, or other health-related events clearly in excess of normal expectancy.
2. The occurrence of a number of cases of a disease that is unusually large or unexpected for a given place and time.

The community or region and the period in which the cases occur are specified precisely. The number of cases indicating the presence of an epidemic varies according to the agent, size, and type of population exposed, previous experience or lack of exposure to the disease, and time and place of occurrence.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

epidemic intelligence

The systematic collection, analysis and communication of any information to detect, verify, assess and investigate events and health risks with an early warning objective.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

epidemic threshold

The critical number or density of susceptible hosts required for an epidemic to occur. The epidemic threshold is used to confirm the emergence of an epidemic so as to step-up appropriate control measures.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

Epidemics Tool

One of the 4 tools within the EU Emergency Toolbox. It is used to respond to and prevent epidemic outbreaks.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Commission, European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations ECHO. European Commission official website. Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/echo/emergency-toolbox-eu-funding-sudden-onset-humanitarian-crises_en (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

epidemiology

The study of the distribution and determinants of health-related states or events in populations and the application of this study to control health problems.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

equity in health

1. The absence of systematic or potentially remediable differences in health status, access to healthcare and health-enhancing environments, and treatment in one or more aspects of health across populations or population groups defined socially, economically, demographically or geographically within and across countries. 2. A measure of the degree to which health policies are able to distribute well-being fairly.

Related categories: 1.1

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

equivalence

Relation between designations in different languages representing the same concept.

Related categories: 3.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 860:2007(en) Terminology work — Harmonization of concepts and terms. Year of publication: 2007. Available from: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:860:ed-3:v1:en> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

essential elements of information (EEI)

Important and standard information items, which support timely and informed decisions.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.2, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7, 4.2, 4.3

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

essential medicines

Essential medicines the most efficacious, safe and cost-effective medicines for priority conditions. A complementary list presents essential medicines for priority diseases for which specialized diagnostic and/or investigative facilities and/or specialist training are required.

A separate list of essential medicines and equipment for disaster situations is the WHO Emergency Health Kit. (Cf.)

Related categories: 3.4, 3.5

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

essential public health functions

The health authority's functions with regard to: 1. monitoring, evaluation and analysis of health status. 2. surveillance, research and control of the risks and threats to public health. 3. health promotion. 4. social participation in health. 5. development of policies and institutional capacity for public health planning and management. 6. strengthening of public health regulation and enforcement capacity. 7. evaluation and promotion of equitable access to necessary health services. 8. human resources development and training in public health. 9. quality assurance in personal and population-based health services. 10. research in public health. 11. reduction of the impact of emergencies and disasters on health.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

ethernet

A popular local area data communication network, which accepts transmissions from computers and terminals.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

Ethernet (IEEE 802.3)

Ethernet is primarily a standard communication protocol used to create local area networks. It transmits and receives data through cables. This facilitates network communication between two or more different types of network cables such as from copper to fiber optic and vice versa.

Related categories: 2.2

ethical review committee

An independent group that oversees the ethical aspects of a research study.

Related categories: 1.1

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

ethical-legal framework

The set of ethical legal rules applicable to a given context. In particular, in EU it is related to those standards, requirements, and binding provisions that are protecting, promoting, and enhancing those fundamental rights stated in the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights.

Related categories: 1.1

ethics

Relating to morals, treating of moral principles, rules of personal and societal conduct, respect for the person, equitable, humane and fair action.

In the practice and administration of health care, covers (a) moral principles of behaviour, (b) professional standards guiding and expected of all involved in health care, (c) patient respect and empowerment and (d) abidance by therapeutic deontological precepts.

Related categories: 1.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

EU 501/82 rules

European Union Regulations and emergency plans for any industrial activity that may be “a major accident hazard”.

Related categories: 1.1, 3.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

EU Civil Protection Committee (CPC)

Is the comitology committee set up through the legislation of the Union Civil Protection Mechanism (article 33 of Decision 1313/2013). It is composed of representatives of the Member State and Participating States' civil protection organizations. Its institutional role is to assist the Commission in the implementation of the civil protection legislation.

In practice, the CPC also serves as a more general forum for dialogue, where Member State and Participating States' and Commission representatives discuss other issues of common interest, on average four times a year.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Union, EU Civil Protection Mechanism. EU Civil Protection Mechanism official website. Available from: <https://ercportal.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ERCC-Response/CP-Pool#/> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

EU Civil Protection Mechanism

Union Mechanism. EU mechanism that aims to strengthen the cooperation between the Union and the Member States and to facilitate coordination in the field of civil protection in order to improve the effectiveness of systems for preventing, preparing for and responding to natural and man-made disasters.

Related categories: 1.1, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 1313/2013/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32013D1313&from=EN>

EU Emergency Toolbox

One of the instruments the European Commission uses to assist in unforeseen, sudden-onset crises. The Emergency Response Coordination Centre (ERCC) of the European Commission administers the various funding tools within this toolbox.

There is 4 tools within the Toolbox: 1) The Acute Large Emergency Response Tool (ALERT). 2) The Small-scale Tool. 3)The Epidemics Tool. 4) The Disaster Relief Emergency Fund (DREF).

The Emergency Toolbox is specifically dedicated to emergency response for vulnerable people outside the EU. It has 3 main characteristics:

1) It aims to (i) rapidly respond to emergencies through short deadlines to decide on allocations, (ii) close cooperation between the ERCC and humanitarian experts, and (iii) simplified procedure for humanitarian organisations to submit project proposals.

2) It is designed to provide first-line funding in the immediate aftermath of a crisis. The maximum duration of an action is limited to either 6 or 12 months. After the swift allocation of the Emergency Toolbox's initial funding, the EU can decide to provide additional support through other funding instruments.

3) *It aims to respond to emergencies that came unexpectedly or could not be anticipated. The Toolbox is separate from – and complementary to – other humanitarian funds which are allocated annually, through humanitarian implementation plans, to specific geographical areas and managed by humanitarian experts. The Emergency Toolbox reduces the need for country humanitarian implementation plans to respond in an ad-hoc way to unexpected needs. It allows them to respond to strategically planned goals.*

Related categories: 2.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Commission, European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations ECHO. European Commission official website. Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/echo/emergency-toolbox-eu-funding-sudden-onset-humanitarian-crises_en (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

EU Working Party on Civil Protection (PROCIV)

The Working Party on Civil Protection is the EU body responsible for discussing issues related to civil protection, such as: 1) The prevention of, preparedness for and response to natural and manmade disasters, such as floods, forest fires and earthquakes (inside and outside of the EU). 2) Issues concerning mutual disaster assistance between EU member states. 3) Cooperation on the protection of European critical infrastructure. 4) Strengthening chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear security in the EU.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Council. European Council official website. Available from: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/council-eu/preparatory-bodies/working-party-civil-protection/> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

euclidean distances

Measure of dissimilarity, which is a straight-line distance in the Euclidean space.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

European Avalanche Warning Services (EAWS)

Voluntary association of European entities established in 1983 whose objective is to improve the network connection of the authorities responsible for avalanche warnings.

The primary purpose of EAWS is to support its Members in preventing the loss of lives and damages due to avalanches by providing the society with efficient and effective avalanche forecasting and warning services.

Related categories: 3.3, 3.8

European Avalanche Warning Services (EAWS) . EAWS website. Available from: <https://www.avalanches.org/> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

European Centre for Disaster Medicine (CEMEC)

Intergovernmental centre established in San Marino under the aegis of the Council of Europe, to promote prevention and mitigation of the effects of natural and technological disasters through research, training programmes and international collaboration, in particular among European countries.

Related categories: 3.2, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

European Civil Protection Pool

A collection of emergency response teams and assets. It functions as a virtual collection of resources, which remain under the command and control of the Participating States in the Union Civil Protection Mechanism.

The EU established the European Civil Protection Pool to advance European cooperation in civil protection. It aims to enable a faster, better-coordinated and more effective European response to human-induced disasters and natural hazards.

Countries that participate in the Union Civil Protection Mechanism make these resources available for collective European emergency response operations. In return, they can benefit from EU financial support.

The Pool includes resources such as urban search and rescue teams, forest fire fighting capacities, emergency medical teams, water purification equipment, high-capacity pumping units, etc.

INSARAG-classified urban search and rescue teams as well as WHO-verified emergency medical teams are per se considered certified in the context of the European Civil Protection Pool.

Resources in the Pool are available for immediate deployment worldwide, following a request for assistance through the European Commission's Emergency Response Coordination Centre.

Related categories: 3.5, 4.4, 4.5

European Union, EU Civil Protection Mechanism. EU Civil Protection Mechanism official website. Available from: <https://ercportal.jrc.ec.europa.eu/ERCC-Response/CP-Pool#/> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

European Commission Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre

EU centre that integrates existing scientific multi-disciplinary knowledge and co-develops innovative solutions for existing needs. Activities of the EC DRMKC support the translation of complex scientific data and analyses into usable information and provides science-based advice for DRM policies.

Related categories: 3.2, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Commission. European Commission official website. Available from: <https://drmkc.jrc.ec.europa.eu/> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

European Commission Humanitarian Operations (ECHO)

A major source of humanitarian aid, the European Union provides emergency relief to victims of both natural and man-made disasters and helps in preparedness and prevention projects, not limited to Europe.

Related categories: 3.2, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

European Emergency Number Association (EENA)

EENA, the European Emergency Number Association, is a Brussels-based NGO set up in 1999 dedicated to promoting high-quality emergency services reached by the number 112 throughout the EU.

EENA serves as a discussion platform for emergency services, public authorities, decision makers, associations and solution providers in view of improving emergency response in accordance with citizens' requirements. EENA is also promoting the establishment of an efficient system for alerting citizens about imminent or developing emergencies.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

European Emergency Response Capacity (EERC)

EU Civil Protection Mechanism pool of pre-committed response capacities of the Member States. Includes modules, other response capacities and experts.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 1313/2013/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32013D1313&from=EN>

European Humanitarian Personnel Network

In response to the recurrent difficulty of recruiting trained health personnel in emergency situations and for disaster response, this network tries to recruit, train and maintain a registry of relevant health personnel for emergency humanitarian work.

Related categories: 3.4, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA)

EMSA was established by Regulation (EC) No 1406/2002 as a major source of support to the European Commission and the Member States in the field of maritime safety and prevention of pollution from ships, and subsequent amendments have refined and enlarged its mandate.

The Agency is managed by an Executive Director whose duties and powers are defined in Article 15 of Regulation (EC) No 1406/2002. The Executive Director is supported by four departments and an Executive Office unit. Currently, the Agency has 11 units, 10 of which come under these 4 departments: 1) Sustainability & Technical Assistance (Sustainability; Visits & Inspections, Human Element; Capacity Building). 2) Department 2: Safety, Security & Surveillance. 3) Digital Services & Simplification (Maritime Digital Services; Digital Infrastructure; Simplification). 4) Corporate Services (Human Resources; Legal, Finance & Facilities).

Related categories: 2.2, 3.8, 4.4

European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA). European Maritime Safety Agency official website. Available from: <http://www.emsa.europa.eu/> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

European Medical Corps

The European Medical Corps enables quick medical assistance and public health expertise from all EU Member States and Participating States to a health emergency inside and outside the EU. The deployment is coordinated by the EU's Emergency Response Coordination Centre, the operational hub of the EU Civil Protection Mechanism.

The European Medical Corps gathers all medical response capacities committed by Member States to the European Civil Protection Pool. Following a request for European assistance, medical capacities can be drawn from this Pool and from other Member States' response capacities.

To date, 11 States party to the Mechanism have committed emergency medical teams and their equipment to the European Medical Corps: Belgium, Estonia, the Czech Republic, Italy, France, Germany, Norway, Portugal, Slovakia, Spain, and Sweden. To become part of the European Medical Corps, the EU has set up a certification and registration process to make sure they meet high standards, including internationally recognised ones by the World Health Organization (WHO) when they exist. Teams are trained to work alongside colleagues from other countries and according to international guidelines.

In return, they benefit from EU financial support. The EU provides grants for upgrading teams to improve their readiness, quality, and availability. Once part of the Pool, the EU covers 75% of transportation costs, as well as 75% operating costs if deployed inside the EU.

Related categories: 3.4, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Commission, European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations ECHO. European Commission official website. Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/echo/what/civil-protection/european-medical-corps_en (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

European Reference Network for Critical Infrastructure Protection (ERNICIP)

EU network whose mission is to foster the emergence of innovative, qualified, efficient and competitive security solutions, through the networking of European experimental capabilities.

ERNICIP aims at providing a framework within which experimental facilities and laboratories will share knowledge and expertise in order to harmonise test protocols throughout Europe, leading to better protection of critical infrastructures against all types of threats and hazards.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.7, 3.8, 4.4

European Commission. European Commission official website. Available from: <https://erncip-project.jrc.ec.europa.eu/about-erncip> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI)

ETSI is an independent, non-profit organization, whose mission is to produce telecommunications standards for today and for the future.

Based in Sophia Antipolis (France), ETSI is officially responsible for standardization of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) within Europe. These technologies include telecommunications, broadcasting and related areas such as intelligent transportation and medical electronics.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

eustress

Where stress enhances function (physical or mental, such as through strength training or challenging work), it may be considered eustress (or “positive stress”).

Related categories: 5

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

evacuation

Organized, phased and supervised movement of people from dangerous or potentially dangerous areas to places of safety

Evacuation plans refer to the arrangements established in advance to enable the moving of people and assets temporarily to safer places before, during or after the occurrence of a hazardous event. Evacuation plans may include plans for return of evacuees and options to shelter in place.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 4.3

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

evacuation command

Series of orders to evacuate people

Related categories: 2.3, 2.4, 3.1, 3.2, 3.6, 4.3

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

evacuation drill

Activity that practises a particular skill related to evacuation and often involves repeating the same thing several times

EXAMPLE: A drill to practise safely evacuating a neighbourhood or village from a landslide

Related categories: 3.1, 4.1, 4.3

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

evaluation

Systematic process that compares the result of measurement to recognised criteria to determine the discrepancies between intended and actual performance

Gaps in performance are inputs into the continual improvement process.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.2, 3.4, 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

evaluator

In simulation exercises: a person who gathers data from the exercise and analyses whether the objectives and the targets of the exercise were met. Their evaluation will include overall performance, operational effectiveness, quality control, capabilities, strengths and weaknesses, and areas for improvement.

Related categories: 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

event

Occurrence or change of a particular set of circumstances

An event can be one or more occurrences, and can have several causes and several consequences

An event can also be something that is expected which does not happen, or something that is not expected which does happen

An event can be a risk source

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

event alert notification time

The time passed between an event occurrence and the reception of the warning message by the citizen is the "event alert notification time".

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.8

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

event-based surveillance

The organized collection, monitoring, assessment and interpretation of mainly unstructured ad hoc information regarding health events or risks, which may represent an acute risk to human health.

Event-based surveillance is a functional component of early warning, alert and response. This information can be rumours and other ad hoc reports transmitted through formal channels (i.e. established routine reporting systems) and informal channels (i.e. the media, health workers and reports from NGOs), including events related to the occurrence of disease in humans and events related to potential human exposure.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

evidence

Any form of knowledge, including, but not confined to research, of sufficient quality to inform decisions.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

evidence gap map

Thematic evidence collection for a particular topic which can be used to identify key gaps in the evidence base which might require new research.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

exercise

Process to train for, assess, practise, and improve performance in an organization

Exercises can be used for validating policies, plans, procedures, training, equipment, and inter-organizational agreements; clarifying and training personnel in roles and responsibilities; improving inter-organizational coordination and communications; identifying gaps in resources; improving individual performance and identifying opportunities for improvement; and a controlled opportunity to practise improvisation. An exercise does not need an expectation of pass or fail.

Related categories: 3.4, 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

exercise annual plan

Document in which the exercisepolicy plan has been translated to exercise goals and exercises, and in which an exercise programme for a certain year is reflected

Related categories: 2.2, 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

exercise controller

Ead facilitator, a single person who supervises the overall conduct of the exercise, ensuring that it proceeds as planned and that its objectives are reached.

The exercise controller is required for drill, functional and full-scale exercises. The exercise director appoints the

exercise controller.

Related categories: 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

exercise coordinator

Person responsible for planning, conducting and evaluating exercise activities

In larger exercises, this function can include several people/staff and can be called “exercise control”.

Some countries use a term such as “exercise director” or similar instead of “exercise coordinator”.

The exercise coordinator role is also responsible for the cooperation among internal and external entities.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.3, 3.8, 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

exercise director

The person who provides strategic oversight and direction for the planning, conduct and evaluation of an exercise. The exercise director is responsible for approving the exercise’s purpose, objectives and supporting documentation, including the concept note, exercise plan and exercise instructions.

Related categories: 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

exercise facilitator

A person responsible for delivering injects and monitoring progress during an exercise. The facilitator is the first point of contact for any questions, clarifications or requests.

Related categories: 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

exercise management team

Team responsible for planning, conducting and evaluating an exercise project.

Related categories: 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

exercise objectives

Specific objectives for the exercise

Related categories: 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

exercise outcomes

The outcomes it is expected to achieve.

Related categories: 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

exercise planning team

The team responsible for all aspects of an exercise, including exercise planning, conduct, and evaluation. The planning team determines exercise capabilities, tasks, and objectives; tailors the scenario to needs; and develops documents used in exercise simulation, control, and evaluation. The exercise planning team should be comprised of representatives from each major participating jurisdiction and agency, but should be kept to a manageable size.

Related categories: 4.1

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

exercise programme

Series of exercise activities designed to meet an overall objective or goal

Related categories: 3.4, 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

exercise programme manager

Person responsible for planning and improving the exercise programme

Related categories: 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

exercise project

A standard approach for building and implementing any exercise consisting of three phases: 1. Pre-exercise planning, material development and set-up. 2. Exercise conduct. 3. Post-exercise reporting and handover phase.

Related categories: 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

exercise project team

Group of individuals responsible for planning, conducting and evaluating an exercise project

Related categories: 2.1, 3.5, 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

exercise report

A report that records, describes and analyses the exercise, drawing on the evaluation, including debriefs and observations.

The report should include all relevant information, including exercise description; type; scenario; outcomes; participating organizations; and recommendations to assist in the design of future exercises. Exercise reports are sometimes referred to as “after action reports.”

Related categories: 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

exercise safety officer

Person tasked with ensuring that any actions during the exercise are performed safely

In larger exercises, involving multiple functions, more than one safety officer can be assigned.

Related categories: 2.3, 2.4, 3.2, 3.4, 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

exercise setup

A pre-staging and dispersal of exercise materials. Exercise setup includes registration materials, documentation, signage, and other equipment, as appropriate.

Related categories: 4.1

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

expansive soil

Earthen material, particularly clays that, upon wetting, freezing, or drying will alternately expand or contract causing damage to foundations of buildings and other structures. Shrinkage is generally referred to as desiccation.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNi/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

experimental research

Research in which the researcher intervenes to change something and to study the effects of that change.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

exposure

1. The situation of people, infrastructure, housing, production capacities and other tangible assets located in hazard-prone areas. 2. contact of a chemical, physical or biological agent with the outer boundary of an organism (for example, through inhalation, ingestion or dermal [skin] contact).

Measures of exposure can include the number of people or types of assets in an area. These can be combined with the specific vulnerability and capacity of the exposed elements to any particular hazard to estimate the quantitative risks associated with that hazard in the area of interest.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.4, 3.7, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

exposure route

The pathway or route by which a person is exposed to a hazard.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.4, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

extended service set identifier (ESSID)

A service set identifier (SSID) is a sequence of characters that uniquely names a wireless local area network (WLAN)

Related categories: 2.2

eXtensible Markup Language (XML)

An internet specification for web documents that enables tags to be used that provide functionality beyond that in Hyper Text Markup Language (HTML).

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

eXtensible Markup Language (XML) instance

An XML document that conforms to a given schema, as a specific instance of that schema.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

eXtensible Markup Language (XML) schema

The formal document definition (structure, content type and constraints) describing a class of XML instance documents. There are various XML schema languages, but in this document, all schemas are assumed to be defined using the W3C XML

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

extensive disaster risk

The risk of low-severity, high-frequency hazardous events and disasters, mainly but not exclusively associated with highly localized hazards.

Extensive disaster risk is usually high where communities are exposed to, and vulnerable to, recurring localized floods, landslides, storms or drought. Extensive disaster risk is often exacerbated by poverty, urbanization and environmental degradation.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

external attack

Attack perpetrated by persons or entities that are not directly or indirectly linked with the legitimate manufacturer, originator of the good or rights holder

Related categories: 2.2, 3.1, 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

external validity

Extent to which a study can be generalized to other situations.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

extraterrestrial hazard

A hazard caused by asteroids, meteoroids, and comets as they pass near-earth, enter the Earth's atmosphere, and/or strike the Earth, and by changes in interplanetary conditions that effect the Earth's magnetosphere, ionosphere, and thermosphere.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

extratropical storm

A type of low-pressure cyclonic system in the middle and high latitudes (also called mid-latitude cyclone) that primarily gets its energy from the horizontal temperature contrasts (fronts) in the atmosphere. When associated with cold fronts, extratropical cyclones may be particularly damaging (e.g., European winter/windstorm, Nor'easter).

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

extreme temperature

A general term for temperature variations above (extreme heat) or below (extreme cold) normal conditions.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

facilitation

1. The effort to help a process move forward towards attaining a particular end or result. 2. The process undertaken to enable the different stakeholders involved in policy dialogue to achieve a high degree of consensus around a specific policy concern and to ensure that negotiations run well.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

facility

Plant, machinery, property, building, transportation units at sea/land/airport, and other items of infrastructure or plant and related systems that have a distinct and quantifiable business function of service

A facility can have formal boundaries as defined by, for example, legislation.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

FAIR principles of data sharing

Principles that state all data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Resuable.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

false alarm

Distress alert initiated for other than an appropriate test, by communications equipment intended for alerting, when no distress situation actually exists

Related categories: 3.8

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icssc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

false alert

Distress alert received from any source, including communications equipment intended for alerting, when no distress situation actually exists, and a notification of distress should not have resulted

Related categories: 3.8

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icssc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icssc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

feasibility

How easy it is to implement the intervention and its related research.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

feedback loop

Interconnected loops within a complex adaptive system that provide regulatory information to other components of the system; feedback can be positive or negative.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

fiber channel over ethernet (FCoE)

Fibre Channel over Ethernet (FCoE) is a computer network technology that encapsulates Fibre Channel frames over Ethernet networks.

Related categories: 2.2

field exercises

Is one form of full-scale exercise, focusing on more specific capacities or series of capacities, such as procedures for rapid response teams (RRT), laboratory analysis or sample collection and transport.

Although there are differences between a field exercise and a full-scale exercise (the latter is often more complex and requires more financial and human resources to be deployed), the development and implementation of both types of exercise - including the planning, exercise conduct, and post-exercise phases - are very similar.

Related categories: 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

field hospital (FHOS)

EU Civil Protection Mechanism module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks is: Provide initial and/or follow-up trauma and medical care, taking into account acknowledged international guidelines for foreign field hospital use, such as World Health Organisation or Red Cross guidelines.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 4.4

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

field notes

Notes taken by a researcher while conducting their research.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

file transfer protocol (FTP)

Standard communication protocol used for the transfer of computer files from a server to a client on a computer network. FTP is built on a client-server model architecture using separate control and data connections between the client and the server.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

fire following earthquake

Urban fires triggered by earthquakes. Particularly susceptible areas include densely spaced, wooden buildings that dominate local architecture, and where the earthquake has damaged or ruptured water and gas pipelines. Small local fires have the potential to merge into conflagrations destroying many city blocks.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

firestorm

The coalescing of many fires into a single big fire creating a convective column, with very high temperatures. Firestorms and superfires are now believed to be the cause of the greatest number of casualties following nuclear war.

Related categories: 3.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

firewall

Hardware or software that isolates an organization's private network or intranet from the Internet, thus protecting it from external intrusions. A firewall can include packet filtering, proxy servers, and NAT.

Related categories: 3.3

first aid

The immediate but temporary care given on site to the victims of an accident or sudden illness in order to avert complications, lessen suffering, and sustain life until competent services or a physician can be obtained.

Related categories: 3.4

United Nations, Department of Humanitarian Affairs. Internationally agreed glossary of basic terms related to Disaster Management. Year of publication: 1992. Available from: <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/004DFD3E15B69A67C1256C4C006225C2-dha-glossary-1992.pdf>

first level of care

The entry point into the health care system, at the interface between services and community. Where the first level of care satisfies a number of quality criteria it is called primary care.

Related categories: 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

first responder

Emergency Management / Response Personnel. Includes Federal, State, territorial, tribal, substate regional, and local governments, nongovernmental organizations (NGOs), private sector organizations; critical infrastructure owners and operators, and all other organizations and individuals who assume an emergency management role. Also known as emergency or first responder.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.3, 2.4, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7, 4.2

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

fixed rope

Ropes fixed by climber during the course of an expedition, enabling them to pass up and down the difficult face of mountain more quickly.

Related categories: 3.4

Jawahar Institute of Mountaineering & Winter Sport. JIM&WS website. Available from:
<https://www.jawaharinstitutepahalgam.com/mtn%20terminology1.php>

flash flood

Heavy or excessive rainfall in a short period of time that produce immediate runoff, creating flooding conditions within minutes or a few hours during or after the rainfall.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from:
https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

floating barrier

A portable, inflatable device placed as an emergency on the surface of a water mass where oil spill has occurred, with the aim of controlling and barring the spread and aspirating the oil to limit further environmental pollution.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

flood

A general term for the overflow of water from a stream channel onto normally dry land in the floodplain (riverine flooding), higher-than-normal levels along the coast and in lakes or reservoirs (coastal flooding) as well as ponding of water at or near the point where the rain fell (flash floods).

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from:
https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

flood containment (FC)

EU Civil Protection Mechanism module referrenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks is: Reinforce existing structures and build new barriers to prevent further flooding of rivers, basins, waterways with rising water levels.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.4, 3.5, 4.4

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Comission of 16 October 2014 . Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

flood rescue using boats (FRB)

EU Civil Protection Mechanism module referrenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks are: 1) Water search and rescue and assist people trapped in a flooding situation by using boats. 2) Provide lifesaving aid and deliver first necessities as required.

Related categories: 2.1, 3.1, 3.4, 3.5, 4.4

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Comission of 16 October 2014 . Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

FMECA

Failure Mode, Effects and Criticality Analysis: is a reliability study methodology used to evaluate, by means of suitable diagrams, the severity of the consequences of a failure correlated with the probability of its occurrence. Through the rigorous FMECA procedures a plan will be obtained that clearly indicates which are the most critical parts of the entity under examination, so as to be able to concentrate one's efforts on improving the criticalities relating to these parts.

Related categories: 3.2

focus

In seismology, the point beneath the surface of the earth where an earthquake rupture originates, hypocentre, and from where seismic waves radiate.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.7

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

focus group

Group of people assembled to discuss a particular topic.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

fog

Water droplets that are suspended in the air near the Earth's surface. Fog is simply a cloud that is in contact with the ground.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgLS55evtT8jBNi/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

food safety

1. Assurance that food will not cause harm to the consumer when it is prepared and/or eaten according to its intended use. 2. Handling, storing and preparing food to prevent infection and help to make sure that our food keeps enough nutrients for us to have a healthy diet.

Related categories: 3.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

food security

A situation that exists when all people, at all times, have physical, social and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life.

Related categories: 3.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

footprint

The geographic area covered by a particular wireless cell or cell sector.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

forecast

Statement or statistical estimate of the occurrence of a future event. This term is used with different meanings in different disciplines, as well as "prediction".

Related categories: 5

United Nations, Department of Humanitarian Affairs. Internationally agreed glossary of basic terms related to Disaster Management. Year of publication: 1992. Available from: <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/004DFD3E15B69A67C1256C4C006225C2-dha-glossary-1992.pdf>

foreign medical team (FMT)

Groups of health professionals and supporting staff outside their country of origin, aiming to provide health care specifically to disaster affected populations. They include governmental (both civilian and military) and non-governmental teams. A FMT has staff to provide basic and/or advanced healthcare based on international classification levels and minimum standards during a limited time period in existing or temporary structures, with or without field hospitals.

Any individuals or groups that do not fit within the definition and cannot comply with the standard should either consider joining a recognized organisation that provides FMT or not responding in the aftermath of a sudden onset disaster.

WHO foreign medical team types:

FMT Type 1: Outpatient Emergency Care (Outpatient initial emergency care of injuries and other significant health care needs)

FMT Type 2: Inpatient Surgical Emergency Care (Inpatient acute care, general and obstetric surgery for trauma and other major conditions)

FMT Type 3: Inpatient Referral Care (Complex inpatient referral surgical care including intensive care capacity)

Related categories: 3.4, 3.5, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

forensic analysys

Scientific methodology for authenticating material goods by confirming an authentication element or an intrinsic attribute throught the use of specialized equipment by a skilled expert with special knowledge.

Related categories: 5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

forest fire

A type of wildfire in a wooded area.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

forest/vegetation fire(s)

Fires in forest, grassland, bush and bushland that usually cover a widespread area and cause extensive damage to property and the environment. They may be due to natural causes, such as lightning or volcanic eruption, may be started illegally by arsonists or carelessly by campers and smokers or may accidentally spread from an intentionally started fire for clearing a forest area.

Disastrous forest fires are quite seasonal in hot, dry regions such as the Mediterranean basin during summer. Widespread and serious air pollution has been caused by huge forest fires in Southeast Asia, with intense accumulation of fine particles that provoke grave respiratory problems.

Related categories: 3.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

formative evaluation

Evaluation conducted while a programme is in progress, mainly for improving implementational details.

Related categories: 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

framework

A work environment, or framework, is a standardized set of concepts, practices and criteria for approaching a particular type of problem that serves as a reference for facing and solving new problems of a similar nature.

Related categories: 2.2

freeze

Freeze occurs when the air temperature is at (32°F/0°C) or below over a widespread area for a climatologically significant period of time. Use of the term is usually restricted to advective situations or to occasions when wind or other conditions prevent frost. Frost and freeze are particularly damaging during the crop growing season.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

frost

Frost is the consequence of radiative cooling resulting in the formation of thin ice crystals on the ground or other surfaces in the form of needles, feathers, scales, or fans. Frost occurs when the temperature of surfaces is below freezing and water vapor from humid air forms solid deposits on the cold surface.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

full-duplex

The term full-duplex describes simultaneous data transmission and receptions over one channel. A full-duplex device is capable of bi-directional network data transmissions at the same time

Related categories: 2.2

full-scale exercise (FSX) (FSE)

Exercise that involves multiple organizations or functions and includes actual activities

Related categories: 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

full-scale exercises (FSX) (FSE)

Is an exercise that simulates a real event as closely as possible and is designed to evaluate the operational capability of emergency management systems in a highly stressful environment, simulating actual response conditions. This includes the mobilization and movement of emergency personnel, equipment and resources. Ideally, the full-scale exercise should test and evaluate most functions of the emergency management plan or operational plan. Differing from the FX, a full-scale exercise typically involves multiple agencies and participants physically deployed in a field location.

Related categories: 3.4, 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

functional annexes

Individual chapters in an emergency operations plan that focus on procedures such as Special Needs or Continuity of Operations. These annexes address all-hazard critical operational functions and describe the actions, roles, and responsibilities of schools and participating organizations. In some plans, functional annexes are referred to as Emergency Support Functions (ESFs).

Related categories: 3.2

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

functional exercise

Exerciset to train for, assess, practise and improve the performance of single functions designed to respond to and recover from an unwanted event)

Functions can include an emergency operations centre (EOC) team, a crisis management team or firefighters decontaminating mock victims.

Related categories: 3.4, 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

functional integration

The extent to which key support functions and activities such as financing, human resources, strategic planning, information management, marketing and quality assurance/improvement are coordinated across all system's units.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

functional needs

Individual circumstances requiring assistance, accommodation, or modification for mobility, communication, transportation, safety, health maintenance, etc., due to any temporary or permanent situation that limits an individual's ability to take action in an emergency.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

functions

Actions or operations required in emergency response or recovery.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

Galileo

Europe's own global navigation satellite system, providing a highly accurate, guaranteed global positioning service under civilian control.

Currently providing initial services, Galileo is interoperable with GPS and Glonass, the US and Russian global satellite navigation systems. By offering dual frequencies as standard, Galileo is set to deliver real-time positioning accuracy down to the metre range. The current Galileo system consists of 26 satellites in all. All but two of these are positioned in three circular Medium Earth Orbit (MEO) planes at 23 222 km altitude above the Earth, and at an inclination of the orbital planes of 56 degrees to the equator. The remaining pair were placed in incorrect orbits by a Soyuz launcher error, and are currently employed for search and rescue but not as operational members of the constellation.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5

European Space Agency (ESA). ESA website. Available from: https://www.esa.int/Applications/Navigation/Galileo/What_is_Galileo (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

gant chart

Bar chart that illustrates a project schedule.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

gatekeeper

1. A health care provider at the first contact level who has responsibilities for the provision of primary care as well as for the coordination of specialized care and referral. 2. Person controlling access to a population.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

gateway

A piece of networking hardware used in telecommunications for telecommunications networks that allows data to flow from one discrete network to another. Gateways are distinct from routers or switches in that they communicate using more than one protocol to connect multiple networks and can operate at any of the seven layers of the open systems interconnection model (OSI).

Related categories: 2.2

NENA (USA National Emergency Number Association). NENA Glossary of 9-1-1 Terminology. Year of publication: 2021. Available from: https://nenawiki.org/wiki/NENA_Glossary_of_9-1-1_Terminology (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

general average

Expenses voluntarily incurred to save a ship and her cargo.

Related categories: 5

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

general budget support

A subcategory of direct budget support focusing on overall policy and budget priorities.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

general packet radio service (GPRS)

GPRS is a mobile data service available to users of GSM mobile phones. It is often described as “2.5G”, that is, a technology between the second (2G) and third (3G) generations of mobile telephony. It provides moderate speed data transfer, by using unused TDMA channels in the GSM network. Originally there was some thought to extend GPRS to cover other standards, but instead those networks are being converted to use the GSM standard, so that is the only kind of network where GPRS is in use.

GPRS is integrated into GSM standards releases starting with Release 97 and onwards. First it was standardized by ETSI but now that effort has been handed onto the

3GPP.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

generalizability

Extent to which the findings of a study can be applied in other situations.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

geo-location

Specific location defined by one of several means to represent latitude, longitude, elevation above sea level and coordinate system

Geo-location generally means the meaningful specification of the position of a point or object on the earth. The term itself does not carry a prescription of the coordinate system to be used. Additional attributes associated with a geo-location are not a part of a geo-location specification.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

geocoding

Interpolation-based computational techniques to derive estimates of geographic locations.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.7

NENA (USA National Emergency Number Association). NENA Glossary of 9-1-1 Terminology. Year of publication: 2021. Available from: https://nenawiki.org/wiki/NENA_Glossary_of_9-1-1_Terminology (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

geographic information system (GIS)

A computer software system that enables one to visualize geographic aspects of a body of data. A computer system that incorporates hardware, software, and infrastructure for capturing, manipulating, integrating, interrogating, modelling, analysing, and visualizing all forms of geographically referenced information.

It contains the ability to translate implicit geographic data (such as a street address) into an explicit map location.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.7

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

NENA (USA National Emergency Number Association). NENA Glossary of 9-1-1 Terminology. Year of publication: 2021. Available from: https://nenawiki.org/wiki/NENA_Glossary_of_9-1-1_Terminology (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

geological hazard

Hazard that originates from internal earth processes. Examples are earthquakes, volcanic activity and emissions, and related geophysical processes such as mass movements, landslides, rockslides, surface collapses and debris or mud flows.

Hydrometeorological factors are important contributors to some of these processes. Tsunamis are difficult to categorize: although they are triggered by undersea earthquakes and other geological events, they essentially become an oceanic process that is manifested as a coastal water-related hazard.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

geomagnetic storm

A type of extraterrestrial hazard caused by solar wind shockwaves that temporarily disturb the Earth's magnetosphere. Geomagnetic storms can disrupt power grids, spacecraft operations, and satellite communications.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

geophysical hazard

Geological hazards

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

geopositioning

Location through satellite triangulation that is represented on a cartographic map.

Related categories: 3.3

geospatial

Data Accurately references to a precise location on the earth's surface.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

GIS attribute

Tabular information about "features" contained in GIS data.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.7

NENA (USA National Emergency Number Association). NENA Glossary of 9-1-1 Terminology. Year of publication: 2021. Available from: https://nenawiki.org/wiki/NENA_Glossary_of_9-1-1_Terminology (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

GIS data layer

A spatial dataset containing a common feature type. Layers are also referred to as themes.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.7

NENA (USA National Emergency Number Association). NENA Glossary of 9-1-1 Terminology. Year of publication: 2021. Available from: https://nenawiki.org/wiki/NENA_Glossary_of_9-1-1_Terminology (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

GIS data provider

A person or group who is responsible for maintaining authoritative GIS data for a given service area.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.7

NENA (USA National Emergency Number Association). NENA Glossary of 9-1-1 Terminology. Year of publication: 2021. Available from: https://nenawiki.org/wiki/NENA_Glossary_of_9-1-1_Terminology (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

GIS feature

Representation of a real-world object in a GIS as a single geometric object

Related categories: 2.1, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.7

NENA (USA National Emergency Number Association). NENA Glossary of 9-1-1 Terminology. Year of publication: 2021. Available from: https://nenawiki.org/wiki/NENA_Glossary_of_9-1-1_Terminology (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

glacial lake outburst

A flood that occurs when water dammed by a glacier or moraine is suddenly released. Glacial lakes can be at the front of the glacier (marginal lake) or below the ice sheet (sub-glacial lake).

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

glacier

A huge mass of ice that moves because of its own weight. Glaciers are formed at places where rate of accumulation of snow is more than the rate of melting of snow.

Related categories: 3.1

Jawahar Institute of Mountaineering & Winter Sport. JIM&WS website. Available from: <https://www.jawaharinstitutepahalgam.com/mtn%20terminology1.php>

glaserian grounded theory

A less structured approach to grounded theory (qualitative research methodology that generates theory grounded in data) that uses active coding in data analysis.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

glasgow coma scale (GCS)

The scale is a practical means of assessing changes in the level of responsiveness in the unconscious, comatose or severely injured person. Three systems are monitored; in the eye, the result may be (a) no response, (b) response to pain, (c) to verbal command, (d) opens eye spontaneously. The total score for a positive degree of consciousness is between 3 and 15.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

global burden of disease

A comprehensive demographic and epidemiological framework to estimate health gaps for an extensive set of disease and injury causes, and for major risk factors, using all available mortality and health data and methods to ensure internal consistency and comparability of estimates.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

global health security

The activities required, both proactive and reactive, to minimize vulnerability to acute public health events that endanger the collective health of populations living across geographical regions and international boundaries.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

global positioning system (GPS)

A system for positioning (locating) any entity on the surface of the Earth with an accuracy of a few meters. To determine the position, four or more satellites are used following a trilateration method.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.3, 3.7

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

global system for mobile communications (GSM)

Global standard for mobile communications. The predominant digital telephone service technology outside the United States, with some services within the United States. The radio interface is either in the 9—MHZ or 1.8GHZ band.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

goal

General statement that indicates the intended solution to an identified problem.

Related categories: 5

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

goods

Items or materials that, upon the placement of a purchase order, are manufactured, handled, processed or transported within the supply chain for usage or consumption by the purchaser

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

grading of recommendations, development and evaluation (GRADE)

Methodology to grade the quality of evidence and strength of recommendations in guidelines.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

grey literature

Documents produced by organizations outside of the traditional commercial or academic publishing and distribution channels.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

ground forest fire fighting (GFFF)

EU Civil Protection Mechanism module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks is: To contribute to the extinction of large forest and vegetal fires by using ground means.

Related categories: 2.4, 3.4, 3.5, 4.4, 4.5

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

ground forest fire fighting using vehicles (GFFF-V)

EU Civil Protection Mechanism module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks is: To contribute to the extinction of large forest and vegetal fires by using vehicles.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.4, 3.4, 3.5, 4.4, 4.5

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

ground movement

Surface displacement of earthen materials due to ground shaking triggered by earthquakes or volcanic eruptions.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgLS5evtT8jBNi/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

grounded theory

Methodology used to construct theories through methodical gathering and analysis of data, using inductive reasoning.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

group

An organizational subdivision established to divide the incident management structure into functional areas of operation.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

guided discovery

A teaching and learning environment allowing active participation in the discovery of knowledge.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

hail

Solid precipitation in the form of irregular pellets or balls of ice more than 5 mm in diameter.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

half-duplex

Half-duplex data transmission means that data can be transmitted in both directions on a signal carrier, but not at the same time.

Related categories: 2.2

hard-to-reach group

Group of people that is typically under-represented in the planning process or has limited capacity for involvement.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

Harvard style

Citation style used in documents, in which partial citations (Smith 2010, for example) are enclosed in parentheses and embedded in the text and the citations are listed in alphabetic order by surname of the first author.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

hash-based message authentication code (HMAC)

A keyed hashing method for message authentication. HMAC is a secret key authentication algorithm that is used with an iterative cryptographic hash function, such as SHA-1, in combination with a secret shared key. The cryptographic strength of HMAC depends on the properties of the underlying hash function.

Related categories: 3.3

hazard

Source of potential harm

Hazard can be a risk source.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

hazard mitigation

Any action taken to reduce or eliminate the long-term risk to human life and property from hazards. The term is sometimes used in a stricter sense to mean cost-effective measures to reduce the potential for damage to a facility or facilities from a disaster or incident.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

hazard monitoring function

Activities to obtain evidence-based information on hazards in a defined area used to make decisions about the need for public warning

Related categories: 2.2, 3.1, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

hazard-specific annexes

Individual chapters in an emergency operations plan that describe strategies for managing missions for a specific hazard. They explain the procedures that are unique to that annex for a hazard type and may be short or long depending on the details needed to explain the actions, roles, and responsibilities. The information in these annexes is not repeated elsewhere in the plan.

Related categories: 3.2

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

hazardous event

The manifestation of a hazard in a particular place during a particular period of time.

Severe hazardous events can lead to a disaster as a result of the combination of hazard occurrence and other risk factors.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

hazardous material (HAZMAT)

Any substance or material that, when involved in an accident and released in sufficient quantities, poses a risk to people's health, safety, and/or property. These substances and materials include explosives, radioactive materials, flammable liquids or solids, combustible liquids or solids, poisons, oxidizers, toxins, and corrosive materials.

Related categories: 3.1

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

HAZMAT

A material (such as flammable or poisonous material) that would be a danger to life or to the environment if released without precautions

Related categories: 3.1

hazmat suit

Personal protective equipment that consists of an impermeable whole-body garment worn as protection against hazardous materials.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

health

A state of complete physical, mental and social well-being, and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

health care facility

Hospitals of all sizes and types; specialized medical services; primary health care clinics; general practitioner's surgery, etc.

Related categories: 3.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

health cluster

A mechanism for coordinated assessments, joint analyses, the development of agreed overall priorities, objectives and a health crisis response strategy, and the monitoring and evaluation of the implementation and impact of that strategy.

Related categories: 3.4, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

health emergency

A type of event or imminent threat that produces or has the potential to produce a range of health consequences, and which requires coordinated action, usually urgent and often non-routine.

A health emergency may pose a substantial risk of significant morbidity or mortality in a community.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

health emergency and disaster risk management (Health- EDRM)

The systematic analysis and management of health risks, posed by actual or potential hazardous events, including emergencies and disasters, through a combination of hazard, exposure and vulnerability reduction to prevent and mitigate risks, preparedness, response, and recovery.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

health impact assessment

The estimation of the effects of any specific action (plans, policies or programmes) in any given environment on the health of a defined population.

Recommendations are produced for decisionmakers and stakeholders, with the aim of maximizing the proposal's positive health effects and minimizing the negative health effects.

Related categories: 3.4, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

health insurance

A contract between the insured and the insurer to the effect that in the event of specified events (determined in the insurance contract) occurring the insurer will pay compensation either to the insured person or to the health service provider.

There are two major forms of health insurance. One is private health insurance, with premiums based on individual or group risks. The other is social security, whereby in principle society's risks are pooled, with contributions by individuals usually dependent on their capacity to pay.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

health needs

objectively determined deficiencies in health that require health care, from promotion to palliation.

Perceived health needs: the need for health services as experienced by the individual and which he/she is prepared to acknowledge; perceived need may or may not coincide with professionally defined or scientifically confirmed need. Professionally defined health needs: the need for health services as recognized by health professionals from the point of view of the benefit obtainable from advice, preventive measures, management or specific therapy; Professionally defined need may or may not coincide with perceived or scientifically confirmed need. Scientifically confirmed health needs: the need confirmed by objective measures of biological, anthropometric or psychological factors, expert opinion or the passage of time; it is generally considered to correspond to those conditions that can be classified in accordance with the International Classification of Diseases.

Related categories: 3.5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

health outcome

A change in the health status of an individual, group or population which is attributable to a planned intervention or series of interventions.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

health planning

1. The orderly process of defining health problems, identifying unmet needs and surveying the resources to meet them, establishing priority goals that are realistic and feasible, and projecting administrative action, concerned not only with the adequacy, efficacy and efficiency of health services but also with those factors of ecology and of social and individual behaviour that affect the health of the individual and the community. 2. The process of organizing decisions and actions to achieve particular ends, set within a policy. 3. A code word for public decision making towards the future, often used interchangeably with policy formation or developing strategies and programmes.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

health policy

1. A set of decisions or commitments to pursue courses of action aimed at achieving defined goals for improving health, stating or inferring the values that underpin these decisions; the health policy may or may not specify the source of funding that can be applied to the action, the planning and management arrangements to be adopted for implementation of the policy, and the relevant institutions to be involved. 2. A general statement of understanding [to] guide decision making that results from an agreement or consensus among relevant partners on the issues to be addressed and on the approaches or strategies to deal with them.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

health sector

Organized public and private health services (including health promotion, disease prevention, diagnostic, treatment and care services), the policies and activities of health departments and ministries, health related nongovernment organizations and community groups, and professional associations.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

health service

Health service: rehabilitation of sick people.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

health system

1. All the activities whose primary purpose is to promote, restore and/or maintain health. 2. The people, institutions and resources, arranged together in accordance with established policies, to improve the health of the population they serve, while responding to people's

legitimate expectations and protecting them against the cost of ill-health through a variety of activities whose primary intent is to improve health.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

health system boundaries

The outer limits (context, institutions, capacities) within which the health system operates.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

heat wave

A period of abnormally hot and/or unusually humid weather. Typically a heat wave lasts two or more days. The exact temperature criteria for what constitutes a heat wave vary by location.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

heatwave

A long lasting period with extremely high surface temperature.

Related categories: 3.1

United Nations, Department of Humanitarian Affairs. Internationally agreed glossary of basic terms related to Disaster Management. Year of publication: 1992. Available from: <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/004DFD3E15B69A67C1256C4C006225C2-dha-glossary-1992.pdf>

heavy urban search and rescue (HUSAR)

1) EU Civil Protection Mechanism module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks are: a) Search for, locate and rescue victims located under debris (such as collapsed buildings and transport incidents). b) Provide lifesaving first aid as required, until handover for further treatment.

2) INSARAG: Difficult and complex technical search and rescue operations. Required to be able to search for entrapped persons using both canine and technical systems, and are envisaged for international assistance in disasters resulting in the collapse of multiple structures, typically found in urban settings, when national response capacity is overwhelmed or does not have the technical capability. Team travelling internationally should arriving in affected country within 48 hours of posting of the disaster.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.5, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

high capacity pumping (HCP)

EU Civil Protection Mechanism module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks are: Provide pumping: 1) in flooded areas, 2) to assist firefighting by delivering water.

Related categories: 3.5, 4.4, 4.5

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

honeypot

It is a computer system designed to attract cyber attackers so that security researchers can see how they operate and what they might be after.

Related categories: 3.3

hop

In computer networks, including the Internet, a hop occurs when a packet is passed from one network segment to the next.

Related categories: 2.2

horizontal integration

Coordination of the functions, activities or operating units that are at the same stage of the service production process. Examples of this type of integration are consolidations, mergers and shared services within a single level of care.

Related categories: 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

hospital capacity

In a mass casualty situation, with many patients arriving at the same time, the theoretical capacity of a hospital would be its ability to admit or manage a number of victims amounting to approximately 20% of its normal bed capacity.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

host

Entity that receives feedback from a reviewer as part of a peer review

The entity can be an organization, partnership, community, city, region, country or other body.

Related categories: 5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

host mobility

Powerful IP new routing capability that allows a device to move to another host network and still be identified.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

host nation support

Any action undertaken in the preparedness and response phases by the country receiving or sending assistance, or by the Commission, to remove foreseeable obstacles to international assistance offered through the Union Mechanism. It includes support from Member States to facilitate the transiting of this assistance through their territory.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.5, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 1313/2013/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32013D1313&from=EN>

hot debrief

1. A debriefing session held immediately after an exercise or incident to identify the strengths and weaknesses of plans, policies and procedures.. 2. A facilitated discussion held immediately following an exercise among exercise players from each functional area that is designed to capture feedback about any issues, concerns, or proposed improvements players may have about the exercise.

The hot wash is an opportunity for players to voice their opinions on the exercise and their own performance. This facilitated meeting allows players to participate in a self-assessment of the exercise play and provides a general assessment of how the jurisdiction performed in the exercise. At this time, evaluators can also seek clarification on certain actions and what prompted players to take them. Evaluators should take notes during the hot wash and include these observations in their analysis. The hot wash should last no more than 30 minutes.

Related categories: 4.1

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

hot wash

Hot debrief.

Related categories: 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

hue

Attribute of a visual sensation where an area appears to be similar to one of the perceived colours, red, yellow, green, and blue, or to a combination of two of them

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

human interpretation

Authenticity as evaluated by an inspector

Related categories: 2.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

human rights

Rights inherent to all human beings, whatever their nationality, place of residence, sex, national or ethnic origin, colour, religion, language or any other status

People are all equally entitled to their human rights without discrimination.

Human rights are: interrelated, universal and inalienable; interdependent and indivisible; equal and non-discriminatory; and both rights and obligations).

Related categories: 2.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

human rights risk analysis (HRRA)

Human rights risk assessment, human rights impact assessment, human rights risk and impact assessment. Process to identify, analyse, evaluate and document human rights-related risks and their impacts, in order to manage risk and to mitigate or prevent adverse human rights impacts and legal infractions

The HRRA is part of the organization's requirement to undertake human rights due diligence to identify, prevent, mitigate and account for how it addresses impacts on human rights.

The HRRA is framed by relevant international human rights principles and conventions and forms a fundamental part of the organization's overall risk assessment.

The HRRA includes an analysis of the severity of actual and potential human rights impacts that the organization can cause or contribute to through its security operations, or which can be linked directly to the organization's operations, projects or services through its business relationships. The HRRA process should include consideration of the operational context, draw on the necessary human rights expertise, and involve direct, meaningful engagement with those interested parties whose rights can be at risk.

The analysis of the consequences of adverse human rights impacts are measured and prioritized in terms of the severity of the impacts.

HRRAs should be undertaken at regular intervals, recognizing that human rights risks can change over time.

HRRAs will vary in complexity with the size of the organization, the risk of severe human rights impacts and the nature and context of its operations.

Related categories: 2.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

human-caused hazards

Hazards that rise from deliberate, intentional human actions to threaten or harm the well-being of others. Examples include school violence, terrorist acts, or sabotage.

Related categories: 3.1

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

humanitarian civil-military coordination

Dialogue and interaction between civilian and military actors in humanitarian emergencies that is necessary to protect and promote humanitarian principles, avoid competition, minimize inconsistency, and when appropriate pursue common goals. Basic strategies range from coexistence to cooperation.

Coordination is a shared responsibility facilitated by liaison and common training. This definition could be extended to interaction between civilian and military actors at national and local levels for all types of emergencies.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.3

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

hydrological hazard

A hazard caused by the occurrence, movement, and distribution of surface and subsurface freshwater and saltwater.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

hydrometeorological hazards

Hazards of atmospheric, hydrological or oceanographic origin.

Examples are tropical cyclones (also known as typhoons and hurricanes), floods (including flash floods), drought, heatwaves and cold spells and coastal storm surges. Hydrometeorological conditions may also be a factor in other hazards such as landslides, wildland fires, locust plagues, epidemics and in the transport and dispersal of toxic substances and volcanic eruption material.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

hypertext transfer protocol (HTTP)

An application layer protocol in the Internet protocol suite model for distributed, collaborative, hypermedia information systems. HTTP is the foundation of data communication for the World Wide Web, where hypertext documents include hyperlinks to other resources that the user can easily access. It is widely used in transfer data approaches such as REST architectures.

Related categories: 2.2

hypertext transfer protocol secure (HTTPS)

Extension of the Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP). It is used for secure communication over a computer network, and is widely used on the Internet. In HTTPS, the communication protocol is encrypted using Transport Layer Security (TLS). The principal motivations for HTTPS are authentication of the accessed website, and protection of the privacy and integrity of the exchanged data while in transit. It protects against man-in-the-middle attacks, and the bidirectional encryption of communications between a client and server protects the communications against sniffing and tampering attacks.

Related categories: 2.2

hypertext transport protocol (HTTP)

Hypertext Transport protocol typically used between a web client and a web server that transports HTML and/or XML. Often used as a transport for SOAP.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

hypothermia

Abnormal lowering of internal body temperature (heat loss) from exposure to cold air, wind, or water

Related categories: 3.4

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icsc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

ice

Ice accumulation when rain hits the cold surface and freezes.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

ice jam flood

The accumulation of floating ice restricting or blocking a river's flow and drainage. Ice jams tend to develop near river bends and obstructions (e.g., bridges).

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

identification

Process of recognizing the attributes that identify an entity

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

immediate aftermath

Refers to response and early recovery generally within the first months after the disaster.

The timeframe considered is the initial response period in which care is focused on the injured and those directly affected by the disaster rather than the temporary replacement of local health services. This period is not fixed and will be influenced by the size of the disaster, numbers of people affected, the level of imbalance between healthcare needs and resources, damage to infrastructure, geographic access to those affected and their health seeking behaviour and whether secondary events occur.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.4

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

impact

Outcome of a disruption affecting objectives

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

impact analysis

Consequence analysis, process of analysing all operational functions and the effect that an operational interruption can have upon them

Impact analysis is part of the risk assessment process and includes business impact analysis. Impact analysis identifies how the loss or damage will manifest itself; the degree for potential escalation of damage or loss with time following an incident; the minimum services and resources (human, physical, and financial) needed to enable business processes to continue to operate at a minimum acceptable level; and the timeframe and extent within which activities, functions and services of the organization should be recovered.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.1, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

impact factor

Scientometric value that shows the yearly average number of citations for articles published in a journal in the last two years.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

impartiality

Actual or perceived presence of objectivity

Objectivity means that conflicts of interest do not exist or are resolved so as not to adversely influence subsequent activities.

Other terms commonly used to convey the element of impartiality are objectivity, independence, freedom from conflict of interests, freedom from bias, lack of prejudice, neutrality, fairness, open-mindedness, even-handedness, detachment and balance.

Related categories: 1.1, 3.2, 3.5, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

improvement plan (IP)

For each task, the Improvement Plan (IP) lists the corrective actions that will be taken, the responsible party or agency, and the expected completion date. The IP is included at the end of the After-Action Report.

Related categories: 3.2

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

improvisation

Act of inventing, composing or performing, with little or no preparation, a reaction to the unexpected

Related categories: 5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

incidence

The number of instances (rate of occurrence) of illness commencing, or of persons falling ill during a given period in a specified population, thus conveying information about the risk of contracting a disease.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

incident

Event that can be, or could lead to, a disruption, loss, emergency or crisis

Related categories: 3.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

incident action plan (IAP)

A document outlining the control objectives, operational period objectives, and response strategy defined by incident command during response planning.

Related categories: 3.2

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

incident base

A location where personnel coordinate and administer logistics functions for an incident. There is typically only one base per incident. (An incident name or other designator is added to the term Base.) The ICP may be co-located with the Incident Base.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

incident command

Process that is conducted as part of an incident management system, and which evolves during the management of an incident

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.6, 3.7, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

incident command post (ICP)

The field location where the primary functions are performed. The Incident Command Post may be co-located with the Incident Base or other incident facilities.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

incident command system (ICS)

A standardized approach to the command, control, and coordination of on-scene incident management, providing a common hierarchy within which personnel from multiple organizations can be effective. ICS is the combination of procedures, personnel, facilities, equipment, and communications operating within a common organizational structure, designed to aid in the management of on-scene resources during incidents. It is used for all kinds of incidents and is applicable to small, as well as large and complex, incidents, including planned events.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

incident commander (IC)

The individual responsible for all incident activities, including the development of strategies and tactics and the ordering and release of resources. The Incident Commander has overall authority and responsibility for conducting incident operations and is responsible for the management of all incident operations at the incident site.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

incident complex

Two or more individual incidents located in the same general area and assigned to a single Incident Commander or Unified Command.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from:

<https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

incident identifier

An identifier assigned by the first PSAP which declares an incident. The form of an Incident Identifier is a URI GUID. Incident Identifiers are globally unique.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

incident management

The broad spectrum of activities and organizations providing effective and efficient operations, coordination, and support applied at all levels of government, utilizing both governmental and nongovernmental resources to plan for, respond to, and recover from an incident, regardless of cause, size, or complexity.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

incident management continuum

A model representing the continuous succession and overlap of incident management functions.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

incident management functions

Prevention, preparedness, mitigation, response, and recovery activities that occur in advance of an incident, during an incident, and/or following an incident.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

incident management system (IMS)

System that defines the roles and responsibilities of personnel and the operating procedures to be used in the management of incidents

IMS is the standardized structure and approach that WHO has adopted to manage its response to public health events and emergencies, and to ensure that the Organization follows best practice in emergency management. WHO has adapted the Incident Management System to consist of six critical functions: Leadership, Partner Coordination, Information and Planning, Health Operations and Technical Expertise, Operations Support and Logistics, and Finance and Administration.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2017. ISBN: 9789241512299. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241512299>

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

incident management team (IMT)

The in-country team responsible for managing and implementing the WHO response to the emergency. It is structured around the six critical Incident Management System functions and their associated sub-functions. The size and composition of the team is flexible and can vary according to context.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2017. ISBN: 9789241512299. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241512299>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

incident manager

The lead of the Incident Management Team, who is responsible for strategic leadership and day-to-day management and oversight of WHO's response to the emergency. The Incident Manager serves as the overall lead of the Incident Management Team and has delegated authority to manage the emergency response, including assigning responsibilities to other critical functions as they are established. S/he works with the health authorities and partners to agree on strategic priorities and objectives for the health response, fully consistent with humanitarian principles

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2017. ISBN: 9789241512299. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241512299>

incident management support team

The team providing day-to-day technical and operational support to the in-country Incident Management Team across all of the critical functions. It is comprised of focal points (either fully dedicated or part-time) for each of the critical functions. An Incident Management Support Team is established at both Regional and Headquarters Offices for graded emergencies, to ensure that resources from across the Organization can be accessed.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2017. ISBN: 9789241512299. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241512299>

incident objectives

Statements of guidance and direction needed to select appropriate strategy(s) and the tactical direction of resources. Incident objectives are based on realistic expectations of what can be accomplished when all allocated resources have been effectively deployed.

Incident objectives must be achievable and measurable, yet flexible enough to allow strategic and tactical alternatives.

Related categories: 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from:

<https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

incident preparedness

Activities taken to prepare for incident response

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.8, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

incident response

Actions taken in order to stop the causes of an imminent hazard and/or mitigate the consequences of potentially destabilizing events) or disruptions, and to recover to a normal situation

Incident response is part of the emergency management process.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

incremental cost-effectiveness ratio

Statistic used in cost-effectiveness analysis to summarize the cost-effectiveness of an intervention, calculated as the difference in cost between two possible interventions, divided by the difference in their effect.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

independent variable

Variable whose variation does not depend on that of another variable.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

indicator-based surveillance (IBS)

1. The systematic (regular) collection, monitoring, analysis and interpretation of structured data, i.e. of indicators produced by a number of well-identified, mostly health-based, formal sources. 2. The routine reporting of cases of disease, including notifiable diseases surveillance systems, sentinel surveillance, laboratory-based surveillance, etc.

This routine reporting is commonly health-care facility based, with reporting done on a weekly or monthly basis.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.7, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

indirect (overhead) costs

Costs that are not directly accountable to a cost object (for example, in research these may be costs for the institution).

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

indirect costs

total sum of morbidity costs (goods and services not produced by the patient because of the illness), mortality costs (goods and services the person could have produced had the illness not been incurred and the person not died prematurely), and productivity cost (related to lost productivity incurred by an employee who leaves work to provide care for the patient).

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

indirect economic loss

A decline in economic value added as a consequence of direct economic loss and /or human and environmental impacts. Indirect economic loss includes microeconomic impacts (e.g. revenue declines owing to business interruption), mesoeconomic impacts (e.g. revenue declines owing to impacts on natural assets, interruptions to supply chains or temporary unemployment) and macroeconomic impacts (e.g. price increases, increases in government debt, negative impact on stock market prices and decline in GDP).

Indirect losses can occur inside or outside of the hazard area and often have a time lag. As a result, they may be intangible or difficult to measure.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

indirectly affected

People who have suffered consequences, other than or in addition to direct effects, over time, due to disruption or changes in economy, critical infrastructure, basic services, commerce or work, or social, health and psychological consequences.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

inductive research

A 'bottom-up' approach to inquiry that involves building theories based on observation and analysis of data gathered in the field.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

infection

The entry and development or multiplication of an infectious agent in the body of humans and animals that may constitute a public health risk.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

infection prevention & control

1. A practical and proven set of organizational and technical approaches and measures to prevent the spread of avoidable infections and antimicrobial resistance within both community and health care settings.

2. The practical discipline concerned with preventing health care-associated infection.

The purpose of infection prevention and control in health care is as follows: to prevent the occurrence of health care-associated infections in patients, health care workers, visitors and other persons associated with health care settings; to prepare health care facilities for the early detection and management of epidemics and to organize a prompt and effective response; to contribute to a coordinated response to control community-acquired infectious diseases, endemic or epidemic, that may be “amplified” via health care; to contribute to preventing the emergence of antimicrobial resistance and /or dissemination of resistant strains of microorganisms; and to minimize the environmental impact of these infections or their management.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

inflatable rescue boat (IRB)

Smaller boat with a raft like construction. They can be rolled up for transportation and launched very easily. They have a rigid transom on which to attach an engine, and can have a semi-rigid floor, e.g., a number of aluminum strips covered with Hypalon.

Related categories: 3.4

Rescue 3 Europe Ltd. Rescue 3 International - Water and Flood Rescue Manual v6.2020. Available from: <https://www.rescue3europe.com/student-downloads/water-and-flood-rescue-manual/>

information

Data processed, organized and correlated to produce meaning

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.3, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

information bias

Bias arising from measurement error.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

information management

The collection, organization, and control over the structure, processing, and delivery of information from one or more sources and distribution to one or more audiences who have a stake in that information.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

information report

Report with the same content as that of situation report but issued by an agency in the event that international assistance has not been subject of an official request by the government.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.6, 3.7

United Nations, Department of Humanitarian Affairs. Internationally agreed glossary of basic terms related to Disaster Management. Year of publication: 1992. Available from: <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/004DFD3E15B69A67C1256C4C006225C2-dha-glossary-1992.pdf>

informed consent

Process by which a person agrees to join a study having been informed about, and understood, its purpose.

Related categories: 1.1

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

infrastructure

System of facilities, equipment and services needed for the operation of an organization

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

ingress protection 68

This is the maximum degree of protection that a cell phone or other electronic device has against the access of particles, such as dust, and liquids.

Related categories: 2.5

inherently dangerous property

Property that, if in the hands of an unauthorized individual, would create an imminent threat of death or serious bodily harm

EXAMPLE: Lethal weapons, ammunition, explosives, chemical agents, biological agents and toxins, nuclear or radiological materials.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

inject

Scripted piece of information inserted into an exercise that is designed to elicit a response or decision and facilitate the flow of the exercise

Injects can be written, oral, televised and/or transmitted via any means (e.g. phone, email, fax, voice, radio or sign).

In simulation exercises: scripted piece of information inserted into an exercise, aimed at one or more participants (players), which is designed to elicit a specific response and facilitate the flow of the exercise. Injects can be written, oral, televised or transmitted via other means (e.g. PowerPoint, fax, phone, e-mail, voice, radio, or sign) by one of the controllers/facilitators.

Related categories: 3.8, 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

inject matrix

In simulation exercises: document detailing the sequence of events to be followed during an exercise, including the time indication of each event. It also identifies who is responsible for tasks, and provides the exercise control/facilitators with a 'script' to follow.

Related categories: 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

injury

The physical or physiological bodily harm resulting from interaction of the body with energy (mechanical, thermal, electrical, chemical or radiant, or due to extreme pressure) in an amount, or at a rate of transfer, that exceeds physical or physiological tolerance.

Injury can also result from lack of vital elements, such as oxygen. Poisoning by and toxic effects of substances are included, as is damage of or due to implanted devices. Maltreatment syndromes are included even if physical or physiological bodily harm has not been reported. Injury usually has rapid onset in response to a well- defined event (e.g. a car crash, striking the ground after falling, drinking a strongly alkaline liquid, an overdose of a medication, a burn sustained during a surgical procedure). These events are often referred to as external causes of injury. The injurious energy can, however, originate from the injured person and / or from his or her immediate environment (e.g. a person running on a hot day sustains heat exhaustion), and injury can be caused by the injured person (i.e. intentional self- harm).

Related categories: 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

inpatient referral care FMT

Type 3 WHO foreign medical team classification. Complex inpatient referral surgical care including intensive care capacity. In addition to type

2 services, a type 3 FMT provides: complex reconstructive wound and orthopaedic care, enhanced, X-ray, blood transfusion, lab and rehab services, high level paediatric and adult anaesthesia, intensive care beds with 24 h monitoring and ability to ventilate, acceptance and referral services.

Capacity: 1 operating theatre with at least 2 operating rooms: 40 inpatient beds; 15 major or 30 minor operations per day, 4–6 intensive care beds If facility provided: wards, operating theatre (2+ tables), outpatient plus intensive care area, Day and night services.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

inpatient surgical emergency care FMT

Type 2 WHO foreign medical team classification. Inpatient acute care, general and obstetric surgery for trauma and other major conditions. Services provided include: Surgical triage, assessment and advanced life support, definitive wound and basic fracture management, damage control surgery, emergency general and obstetric surgery, inpatient care for non-trauma emergencies basic anaesthesia, X-ray, blood transfusion, lab and rehab services acceptance

and referral services

Capacity: 1 operating theatre with 1 operating room: 20 inpatient beds; 7 major or 15 minor operations per day. If facility provided, at least 20 inpatient

beds and 1 operating theatre and 1 table. Day and night services.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

input

A quantified amount of a resource put in a process.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

instant call recorder

A device that allows the user to instantly playback all (or portions of) a call for service to clarify or validate what was heard by the operator to what was said by the caller. Also called and Instant Recall recorder.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

Institute of Electrical and Electronic Engineers

A publishing and standards making body responsible for many telecom and computing standards.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

instrumental activities for daily living (IADL)

Activities that allow a person to live independently in a community.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

integrated communications

Communications facilitated through the development and use of a common communications plan.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

Integrated Health Services Delivery Network

A network of organizations that provides, or makes arrangements to provide, equitable, comprehensive and integrated health services to a defined population and is willing to be held accountable for its clinical and economic outcomes and for the health status of the population that it serves .

Related categories: 4.2, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

integrated services digital network (ISDN)

International standard for a public communication network to handle circuit- switched digital voice, circuit-switched data, and packet-switched data.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

integrity

Property of safeguarding the accuracy and completeness of assets

Related categories: 3.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

intelligent network

A telecommunications network that has functions and controls distributed at various nodes on and off the network, enabling great flexibility in transport.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

intensive care unit

A specialized medical care facility where there are physicians, surgeons, nurses, anaesthetists and other appropriate skills and the necessary equipment to provide emergency, acute and continuing care to critically ill persons.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

intensive disaster risk

The risk of high-severity, mid- to low-frequency disasters, mainly associated with major hazards. Note: Intensive disaster risk is mainly a characteristic of large cities or densely populated areas that are not only exposed to intense hazards such as strong earthquakes, active volcanoes, heavy floods, tsunamis or major storms but also have high levels of vulnerability to these hazards.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

interactive voice response (IVR)

A computer system accessible by registered users utilized to identify the Service Provider and 24 X 7 access number for telephone numbers which have been ported or pooled.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

interconnectivity

An attribute of complex adaptive systems where the component parts are loosely or tightly coupled with one another, adding to the complexity of the system.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.6, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

interested party

Stakeholder, person or organization that can affect, be affected by, or perceive itself to be affected by a decision or activity

EXAMPLE: Customers, owners, personnel, providers, bankers, regulators, unions, partners or society that can include competitors or opposing pressure groups.

A decision maker can be an interested party.

Impacted communities and local populations are considered to be interested parties.

This constitutes one of the common terms and core definitions of the high level structure for ISO management system standards. The original definition has been modified by adding the example and the notes to entry.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.6, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

interference

Electromagnetic interference, radio interference, or radio frequency interference is the disturbance that occurs in any electronic circuit, component, or system caused by an external or internal source of electromagnetic radiation.

Related categories: 3.3

internal attack

Attack perpetrated by people or entities directly or indirectly linked with the legitimate manufacturer, originator of the goods or rights holder (staff of the rights holder, subcontractor, supplier, etc.)

Related categories: 2.4, 3.1, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

internal audit

Audit conducted by, or on behalf of, an organization itself for management review and other internal purposes, and which can form the basis for an organization's self-declaration of conformity

In many cases, particularly in smaller organizations, independence can be demonstrated by the freedom from responsibility for the activity being audited.

Related categories: 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

internal validity

Extent to which an individual study can answer the research question.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

internally displaced persons (IDP)

Persons or groups of persons who have been forced or obliged to flee or to leave their homes or places of habitual residence, in particular as a result of, or in order to, avoid the effects of armed conflicts, situations of generalized violence, violations of human rights or natural or human-made disasters, and who have not crossed an internationally recognized State border.

Related categories: 1.1, 3.2, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC)

The world's largest humanitarian network. Its secretariat supports local Red Cross and Red Crescent action in more than 192 countries, bringing together almost 14 million volunteers.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.5

International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies. IFRC website. Available from: <https://www.ifrc.org/about-ifrc> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

international health regulations (IHR)

Regulations designed to prevent the international spread of disease adopted by the Fifty-eighth World Health Assembly on 23 May 2005 and which entered into force on 15 June 2007. The purpose and scope of the IHR (2005) are to prevent, protect against, control and provide a public health response to the international spread of disease in ways that are commensurate with and restricted to public health risks and which avoid unnecessary interference with international traffic and trade.

Related categories: 1.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

international law

The corpus of principles, rules, treaties and procedures that govern the conduct, relationships and exchanges between and among States and juridical institutions. Laws that concern health include, inter alia, the International Health Regulations, the Geneva Protocols, human rights laws, environmental and climate laws, International Humanitarian Laws, relevant UN protocols.

Related categories: 1.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

international mobile equipment identity (IMEI)

15- or 17-digit code that uniquely identifies mobile phone sets. The IMEI code can enable a GSM (Global System for Mobile communication) or UMTS (Universal Mobile Telecommunications Service) network to prevent a misplaced or stolen phone from initiating calls.

Related categories: 2.2

NENA (USA National Emergency Number Association). NENA Glossary of 9-1-1 Terminology. Year of publication: 2021. Available from: https://nenawiki.org/wiki/NENA_Glossary_of_9-1-1_Terminology (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

International Search And Rescue Advisory Group (INSARAG)

Global network of more than 90 countries and organizations under the United Nations umbrella. INSARAG deals with urban search and rescue (USAR) related issues, aiming to establish minimum international standards for USAR teams and methodology for international coordination in earthquake response based on the INSARAG Guidelines endorsed by the United Nations General Assembly Resolution 57/150 of 2002, on "Strengthening the Effectiveness and Coordination of International Urban Search and Rescue Assistance".

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

United Nations, International Search And Rescue Advisory Group. INSARAG website. Available from: <https://www.insarag.org> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

International Standards Organization (ISO)

Independent, non-governmental international organization with a membership of 161 national standards bodies.

Related categories: 1.1

NENA (USA National Emergency Number Association). NENA Glossary of 9-1-1 Terminology. Year of publication: 2021. Available from: https://nenawiki.org/wiki/NENA_Glossary_of_9-1-1_Terminology (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

international statistical classification of diseases and related health problems (ICD)

Globally used tool to categorize diseases.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

international supply chain

Supply chain that at some point crosses an international or economic border

All portions of this chain are considered international from the time a purchase order is concluded to the point where the goods are released from customs control in the destination country or economy.

If treaties or regional agreements have eliminated customs clearance of goods from specified countries or economies, the end of the international supply chain is the port of entry into the destination country or economy where the goods would have cleared customs if the agreements or treaties had not been in place.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

International Telecommunications Union (ITU)

The telecommunications agency of the United Nations established to provide worldwide standard communications practices and procedures. Formerly CCITT

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

internet control message protocol (ICMP)

Supporting protocol in the Internet protocol suite. It is used by network devices, including routers, to send error messages and operational information indicating success or failure when communicating with another IP address, for example, when an error is indicated when a requested service is not available or that a host or router could not be reached. For IPv6 addresses, ICMPv6 is used instead.

Related categories: 2.2

Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF)

Lead standard setting authority for internet protocols.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

internet message access protocol (IMAP)

An Internet standard protocol used by email clients to retrieve email messages from a mail server over a TCP/IP connection.

Related categories: 2.2

internet of things (IoT)

The internet of things is a concept that refers to a digital interconnection of everyday objects with the internet. It is, in short, the connection of the internet more with objects than with people. It is also often referred to as the internet of all things or the internet of things.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

internet protocol (IP)

The method by which data is sent from one computer to another on the Internet or other networks.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

internet protocol address (IP address)

A 32-bit address assigned to hosts using TCP/IP. An IP address belongs to one of five classes (A, B, C, D, or E) and is written as 4 octets separated by periods (dotted decimal format). Each address consists of a network number, an optional sub network number, and a host number. The network and sub network numbers together are used for routing, while the host number is used to address an individual host within the network or sub network.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

internet protocol security (IPsec)

Internet Protocol Security (IPsec) is a secure network protocol suite that authenticates and encrypts the packets of data to provide secure encrypted communication between two computers over an Internet Protocol (IP) network. It is used in virtual private networks (VPNs).

Related categories: 2.2

internet protocol suite

The Internet protocol suite, commonly known as TCP/IP, is the set of communications protocols used in the Internet and similar computer networks. The current foundational protocols in the suite are the Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) and the Internet Protocol (IP).

Related categories: 2.2

internet protocol telephony (IP telephony)

A general term for the technologies that use the IP's packet-switched connections to exchange voice, fax, and other forms of information that have traditionally been carried over the dedicated Circuit-Switched (CS) connections of the PSTN. The IP address may change each time the user logs on.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

internet protocol version 4 (IPv4)

Internet Protocol version 4 (IPv4) is the fourth version of the Internet Protocol (IP) which defines and enables internetworking at the internet layer of the Internet protocol suite. IPv4 is a connectionless protocol, and operates on a best-effort delivery model, in that it does not guarantee delivery, nor does it assure proper sequencing or avoidance of duplicate delivery. These aspects, including data integrity, are addressed by an upper layer transport protocol, such as the Transmission Control Protocol (TCP).

Related categories: 2.2

internet protocol version 6 (IPv6)

Internet Protocol version 6 (IPv6) is the most recent version of the Internet Protocol (IP), the communications protocol that provides an identification and location system for computers on networks and routes traffic across the Internet. It solves issues existing in IPv4, such as the limitation of available public addresses. It is commonly used in Internet of Things (IoT) scenarios.

Related categories: 2.2

internet service provider (ISP)

Company that provides Internet access to other companies and individuals

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

internet telephony service provider (ITSP)

A Company providing Internet based telephony services.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

interoperability

1. The ability of systems, personnel, and equipment to provide and receive functionality, data, information, and/or services to and from other systems, personnel, and equipment, between both public and private agencies, departments, and other organizations, in a manner enabling them to operate effectively together. 2. diverse systems: ability of diverse systems and

organizations to work together. 3. single-entry point: ability of single-entry point to route queries for objects carrying unique identifiers (UIDs) to the responsible authoritative source for trusted verification function (TVF)

Interoperability includes the ability of multiple authentication systems to deliver similar responses to user groups.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

intersectoral collaboration

The process of joint planning, construction, implementation and monitoring by ministries and authorities belonging to different public sectors, including sharing of resources in order to enable each ministry or body to carry out their responsibilities that were mutually agreed upon.

Related categories: 3.2, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

interval data

Data measured on a scale in which the points are equal distances apart.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

intervention

An activity or set of activities aimed at modifying a process, course of action or sequence of events, in order to change one or several of their characteristics such as performance or expected outcome.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

intervention team

EU Civil Protection Mechanism human and material resources, including modules, set up by one or more Member States for civil protection interventions.

Related categories: 3.4, 4.2, 4.4

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

interworking

Concept where systems or components from different origins or companies, running on different hardware and operating systems, working together to perform some tasks using common standard network procedure or protocol.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

intrusion detection system (IDS)

An intrusion detection system (IDS) is a system that monitors network traffic for suspicious activity and alerts when such activity is discovered.

Related categories: 3.3

investment

Allocation of resources to achieve defined objectives and other benefits

Investment takes two main forms: direct spending on buildings, machinery and similar assets; and indirect spending on financial securities such as bonds and shares.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.3, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

invocation

Act of declaring that an organization's business continuity arrangements need to be put into effect in order to continue delivery of key products or services

Related categories: 2.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

IPv6 over low power wireless personal area networks (6LoWPAN)

6LoWPAN is a standard that enables the use of IPv6 over networks based on the IEEE 802.15.4 standard. It makes it possible for devices such as wireless network nodes to communicate directly with other IP devices.

Related categories: 2.2

isolation

Separation of ill or contaminated persons or affected baggage, containers, conveyances, goods or postal parcels from others in such a manner as to prevent the spread of infection or contamination.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

iterative logic model

Logic models that are adapted at any point in the research or evaluation study to reflect findings or new knowledge.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

jitter

Jitter is the variation in time delay between when a signal is transmitted and when it's received over a network connection.

Related categories: 2.2

judgemental sampling

Sampling based on the opinion of an expert.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

jurisdiction

An organization (level of government or designated agency) with the authority and responsibility to provide particular functions and services within a defined area.

Related categories: 1.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

key informant interview

Qualitative in-depth interviews with people with relevant knowledge or expertise.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

key performance indicator (KPI)

Quantifiable measure that an organization uses to gauge or compare performance in terms of meeting its strategic and operational objectives

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

keylogger

Keyloggers are activity-monitoring software programs that give hackers access to your personal data.

Related categories: 3.3

keystore

The location on the disk or card where cryptographic keys are stored.

Related categories: 3.3

lahar

Hot or cold mixture of earthen material flowing on the slope of a volcano either during or between volcanic eruptions.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

landline

Colloquial term for the Public Switched Telephone Network access via an actual copper or fibre optic transmission line that travels underground or on telephone poles. Used to differentiate the “wireless” connectivity of a cellular or PCS system.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

landmark location

Landmark locations can be Civic Addresses but are generally the names of buildings or other commonly known recognized places (e.g., The Empire State Building, The Alamo, etc.) or the name by which a prominent feature is publicly known.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 3.3, 3.7

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

landslide

Wide variety of processes that result in the downward and outward movement of slope-forming materials including rock, soil, artificial fill or a combination of these

Related categories: 2.2, 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

landslide following earthquake

Independent of the presence of water, mass movement may also be triggered by earthquakes.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

lava flow

The ejected magma that moves as a liquid mass downslope from a volcano during an eruption.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

lead agency

Agency or sector responsible for managing specific types of emergencies.

Related categories: 3.2, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

leader

The ICS title for an individual who is responsible for supervision of a unit, strike team, resource team, or task force.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

leadership

The process of engaging others and fostering constructive processes for working together, and sustaining collaborative interaction to guide activities and achieve objectives.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

leeway

The movement of a search object through water caused by winds blowing against exposed surfaces

Related categories: 3.4

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icsc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

lessons learned

Identified issues for which remedial actions may be implemented, in order to improve performance.

Related categories: 3.2, 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

level of event

A structured process, internal to an organization, that evaluates the extent, complexity and probable duration of an incident with reference to the response resources that will be required.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.6, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

level of risk

Magnitude of a risk or combination of risks, expressed in terms the combination of consequences and their likelihood.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.6, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

liaison

A form of communication for establishing and maintaining mutual understanding and cooperation.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

liaison officer

A member of the Command Staff responsible for coordinating with representatives from cooperating and assisting agencies or organizations assisting at an incident.

Related categories: 3.3, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

licensure

Process by which a governmental authority grants permission to an individual practitioner or health care organization to operate or to engage in an occupation or profession.

Licensure regulations are generally established to ensure that an organization or individual meets minimum standards to protect public health and safety. Licensure to individuals is usually granted after some form of examination or proof of education and maybe renewed periodically through payment of a fee and/or proof of continuing education or professional competence. Organizational licensure is granted following an on-site inspection to determine if minimum health and safety standards have been met.

Related categories: 1.1

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

life support emergency

Immediate help, specialized techniques and apparatus applied in assisting a seriously injured person or a disaster victim to maintain the vital functions.

Related categories: 3.3

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

life-years gained

Additional number of years of life that a person lives as a result of receiving a treatment.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

light detection and ranging (LiDAR)

Method for measuring distances by illuminating the target with laser light and measuring the reflection with a sensor.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.3

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

lightning

A high-voltage, visible electrical discharge produced by a thunderstorm and followed by the sound of thunder.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgLS55evtT8jBNi/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

likelihood

Chance of something happening

In risk management terminology, the word “likelihood” is used to refer to the chance of something happening, whether defined, measured or determined objectively or subjectively, qualitatively or quantitatively, and described using general terms or mathematically (such as a probability or a frequency over a given time period).

The English term “likelihood” does not have a direct equivalent in some languages; instead, the equivalent of the term “probability” is often used. However, in English, “probability” is often narrowly interpreted as a mathematical term. Therefore, in risk management terminology, “likelihood” is used with the intent that it should have the same broad interpretation as the term “probability” has in many languages other than English.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.1, 3.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

Likert scale

Rating scale used to measure attitudes or opinions on a linear scale with respondents asked to choose one from a number of values.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

line of sight

A characteristic of electromagnetic radiation or acoustic wave propagation is where the transmitter and receiver have a direct vision so that the transmitted signal (wireless in the case of radio) can be transmitted without any obstacle between them.

Related categories: 3.3

local area network (LAN)

A local area network (LAN) is a collection of devices connected together in one physical location, such as a building, office, or home. A LAN can be small or large, ranging from a home network with one user to an enterprise network with thousands of users and devices in an office or school.

Related categories: 2.2

local loop

A physical facility between a customer’s network interface and the local serving central office. The most common form of local loop is a pair of wires.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

location determination

Act of using measurements taken from the access network to calculate or otherwise discover the physical location of a device.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.1, 3.6, 3.7

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

location information

The actual geo or civic location data independent of its containers, protocols or reference mechanisms.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.1, 3.6, 3.7

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

location validation

Refers to the action of ensuring that a civic address can be used to discern a route to a PSAP.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.1, 3.6, 3.7

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

logframe (logical framework)

Array of different approaches to mapping a process. Logical framework analysis.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

logic model

Hypothesized description of the chain of causes and effects.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

logical framework analysis (LFA)

A formalized approach to planning, programming and evaluation, adopted by many agencies as aid management tool. Logframes define the project's objectives and indicators for monitoring and evaluation.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

logical structure

Arrangement of data to optimize their access or processing by given user (human or machine)

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.3

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

login

The process of identifying and authenticating oneself to a computer, ACD or 112 attendant position system.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

logistic regression

Statistical model that uses a logistic function to model a binary dependent variable.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

logistical support

EU Civil Protection Mechanism essential equipment or services required for expert teams referred to in Article 17(1) to perform their tasks, inter alia communication, temporary accommodation, food or in-country transport.

Related categories: 3.5, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 1313/2013/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32013D1313&from=EN>

logistics

The range of operational activities concerned with supply, handling, transportation and distribution of materials. Also applicable to the transportation of people

Related categories: 3.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

United Nations, Department of Humanitarian Affairs. Internationally agreed glossary of basic terms related to Disaster Management. Year of publication: 1992. Available from: <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/004DFD3E15B69A67C1256C4C006225C2-dha-glossary-1992.pdf>

logistics section

The Incident Command System Section responsible for providing facilities, services, and material support for the incident.

Related categories: 3.5

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf>

logistics section chief

A member of the General Staff who provides resources and needed services to support the achievement of the incident objectives.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

longitudinal study

Study that follows participants over time.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

loop back

A type of diagnostic test in which a transmitted signal is returned to the transmitting device and then compared to the original signal.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

LoRaWAN

LoRa (from "long range") is a proprietary low-power wide-area network modulation technique. It is based on spread-spectrum modulation techniques derived from chirp spread spectrum (CSS) technology. Since LoRa defines the lower physical layer, the upper networking layers were lacking. LoRaWAN is one of several protocols that were developed to define the upper layers of the network. LoRaWAN is a cloud-based medium access control (MAC) layer protocol, but acts mainly as a network layer protocol for managing communication between LPWAN gateways and end-node devices as a routing protocol, maintained by the LoRa Alliance.

Related categories: 2.2

low power wide area network (LPWAN)

A set of long-range radio technologies that use low power frequencies to obtain a very long transmission distance while remaining very robust to possible interference or noise.

Type of wireless telecommunication wide area network designed to allow long-range communications at a low bit rate among things (connected objects), such as sensors operated on a battery. The low power, low bit rate, and intended use distinguish this type of network from a wireless WAN that is designed to connect users or businesses, and carry more data, using more power.

Related categories: 3.3

MAC address

A media access control address (MAC address) is a unique identifier assigned to a network interface controller (NIC) for use as a network address in communications within a network segment.

Related categories: 2.2

machine learning algorithm

The act of building a mathematical model based on sample data in order to make predictions or decisions without being explicitly programmed to do so. This can also be described as predictive analytics.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

machine science

The use of advanced computational techniques to generate data analytics, hypotheses and develop models.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

machine-readable format

Structured data in a format that can be processed by a computer.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

macroeconomic impacts

Impact on the economy as a whole.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

major injury

Injury severity score >15, comprising at least one severe life-threatening regional injury. OR at least two severe non-life-threatening regional injuries. OR at least two severe non-life-threatening injuries plus at least two injuries of moderate severity.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

management

Coordinated activities to direct and control an organization

Related categories: 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

management by objectives

A management approach, fundamental to NIMS, that involves (1) establishing objectives, e.g., specific, measurable and realistic outcomes to be achieved;(2) identifying strategies, tactics, and tasks to achieve the objectives; (3) performing the tactics and tasks and measuring and documenting results in achieving the objectives; and (4) taking corrective action to modify strategies, tactics, and/or performance to achieve the objectives.

Related categories: 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

management plan

Clearly defined and documented plan of action, typically covering the key personnel, resources, services, and actions needed to implement the management process

Related categories: 3.2, 3.6, 4.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

management system

Set of interrelated or interacting elements of an organization to establish policies and objectives and processes to achieve those objectives

A management system can address a single discipline or several disciplines.

The system elements include the organization's structure, roles and responsibilities, planning and operation.

The scope of a management system can include the whole of the organization, specific and identified functions of the organization, specific and identified sections of the organization, or one or more functions across a group of organizations.

This constitutes one of the common terms and core definitions of the high level structure for ISO management system standards.

Related categories: 1.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

management system consultancy and/or associated risk assessment

Participation in designing, implementing or maintaining a supply chain security management system and in conducting risk assessments

EXAMPLE: Preparing or producing manuals or procedures; giving specific advice, instructions or solutions towards the development and implementation of a supply chain security management system; conducting internal audits (3.1.34); conducting risk assessment and analysis.

Arranging training and participating as a trainer is not considered as consultancy, provided that, where the course relates to supply chain security management systems or auditing, the course is confined to the provision of generic information that is freely available in the public domain, i.e. the trainer does not provide company-specific solutions.

Related categories: 1.1, 3.2, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

manager

The individual within an ICS organizational unit assigned specific managerial responsibilities (e.g., Staging Area Manager or Camp Manager).

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

MARCH

Mnemonic acronym for Massive hemorrhage, Airway, Respirations, Circulation, Head injury/Hypothermia, used by Tactical Combat Casualty Care (TCCC) trained individuals to help remember the proper order of treatment.

Tactical Combat Casualty Care guidelines are evidence-based and battlefield-proven to reduce deaths at the point of injury (POI). Department of Defense (DOD) and NATO allies require TCCC training for deploying forces because it combines effective tactics and medicine.

Related categories: 3.4

U.S. Army, Tactical Combat Casualty Care (TCCC) Working Group. Tactical Combat Casualty Care Handbook. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: <https://usacac.army.mil/sites/default/files/publications/17493.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

marginal cost

The change in total cost that results from a unit increase in output.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

mass care

Actions taken to protect evacuees and other disaster victims from the effects of the disaster. Activities include providing temporary shelter, food, medical care, clothing, and other essential life support needs to the people who have been displaced because of a disaster or threatened disaster.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

mass casualty incident

An event which generates more patients at one time than locally available resources can manage using routine procedures.

It requires exceptional emergency arrangements and additional or extraordinary assistance.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

mass casualty management system

A coherent and interrelated set of established procedures, policies, and plans that contribute to the shared objectives of optimizing the baseline capacity to deal with patient populations expected in a mass casualty incident, and efficiently increasing this capacity during the response to a mass casualty incident.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

mass gathering

An organized or unplanned event can be classified as a mass gathering if the number of people attending is sufficient to strain the planning and response resources of the community, State or nation hosting the event.

A gathering of persons usually defined as more than a specified number of persons (which may be as few as 1,000 persons although much of the available literature describes gatherings exceeding 25,000 persons) at a specific location for a specific purpose (a social function, large public event or sports competition) for a defined period of time.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

mass movement

Displacement of materials such as soil, rock, mud, snow or a combination of matter down a slope under the influence of gravity

Related categories: 1.1, 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

mass rescue operation (MRO)

Search and rescue services characterized by the need for immediate response to large numbers of persons in distress, such that the capabilities normally available to search and rescue authorities are inadequate

Related categories: 3.4

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icssc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

master clock

An accurate timing device that generates synchronization signals to control other clocks or equipment.

Related categories: 2.2

NENA (USA National Emergency Number Association). NENA Glossary of 9-1-1 Terminology. Year of publication: 2021. Available from: https://nenawiki.org/wiki/NENA_Glossary_of_9-1-1_Terminology (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

material good

Manufactured, grown product or one secured from nature

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.5, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

material good life cycle

Stages in the life of a material good including conception, design, manufacture, storage, service, resell and disposal

Related categories: 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

maximum acceptable outage (MAO)

Maximum tolerable period of disruption (MTPD), time it would take for adverse impacts, which can arise as a result of not providing a product/service or performing an activity, to become unacceptable

Related categories: 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

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Maximum acceptable outage (MAO), time it would take for adverse impacts, which can arise as a result of not providing a product/service or performing an activity , to become unacceptable

Related categories: 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

maximum transmission unit (MTU)

The maximum transfer unit is a computer networking term that expresses the size in bytes of the largest unit of data that can be sent using a communications protocol.

Related categories: 2.2

MAYDAY

The international radio telephony distress signal

Related categories: 3.3, 3.8

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icssc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

measurement

Process to determine a value

This constitutes one of the common terms and core definitions of the high level structure for ISO management system standards.

Related categories: 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

MEDEVAC

1. Emergency Evacuation of a person for medical reasons

2. A helicopter used for medevac

Related categories: 3.4

medical act

1. Any intervention or effort by a medically qualified person to bring health assistance to a patient. 2. In health economics, it is the measurement unit for calculating health-care costs, health expenditure and for quantifying a health professional's remuneration.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

medical aerial evacuation of disaster victims (MEVAC)

EU Civil Protection Mechanism module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks is: Transport disaster victims to health facilities for medical treatment using helicopters/planes with stretchers.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.5, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

MEDICO

Medical advice. Exchange of medical information and recommended treatment for sick or injured persons where treatment cannot be administered directly by prescribing medical personnel

Related categories: 3.3

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icsc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

medium urban search and rescue (MUSAR)

1) EU Civil Protection Mechanism module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks are: a) Search for, locate and rescue victims located under debris (such as collapsed buildings and transport incidents). b) Provide lifesaving first aid as required, until handover for further treatment.

2) INSARAG: Technical search and rescue operations in structural collapse incidents, required to be able to search for entrapped persons. International teams must arrive in the affected country within 32 hours of posting the disaster.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.5, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

member-checking

Technique used in qualitative research in which the participants check the findings.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

mental health and psychosocial support

Any type of local or outside support that aims to protect or promote psychosocial wellbeing and /or prevent or treat mental disorder.

Traditionally, mental health care has been used by health professionals to describe specialized interventions to treat individuals diagnosed with mental health conditions. Psychosocial support and psychosocial interventions are terms used by a broader range of workers in the emergency response field to refer to activities that support both the psychological and social health of individuals and communities as a whole rather than focusing specifically on treating mental health conditions.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

MeSH

Controlled vocabulary for the purpose of indexing journal articles and books in the life sciences.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

mesh network

A mesh network is a network in which devices or nodes are linked together, branching off other devices or nodes. These networks are set up to efficiently route data between devices and clients. They help organizations provide a consistent connection throughout a physical space.

Related categories: 2.2

message

Information that is transmitted between one or more entities.

Related categories: 2.2

message encryption

Message encryption is a process of disguising a message in such a way as to hide its substance.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

message integrity

Message integrity mechanisms provide protection against unauthorized message modifications.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

meta-analysis

Statistical combination of data from a series of studies (usually in a systematic review) to obtain a summary effect estimate.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

metadata

information to describe audio-visual content and data essence in a format defined by ISO or any other authority

EXAMPLE Time and date, text strings, location identifying data, audio and any other associated, linked or processed information.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

meteorological hazard

A hazard caused by short-lived, micro- to meso-scale extreme weather and atmospheric conditions that last from minutes to days.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

methodological search filters

Search strategies designed to help people search the literature for studies of a particular design.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

Metropolitan Area Network (MAN)

A metropolitan area network (MAN) is a computer network that connects computers within a metropolitan area, which could be a single large city, multiple cities and towns, or any given large area with multiple buildings. A MAN is larger than a local area network (LAN) but smaller than a wide area network (WAN).

Related categories: 2.2

microservice

Microservices architecture is an approach to software development that consists of building an application as a set of small services, which run in their own process and communicate with lightweight mechanisms.

Related categories: 2.2

military medicine

The art and science of medicine, including in particular, critical care, emergency surgery and traumatology, as applied to mass casualty situations, battlefield conditions, the needs of soldiers and, increasingly, of civilian disaster victims.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.5, 4.3

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

minimization

Technique used to allocate participants to their intervention group in a randomized trial which seeks to balance participant characteristics across groups.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

minimum business continuity objective (MBCO)

Minimum capacity or level of services and/or products that is acceptable to an organization to achieve its business objectives during a disruption

Related categories: 3.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

minimum data set (MDS)

Collection of datasets designed to support the information structure in SIGRUN.

It includes all the basic information necessary to support the coordinated action of the main agencies and organizations involved in the first response to mass casualty incidents and disasters in the European Union (with a wide variation in the existing practices).

Example: in terms of operational procedures: The minimum data necessary to carry out the standard operational procedures (SOPs). A dataset is a structured collection of data generally associated with a unique body of work. A database is an organized collection of data stored as multiple datasets. Those datasets are generally stored and accessed electronically from a computer system that allows the data to be easily accessed, manipulated, and updated.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.6

European Association for Injury Prevention and Safety Promotion (EuroSafe). IDB-Minimum Data Set (IDB-MDS) Data Dictionary. Year of publication: 2016. Available from: https://www.eurosafe.eu.com/uploads/inline-files/IDB_MDS_Data_Dictionary_JAN%202017.pdf (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

minimum deployment standards

Criteria, which foreign medical teams (FMT) must adhere to.

While many standards describe structure and performance during deployment these should be acknowledged and implemented prior to deployment. This allows the affected country to have confidence in the capabilities of the FMT and an opportunity to hold FMT accountable if they do not meet their stated capability.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.5, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

missing person

1. A person whose whereabouts are unknown to his / her relatives and /or who, on the basis of reliable information, has been reported missing in accordance with the national legislation in connection with an international or non-international armed conflict, a situation of internal violence or disturbances, natural catastrophes or any other situation that may require the intervention of a competent State authority.

2. Persons whose status during or after an emergency is not known.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

mitigation

Limitation of any negative consequence of a particular incident

Related categories: 2.3, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

mixed method matrix

A technique using a table to summarize and display the qualitative and quantitative data for a given case for integration during analysis; it enables researchers to view more information about the case during analysis.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

mixed methods research

Research that uses both qualitative and quantitative methods.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

mobile satellite communication (SATCOM)

System Communication of necessary detailed information by disaster managers using satellite exchange when other communication facilities have broken down due to the disaster.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.3

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

mobilization

The processes and procedures for activating, assembling, and transporting resources that have been requested to respond to or support an incident.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.8, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

modem

An interface device which allows digital data signals to be transmitted over analog telephone lines.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

module

An EU Civil Protection Mechanism self-sufficient and autonomous predefined task- and needs-driven arrangement of Member States' capabilities or a mobile operational team of the Member States, representing a combination of human and material means that can be described in terms of its capacity for intervention or by the task(s) it is able to undertake.

Related categories: 3.5, 4.4

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 1313/2013/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32013D1313&from=EN>

monitoring

Determining the status of a system, a process or an activity

To determine the status, there can be a need to check, supervise or critically observe.

This constitutes one of the common terms and core definitions of the high level structure for ISO management system standards.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.3, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

monitoring process owner

Individual or legal entity responsible for the receipt, integration, generation, analysis, transfer and output of data

A monitoring process or owner of a system within the monitoring process can be represented, e.g. by a sub-contractor.

Related categories: 2.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

morbidity

The relative incidence of a particular disease. In common clinical usage, any disease state, including diagnosis and complications, is referred to as morbidity.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

morbidity rate

The rate of disease or proportion of diseased people in a population.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

mortality

The number of deaths occurring in a given period in a specified population.

Mortality can be expressed as an absolute number of deaths per year or as a rate per 100,000 persons per year.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

mortality ratio

The ratio of deaths in an area to the population of that area, within a particular period of time.

The death rate in a population or locality.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

moving water

Water flowing down a gradient, e.g., streams, rivers, drainage, or channels

Related categories: 3.1

Rescue 3 Europe Ltd. Rescue 3 International - Water and Flood Rescue Manual v6.2020. Available from: <https://www.rescue3europe.com/student-downloads/water-and-flood-rescue-manual/>

mud flow

Type of landslide that occur when heavy rain or rapid snow/ice melt send large amounts of mud downslope by gravitational forces.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

multi-agency coordination centre

A form of large-scale, high-level multiagency and multijurisdictional coordination among affected agencies that is removed from routine event management activities.

This is the highest level of strategic coordination and involves the executive and policy levels of the participating agencies as well as political representatives from affected and participating jurisdictions.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.2, 3.3, 3.6, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

multi-cluster / sector initial rapid assessment (MIRA)

Process designed to identify strategic humanitarian priorities during the first weeks following an emergency.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

multi-hazard

The selection of multiple major hazards that the country faces, and the specific contexts where hazardous events may occur simultaneously, cascadingly or cumulatively over time, and taking into account the potential interrelated effects.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

multi-hazard early warning systems

Systems that address several hazards and/or impacts of similar or different type in contexts where hazardous events may occur alone, simultaneously, cascadingly or cumulatively over time, and taking into account the potential interrelated effects.

A multi-hazard early warning system with the ability to warn of one or more hazards increases the efficiency and consistency of warnings through coordinated and compatible mechanisms and capacities, involving multiple disciplines for updated and accurate hazards identification and monitoring for multiple hazards.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

multi-year training and exercise plan

A multi-year plan providing a mechanism for long-term coordination of training and exercise activities toward a school's preparedness goals. This plan describes the program's training and exercise priorities and associated capabilities, and aids in employing the building-block approach for training and exercise activities.

Related categories: 4.1

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

multiagency coordination group (MAC group)

A group, typically consisting of agency administrators or executives from organizations, or their designees, that provides policy guidance to incident personnel, supports resource prioritization and allocation, and enables decision making among elected and appointed officials and senior executives in other organizations, as well as those directly responsible for incident management.

MAC Groups may also be known as policy groups, multiagency committees, emergency management committees, or as otherwise defined by the Multiagency Coordination System.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.2, 3.3, 3.6, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

multiagency coordination system (MACS)

A system that provides the architecture to support coordination for incident prioritization, critical resource allocation, communications systems integration, and information coordination. Multiagency Coordination Systems assist agencies and organizations responding to an incident. The elements of a MACS include facilities, equipment, personnel, procedures, and communications. Two of the most commonly used elements are Emergency Operations Centers and MAC Groups.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.2, 3.3, 3.6, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

multicast

Multicast is group communication where data transmission is addressed to a group of destination computers simultaneously. Multicast can be one-to-many or many-to-many distribution.

Related categories: 2.2

multijurisdictional incident

An incident requiring action from multiple agencies that each have jurisdiction to manage certain aspects of an incident. In the Incident Command System, these incidents are managed under Unified Command.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.6, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

multiple trauma / polytrauma

Injury to one body cavity such as head, thorax, abdomen, plus two long-bone and/or pelvic fractures. OR, plus injury to two body cavities.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

municipal civil protection service

To support the Civil Protection agents and other support entities in their actions during an emergency

Related categories: 3.6

mutual accountability

Situation where governments, donors and involved stakeholders are all accountable to each other for development results.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

mutual aid agreement

Pre-arranged understanding between two or more entities to render assistance to each other

Related categories: 2.2, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

narrative exposure therapy

Short-term psychological treatment strategy focusing on the management of trauma-spectrum disorders, such as post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) using a narrative approach.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

narrative research

A type of qualitative research methodology that explores people's experiences as told in the form of stories from one or more individuals of interest.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

narrative systematic review

Systematic review in which each included study is discussed, but without a synthesis of their overall results.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

natech

A chemical accident, including spills of oil and oil products, triggered by a natural hazard or natural disaster (such as extreme temperatures, high winds, floods, storms, earthquakes, or wildfires).

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

national disaster inventory (or registry)

National system for understanding disaster risk that would act as the central repository of all publicly available risk information.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.6, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

national disaster management agency (or authority)

The national government agency that is responsible for coordinating disaster or emergency management policy and practice.

There is no common definition for this agency or organization as the name and scope of functions varies across countries and is usually defined by national legislation or policies.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

national disease programme / strategic plan

Strategic plan to guide the control of a particular disease or health problem at national level, with the intended actions to achieve the goals of a given programme. Ideally aligned to the national health strategic plan.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

national emergency number association (NENA)

The National Emergency Number Association is a not-for-profit corporation established in 1982 to further the goal of “One Nation-One Number.”

NENA is a networking source and promotes research, planning and training. NENA strives to educate, set standards and provide certification programs, legislative representation and technical assistance for implementing and managing 9-1-1 systems.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

national IHR focal point

The national centre, designated by each State Party, which shall be accessible at all times for communications with WHO IHR Contact Points under these International Health Regulations (IHR).

Related categories: 2.2, 3.2, 4.2

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

national incident management system (NIMS)

A set of principles that provides a systematic, proactive approach guiding government agencies at all levels, nongovernmental organizations, and the private sector to work seamlessly to prevent, protect against, respond to, recover from, and mitigate the effects of incidents, regardless of cause, size, location, or complexity, in order to reduce the loss of life or property and harm to the environment.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

national platform for disaster risk reduction

A generic term for national mechanisms for coordination and policy guidance on disaster risk reduction that are multisectoral and interdisciplinary in nature, with public, private and civil society participation involving all concerned entities within a country.

Effective government coordination forums are composed of relevant stakeholders at national and local levels and have a designated national focal point. For such mechanisms to have a strong foundation in national institutional frameworks, further key elements and responsibilities should be established through laws, regulations, standards and procedures, including: clearly assigned responsibilities and authority; building awareness and knowledge of disaster risk through the sharing and dissemination of non-sensitive disaster risk information and data; contributing to and coordinating reports on local and national disaster risk; coordinating public awareness campaigns on disaster risk; facilitating and supporting local multisectoral cooperation (e.g. among local governments); and contributing to the determination of and reporting on national and local disaster risk management plans and all policies relevant for disaster risk management.

Related categories: 3.2, 4.2, 4.4

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

national preparedness

The actions taken to plan, organize, equip, train, and exercise to build and sustain the capabilities necessary to prevent, protect against, mitigate the effects of, respond to, and recover from those threats that pose the greatest risk to the security of the Nation.

Related categories: 3.2, 4.2, 4.4

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

natural fire

Any fire started by natural causes, such as lightning, spontaneous combustion or volcanic activity. Thus, lightning fire, spontaneous fire, volcanic fire.

Related categories: 3.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

natural hazard

Hazards that are predominantly associated with natural processes and phenomena.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

natural language processing

Subfield of linguistics, computer science, information engineering and artificial intelligence concerned with the interactions between computers and human languages.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

needs

The sum of the biological, social, psychological and physical elements necessary, at a given time, for the well-being, existence and even survival of the individual or society.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

needs assessment

In simulation exercises: process of defining the reasons for conducting an exercise and identifying the functions to be exercised. Need assessments enable the design of an effective exercise constructed around specific objectives and functions.

Related categories: 4.1, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

needs based response

A response in which the assistance provided is both appropriate to the anticipated epidemiological profile of the disaster and health profile of the affected community as well as being consistent with the actual health care required by that community

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

net benefit

Measure of the benefits minus the costs (including negative consequences) of an action or event.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

network address translation (NAT)

Protocol used to perform a mapping between public and private IP addresses.

Related categories: 2.2

network control protocol (NCP)

Network Control Protocol (NCP) was an early protocol implemented by ARPANET, the world's first operational packet-switching network that later evolved into what became the Internet. NCP allowed users to access and use computers and devices at remote locations and to transmit files between computers.

Related categories: 2.2

network file system (NFS)

Is a distributed file system protocol originally developed by Sun Microsystems (Sun) in 1984, allowing a user on a client computer to access files over a computer network much like local storage is accessed.

Related categories: 2.2

network host

A network host is a computer or other device connected to a computer network. A host may work as a server offering information resources, services, and applications to users or other hosts on the network.

Related categories: 2.2

network of services

Set of provider units that: are functionally coordinated; are hierarchically organized according to level of complexity; have a common geographic point of reference; are commanded by a single operator; share operating standards, information systems and other logistical resources; and share a common purpose.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

network time protocol (NTP)

Protocol used for clock synchronization between computer systems.

Related categories: 2.2

next generation 112 (NG112)

NG112 is defined by two major aspects: 1) Interoperability between emergency services: NG112 enables the several Public Safety Answering Points to be part of a common emergency service IP-network, providing them with redundancy and interoperability features. This network should support data and communications needs for coordinated incident management between PSAPs and provide a reliable and secure environment for emergency communications. 2) Communication between citizens and emergency services: NG112 is designed to enable citizens to reach an authority (e.g., PSAP) by calls using VoIP, text messaging, instant messaging, real-time text, pictures and videos. It could also provide emergency services with more data such as telematics and health data. NG112 enables the delivery of calls, messages and data to the appropriate Public Safety Answering Point (PSAP) and other appropriate emergency entities and makes call handling easier.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

node

In telecommunications networks, a node is either a redistribution point or a communication endpoint.

Related categories: 2.2

noise

Undesired signals are always present in an electrical system. Noise reduces the receiver's ability to recognize symbols correctly, limiting transmission speed.

Related categories: 3.3

nomadic

In the context of location information to support IP based emergency services: A user is said to be nomadic if they are constrained within an access network such that their location can be represented as a definitive civic address for that network attachment. The user may move from one network attachment to another but cannot maintain a session during that move.

If the user is able to move outside the definitive civic address without losing network attachment then the user is considered to be mobile, not nomadic.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

nomadic voip call

Call generated by a VoIP user other than their originally provisioned fixed location using the terminal equipment from that location (i.e.: VoIP handset, laptop, VoIP terminal, PC).

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

nominated emergency contact

Person nominated by an individual staff member who is their chosen first point of contact in the event of the organization needing to make contact

This can be the legal next of kin.

Related categories: 3.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

non-personal data

'Non-Personal data' means any information that is not relating to an identified or identifiable natural person or data subject. In this case, the EU Regulation 2016/679 on General Data Protection Regulation is not applicable.

Related categories: 1.1, 2.2, 2.3, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7

nonconformity

Non-fulfilment of a requirement

This constitutes one of the common terms and core definitions of the high level structure for ISO management system standards.

Related categories: 3.1, 4.3

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

nongovernmental organization (NGO)

An entity with an association that is based on interests of its members, individuals, or institutions. It is not created by a government, but it may work cooperatively with government. Such organizations serve a public purpose, not a private benefit.

Examples of nongovernmental organizations include faith-based charity organizations and the American Red Cross. NGOs, including voluntary and faith-based groups, provide relief services to sustain life, reduce physical and emotional distress, and promote the recovery of disaster victims. Often these groups provide specialized services that help individuals with disabilities. NGOs and voluntary organizations play a major role in assisting emergency managers before, during, and after an emergency.

Related categories: 1.1, 4.2, 4.5

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

nonstructural

Any portion of the building not connected to the main structure including file cabinets and furnishings.

Related categories: 3.1

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

normalization

Process of transforming a relation into one or more simpler relations free of attribute redundancies or inconsistencies in order to support referential integrity.

Related categories: 3.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO/IEC 20944-1:2013(en) Information technology - Metadata Registries Interoperability and Bindings (MDR-IB) - Part 1: Framework, common vocabulary, and common provisions for conformance. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui#iso:std:iso-iec:20944:-1:ed-1:v1:en:term:3.14.4.12> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

notifiable disease

A disease that, by statutory / legal requirements, must be reported to a public health or other competent authority in the pertinent jurisdiction when the diagnosis is made.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

notification

Part of public warning that provides essential information to people at risk regarding the decisions and actions necessary to cope with an emergency situation

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.8, 4.2, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

nuclear emergency

An emergency in which there is, or is perceived to be, a hazard due to the energy resulting from a nuclear chain reaction or from the decay of the products of a chain reaction.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

nutrition

The intake of food, considered in relation to the body's dietary needs.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

OASIS Open

A non-profit standards body which offers projects, including open source projects, a path to standardization and de jure approval for reference in international policy and procurement.

OASIS Open promotes projects in cybersecurity, blockchain, IoT, emergency management, cloud computing, legal data exchange and much more with the mission of promoting fair and transparent development of open source software and standards through the power of collaboration. and the global community.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3

OASIS Open. OASIS Open website. Year of publication: 2022. Available from: <https://www.oasis-open.org/org/> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

object

Single and distinct entity that can be identified

Related categories: 1.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

objective

Result to be achieved

An objective can be strategic, tactical, or operational.

Objectives can relate to different disciplines (such as financial, health and safety, and environmental goals) and can apply at different levels (such as strategic, organization-wide, project, product and process).

An objective can be expressed in other ways, e.g. as an intended outcome, a purpose, an operational criterion, as a business continuity objective, or by the use of other words with similar meaning (e.g. aim, goal, or target).

In the context of business continuity management systems, business continuity objectives are set by the organization, consistent with the business continuity policy, to achieve specific results.

This constitutes one of the common terms and core definitions of the high level structure for ISO management system standards.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

observer

Participant who witnesses the exercise while remaining separate from exercise activities.
Person who observes the exercise.

Observers may submit their observations as part of the evaluation process, although they have no official role in the conduct of the exercise.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3, 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA)

UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs. Is the part of the United Nations Secretariat responsible for bringing together humanitarian actors to ensure a coherent response to emergencies. OCHA also ensures there is a framework within which each actor can contribute to the overall response effort.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

United Nations, Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs. OCHA website. Available from: <https://www.unocha.org/> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

officer

The ICS title for a member of the Command Staff authorized to make decisions and take action related to his/her area of responsibility.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from:

<https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

omnidirectional antenna

Antenna designed to provide a radiation pattern of 360 degrees. They propagate the electromagnetic signal in all directions of the horizontal plane, although they offer a limited range in the vertical plane.

Related categories: 2.2

on-scene

The search area or the actual distress site

Related categories: 3.4

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icsc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

on-scene coordinator (OSC)

A person designated to coordinate search and rescue operations within a specified area

Related categories: 2.3, 3.4, 3.6

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icsc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

on-scene endurance

The amount of time a facility is capable of spending at the scene, engaged in search and rescue activities

Related categories: 3.4

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icsc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

open channel

Unencrypted radio transmissions allow a person with the necessary equipment to receive and listen to their content.

Related categories: 3.3

open coding

An analysis process in Straussian Grounded Theory in which the researcher labels and categorizes information in the data, before attempting to relate categories to each other via axial coding.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

open data

Data that anyone can access, use and share.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

open shortest path first (OSPF)

Routing protocol for Internet Protocol (IP) networks. OSPF gathers link state information from available routers and constructs a topology map of the network. The topology is presented as a routing table to the Internet Layer for routing packets by their destination IP address. OSPF supports Internet Protocol Version 4 (IPv4) and Internet Protocol Version 6 (IPv6) networks.

Related categories: 2.2

open-sourcing

The development of data or materials that will become freely available, where there is often no clear 'call' to work (for example, open sourced software programmes).

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

operational information

Information that has been contextualized and analysed to provide an understanding of the situation and its possible evolution

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.1, 3.6, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

operational oversight

The responsibility for direct supervision of the Head of the WHO Office in countries, territories and areas for emergency operations. This responsibility includes day-to-day monitoring of the effectiveness of the organizational response to the emergency and delegated authority to make technical, operational and management decisions regarding the response. Operational oversight is usually the responsibility of the Regional Emergency Director. Depending on the context, the Executive Director and the Regional Director may assign this responsibility to the Director of Emergency Operations at headquarters.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.6, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2017. ISBN: 9789241512299. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241512299>

operational plan

Operational plans focus on effective management of resources with a short time framework, converting objectives into targets and activities, and arrangements for monitoring implementation and resource usage.

Specific meanings include: 1. translation of the national strategic plan within a one-year time frame. 2. translation of the national strategic plan into a sub-national plan, e.g. a district plan, usually with a shorter time frame than the national strategic plan. 3. a subset of a national strategic plan, limited to a particular programme.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

operational priorities

The desired end-state for the operations.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

operational response

The emergency actions that exceed the usual country-level cooperation that the WHO Office in countries, territories and areas has with the Member State.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2017. ISBN: 9789241512299. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241512299>

operations section

The Incident Command System (ICS) Section responsible for all tactical incident operations and implementation of the Incident Action Plan.

In ICS, the Operations Section may include subordinate branches, divisions, and/or groups.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

operations-based exercises

Operations-based exercises are characterized by actual response, mobilization of apparatus and resources, and commitment of personnel, usually held over an extended period of time. Operations-based exercises can be used to validate plans, policies, agreements, and procedures and include drills, functional exercises, and full-scale exercises. They can clarify roles and responsibilities, identify gaps in resources needed to implement plans and procedures, and improve individual and team performance.

Related categories: 4.1

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

opportunity cost

The value of the next best alternative forgone as a result of the decision made.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

ordinal data

Categorical data where the variables have natural, ordered categories.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

organization

Person or group of people that has its own functions with responsibilities, authorities and relationships to achieve its objectives

The concept of organization includes, but is not limited to, sole-trader, company, corporation, firm, enterprise, authority, partnership, charity or institution, or part or combination thereof, whether incorporated or not, public or private.

This constitutes one of the common terms and core definitions of the high level structure for ISO management system standards.

Related categories: 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

organization and assignment of responsibilities

A component of the basic plan that lists tasks staff will perform in the event of incident by position and organization.

Related categories: 3.2

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

organization in the supply chain

Entity that:

- manufactures, handles, processes, loads, consolidates, unloads or receives goods upon placement of a purchase order that at some point crosses an international or economy border;
- transports goods by any mode in the international supply chain regardless of whether their particular segment of the supply chain crosses national (or economy) boundaries; or
- provides, manages or conducts the generation, distribution or flow of shipping information used by customs agencies or in business practices.

Related categories: 3.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

organizational culture

Collective beliefs, values, attitudes and behaviour of an organization that contribute to the unique social and psychological environment in which it operates

Related categories: 5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

organizational resilience

Ability of an organization to absorb and adapt in a changing environment

Related categories: 4.2, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

organized rescue

An organized rescue is one carried out by trained professionals or volunteers such search & rescue organization, ski patrol or guiding company using a prepared rescue plan. It can involve numerous personnel and extensive resources such as helicopters and avalanche rescue dogs and can last several days

Related categories: 3.4

Avalanche Canada . Avalanche Canada website. Available from: <https://www.avalanche.ca/glossary> (Date of consultation: 26/01/2022)

originating carrier

An entity that provides telecommunications services to the end user.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

outbreak

Often used synonymously with “epidemic”, usually to indicate localised as opposed to generalised epidemics.

Typically defined as two or more people with the same health condition, at the same time and in the same place.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

outcome

Those aspects of health that result from the interventions provided by the health system, the facilities and personnel that recommend them and the actions of those who are the targets of the interventions.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

outpatient emergency care FMT

Type 1 WHO foreign medical team classification. Outpatient initial emergency care of injuries and other significant health care needs. Services include: triage, assessment, first aid, stabilisation + referral of severe trauma and non trauma emergencies, definite care for minor trauma and non trauma emergencies

Capacity: 100 outpatients/day for 2 weeks. If facility provided: rapidly deployable temporary shelter care for outpatient capacity of that FMT, or mobile. Day time services.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

output

The quantity and quality of activities carried out by a programme.

In simulation exercises: actual findings, recommendations and results stemming from the exercise. These should correspond with the exercise objectives and are presented in the exercise report.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

outsource

Make an arrangement where an external organization performs part of an organization's function or process

An external organization is outside the scope of the management system, although the outsourced function or process is within the scope.

This constitutes one of the common terms and core definitions of the high level structure for ISO management system standards.

Related categories: 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

out-of-pocket payments (OOP)

Payments for goods or services that include: 1. direct payments: payments for goods or services that are not covered by any form of insurance. 2. cost sharing: a provision of health insurance or third-party payment that requires the individual who is covered to pay part of the cost of health care received. 3. informal payments: unofficial payments for goods and services that should be fully funded from pooled revenue.

Related categories: 3.5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

overflow

The routing condition that occurs when all trunks from the originating network element (e.g. LEC end office, ESGW, PBX) to the SR are busy with calls and additional calls need to be routed to the PSAP. Call volume exceeds available end office to SR trunk capacity. The term "overflow" refers to the treatment a call receives and may include routing to announcements and/or all-trunks-busy tones, or b) all dedicated end office to SR trunks, primary and secondary routes, are out of service (i.e. trunk failure condition).

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

overhead (indirect) costs

Costs that are not directly accountable to a cost object (in research these may be costs for the institution, for example).

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

owner

Entity that legally controls the licensing and user rights and distribution of the object associated with the unique identifier (UID)

Related categories: 1.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

packet

Logical grouping of information that includes a header containing control information and (usually) user data. Network packet or data packet is each of the blocks into which the information to be sent is divided at the network level.

Packets are most often used to refer to network layer units of data. The terms datagram, frame, message, and segment are also used to describe logical information groupings at various layers of the OSI reference model and in various technology circles

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

packet loss

Packet loss occurs when one or more packets of data travelling across a computer network fail to reach their destination. Packet loss is either caused by errors in data transmission, typically across wireless networks, or network congestion. Packet loss is measured as a percentage of packets lost with respect to packets sent.

Related categories: 2.2

packet-switched data networks

In telecommunications, packet-switching is now- dominant communications paradigm, in which packets (units of information carriage) are individually routed between nodes over data links which might be shared by many other nodes. In packet switched networks, such as the Internet, the data is split up into packets, each labelled with the complete destination address and routed individually.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

PAN-PAN

The international radiotelephony urgency signal

Related categories: 2.2

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icssc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

pandemic

1. Worldwide spread of a new disease.

2. A worldwide outbreak of a disease in humans in numbers clearly in excess of normal.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

parameter

Specific value describing the measurable or theoretical features of the elements of a system

Related categories: 2.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

Paris declaration on aid effectiveness

An international agreement to which over one hundred ministers, heads of agencies and other senior officials adhered and committed their countries and organizations to continue to increase efforts in ownership, harmonization, alignment, mutual accountability and managing aid for development results with a set of monitorable actions and indicators, endorsed on March 2, 2005 at the Second High Level Forum on Aid Effectiveness.

Related categories: 1.1

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

participant

Person or organization who performs a function related to an exercise

Related categories: 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

participant narrative

Data generated by talking directly to participants through interviews and focus groups.

Related categories: 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

participant observer

A method of data collection in which the researcher becomes immersed in the day-to-day lives of the group they are researching, both observing and participating in the world around them.

Related categories: 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

partnering

Associating with others in an activity or area of common interest in order to achieve individual and collective objectives

Related categories: 1.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

partnership

Organized relationship between two bodies (public–public, private–public, private–private) that establishes the scope, roles, procedures and tools to prevent and manage any incident impacting on security and resilience with respect to related laws

Related categories: 3.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

pathogens

Disease-causing organisms (e.g. bacteria, helminths, protozoa or viruses)

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

patient

A sick person who needs, is receiving or will receive medical care, treatment or surgical attention.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

peer review

Process used by a reviewer to examine the performance of a host, provide feedback on an analysis area and learn lessons that are transferable to its own context

A peer review can cover multiple analysis areas.

The host can replace “review” with a synonym such as “assessment”, “appraisal” or “analysis” to better describe the activity.

Related categories: 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

peer-to-peer (P2P)

Computing or networking is a distributed application architecture that partitions tasks or workloads between peers. Peers are equally privileged, equipotent participants in the application. They are said to form a peer-to-peer network of nodes.

Related categories: 2.2

people aspects of business continuity

Elements associated with the management of people involved in, or affected by, an incident in order to minimize distress, maximize productivity and recovery, and achieve the recovery objectives of the organization’s business continuity programme

Related categories: 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

people at risk

Individuals in the area who could be affected by an incident

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.2, 3.7, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

performance

Measurable result

Performance can relate either to quantitative or qualitative findings.

Performance can relate to managing activities , processes, products (including services), systems or organizations.

This constitutes one of the common terms and core definitions of the high level structure for ISO management system standards.

Related categories: 5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

performance evaluation

Process to determine measurable results against the set criteria

Related categories: 5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

performance monitoring

The continuous process of collecting and analysing data to compare how well a project, program, or policy is being implemented against expected results.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.6, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

personal area network (PAN)

It is a network standard for communication between different devices near the access point. These networks are of a few meters and for personal use.

Related categories: 2.2

personal data

Personal data means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person or data subject. An identifiable person is someone who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular with reference to an identification number or to one or more factors specific to their physical, physiological, mental, economic, cultural or social identity.

Related categories: 1.1

personal health services

Health services targeted at the individual. These include, among others, health promotion, timely disease prevention, diagnosis and treatment, rehabilitation, palliative care, acute care and long-term care services.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

personal locator beacon (PLB)

A portable device, manually activated, which transmits a distress signal on 406 MHz, and may have an additional homing signal on a separate frequency

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.7

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icscc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

personal protective equipment (PPE)

1. Protective clothing (gowns, gloves, boots etc.) and equipment (masks, shields, respirators, earplugs etc.) necessary to shield or isolate a person from biological, chemical, physical, sonic and thermal exposure.

2. Specialized clothing and equipment designed to create a barrier against health and safety hazards.

Examples include safety goggles, blast shields, hard hats, hearing protectors, gloves, respirators, aprons, and work boots.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

personnel

People working for and under the control of an organization

The concept of personnel includes, but is not limited to, employees, part-time staff and agency staff.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

phases of disaster

A disaster can be phased in chronological order, e.g. pre-event status, preparedness, warning, threat, impact, rescue, reconstruction, rehabilitation.

Related categories: 3.2

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

phishing

A technique for attempting to acquire sensitive data, such as bank account numbers, through a fraudulent solicitation in email or on a web site, in which the perpetrator masquerades as a legitimate business or reputable person.

Related categories: 3.3

pilot study

Small, preliminary study usually done before a definitive study.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

pitch

The distance between two belays that a climber has to travel.

Related categories: 3.4

Jawahar Institute of Mountaineering & Winter Sport. JIM&WS website. Available from: <https://www.jawaharinstitutepahalgam.com/mtn%20terminology1.php>

place of safety

A location where rescue operations are considered to terminate; where the survivors' safety of life is no longer threatened and where their basic human needs (such as food, shelter and medical needs) can be met; and, a place from which transportation arrangements can be made for the survivors' next or final destination. A place of safety may be on land, or it may be on board a rescue unit or other suitable vessel or facility at sea that can serve as a place of safety until the survivors are disembarked at their next destination

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icssc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

plain language

Communication that the intended audience can understand and that meets the communicator's purpose. For the purpose of NIMS, plain language refers to a communication style that avoids or limits the use of codes, abbreviations, and jargon, as appropriate, during incidents involving more than a single agency.

Related categories: 2.2

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

plan development

The process of generating and comparing possible solutions for achieving goals and objectives, determining response and recovery capabilities, and identifying resource gaps.

Related categories: 3.2

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

planned event

An incident that is a scheduled non-emergency activity (e.g., sporting event, concert, parade).

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

planning

Part of management focused on setting objectives and specifying necessary operational processes and related resources to fulfil the objectives

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

planning section

The Incident Command System Section responsible for the collection, evaluation, and dissemination of operational information related to the incident, and for the preparation and documentation of the Incident Action Plan. This Section also maintains information on the current and forecasted situation and on the status of resources assigned to the incident.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

planning section chief

A member of the General Staff who supports the incident action planning process by tracking resources, collecting/analyzing information, and maintaining documentation.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

plans

Generic reference to documents designed to identify, at various levels, responsibility for a range of activities and intended objectives, strategies and tactics.

Related categories: 3.2

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

point of entry

A passage for international entry or exit of travellers, baggage, cargo, containers, conveyances, goods and postal parcels as well as agencies and areas providing services to them on entry or exit.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

point prevalence

Existing case at a particular point in time.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

point-to-point protocol (PPP)

A data link layer (layer 2) communication protocol between two routers directly without any host or any other networking in between. It can provide connection authentication, transmission encryption, and data compression.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

policy

Intentions and direction of an organization, as formally expressed by its top management

This constitutes one of the common terms and core definitions of the high level structure for ISO management system standards.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

pollution

Degradation of one or more elements or aspects in the environment by noxious industrial, chemical or biological wastes, from debris of man-made products and from mismanagement of natural and environmental resources

Related categories: 3.1

United Nations, Department of Humanitarian Affairs. Internationally agreed glossary of basic terms related to Disaster Management. Year of publication: 1992. Available from: <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/004DFD3E15B69A67C1256C4C006225C2-dha-glossary-1992.pdf>

polytomous

Data that can take one of more than two values.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

population

Group of people being studied.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

portability (right to)

The right to data portability allows individuals to obtain and reuse their personal data for their own purposes across different services

Related categories: 1.1

position qualifications

The minimum criteria necessary for individuals to fill a specific position.

Related categories: 1.1

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

post-traumatic stress disorder / syndrome

Delayed or protracted reaction to an exceptionally strong stressful event of catastrophic dimension which can cause pervasive distress in almost any person, but more marked in some, following a natural or man-made disaster, combat, violent death, torture, rape, terrorism, etc. The onset may follow the trauma within a few weeks or at most six months. Typical symptoms include “reliving” or “flashbacks” of the event, “numbness” and detachment and fearful reminiscences.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

pragmatic trial

Study to determine the effects of an intervention when used in routine practice.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

precaution adoption process model (PAPM)

Model to explain how a person makes decisions to take action and how they translate that decision into action.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

prehospital medicine

The system and provision of basic emergency treatment to persons who have suffered a sudden illness or injury outside the availability of a hospital or organized medical services and rendered by competent persons with the intention of preventing disability or death and ensuring safe transfer to a hospital or other appropriate facility.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

preparedness

1. Activities , programmes, and systems developed and implemented prior to an incident that can be used to support and enhance prevention, protection from, mitigation of, response to and recovery from disruptions, emergencies or disasters. 2. A state of readiness and capability of human and material means, structures, communities and organisations enabling them to ensure an effective rapid response to a disaster, obtained as a result of action taken in advance.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.1, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 1313/2013/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32013D1313&from=EN>

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

preparedness plan

A plan that establishes arrangements in advance to enable timely, effective and appropriate responses to specific potential hazardous events or emerging disaster situations that might threaten society or the environment.

Related categories: 3.2, 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

prestandard

Document that is adopted provisionally by a standardizing body and made available to the public in order that the necessary experience may be gained from its application on which to base a standard.

Related categories: 3.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO/IEC 20944-1:2013(en) Information technology - Metadata Registries Interoperability and Bindings (MDR-IB) - Part 1: Framework, common vocabulary, and common provisions for conformance. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui#iso:std:iso-iec:20944:-1:ed-1:v1:en:term:3.14.4.12> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

prevalence

The number of cases in a defined population at a specific point in time.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

prevention

Measures that enable an organization to avoid, preclude or limit the impact of an undesirable event or potential disruption

Related categories: 2.2, 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.8, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 1313/2013/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32013D1313&from=EN>

prevention of hazards and threats

Process, practices, techniques, materials, products, services or resources used to avoid, reduce, or control hazards and threats and their associated risks of any type in order to reduce their potential likelihood or consequences

Related categories: 2.2, 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

preventive action

Action to eliminate the cause of a potential nonconformity or other undesirable potential situation

There can be more than one cause for a potential nonconformity.

Preventive action is taken to prevent occurrence whereas corrective action is taken to prevent recurrence

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

primary data

Data collected by a researcher from first-hand sources (for example through surveys, interviews or experiments).

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

primary health care

Often used interchangeably with first level of care. 1. The part of a health services system that assures person focused care over time to a defined population, accessibility to facilitate receipt of care when it is first needed, comprehensiveness of care in the sense that only rare or unusual manifestations of ill health are referred elsewhere, and coordination of care such that all facets of care (wherever received) are integrated. Quality features of primary care include effectiveness, safety, people-centredness, comprehensiveness, continuity and integration. 2. The provision of integrated, accessible health care services by clinicians who are accountable for addressing a large majority of personal health care needs, developing a sustained partnership with patients, and practicing in the context of family and community.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

primary prevention

Strategies to prevent a disease from occurring.

Related categories: 3.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

primary public safety answering point

Physical location working on behalf of the national authorities where emergency calls are first received under the responsibility of a public authority or a private organisation recognised by the national.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

principal components analysis (PCA)

Transforming the high-dimensional data into a lower- dimensional form, without losing too much information.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

prioritized activity

Activity to which urgency is given in order to avoid unacceptable impacts to the business during a disruption

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.2, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

priority setting

The identification, balancing and ranking of priorities by stakeholders.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

PRISMA

Reporting guideline for systematic reviews and meta- analyses.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

private sector

Organizations and individuals that are not part of any governmental structure. The private sector includes for-profit and not-for-profit organizations, formal and informal structures, commerce, and industry.

Related categories: 5

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

private security company (PSC)

Private security service provider (PSPP)

Related categories: 2.2, 3.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

private security service provider (PSP)

Private security company (PSC), organization that conducts or contracts security operations and whose business activities include the provision of security services either on its own behalf or on behalf of another

PSSPs provide services to clients with the aim of ensuring their security and that of others.

PSSPs typically work in circumstances where governance is weak or rule of law undermined due to human- or naturally caused events) and provide services for which personnel can be required to carry weapons in the performance of their duties in accordance with the terms of their contract.

Examples of security services provided by PSSPs include: guarding; close protection; physical protection measures; security awareness and training; risk, security and threat assessment; the provision of protective and defensive measures for individuals' compounds, diplomatic and residential perimeters; escort of transport; and policy analysis.

A joint venture is considered part of the organization.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.2, 3.3

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

probability

Measure of the chance of occurrence expressed as a number between 0 and 1, where 0 is impossibility and 1 is absolute certainty

See also likelihood.

Related categories: 2.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

procedure

Specified way to carry out an activity or a process

Procedures can be documented or not.

When a procedure is documented, the term "written procedure" or "documented procedure" is frequently used. The document that contains a procedure can be called a "procedure document".

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

process

Set of interrelated or interacting activities that transforms inputs into outputs

This constitutes one of the common terms and core definitions of the high level structure for ISO management system standards.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

process-based logic model

Hypothesized description that focuses on theorizing aspects of complexity between the processes occurring as part of an intervention and its multiple outcomes.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

processing (of data)

‘Processing’ means any operation or set of operations which is performed on data or on sets of data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction.

If data are personal ones, the EU Regulation 2016/679 General Data Protection Regulation finds application.

Related categories: 1.1

product and service

Output or outcome provided by an organization to interested parties

EXAMPLE: Manufactured items, car insurance, community nursing.

Related categories: 3.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

product fraud

Wrongful or criminal deception that utilizes material goods for financial or personal gain

Fraud means wrongful or criminal deception intended to result in financial or personal gain that creates social or economic harm.

Products include electronic media carried on material goods.

Fraud related to digitally transmitted electronic media shall be considered separately.

Related categories: 3.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

programme theory

Hypothesis explaining how an intervention is expected to lead to a change in the outcome.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

project aid

Aid flows earmarked to specific activities or a discrete set of activities for which coherent objectives and outputs and the inputs required to achieve them are defined.

Related categories: 2.4, 3.2, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

prospective study

Study that follows participants over time into future.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

protection

Measures that safeguard and enable an organization to reduce the impact of a potential disruption

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

protocol

1. A set of rules or conventions that govern the format and relative timing of data in a communications network. There are three basic types of protocols: character-oriented, byte-oriented, and bit-oriented. The protocols for data communications cover such things as framing, error handling, transparency, and line control. 2. A set of established guidelines for actions (designated by individuals, teams, functions, or capabilities) under various specified conditions.

Related categories: 2.3, 2.4, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

protocol stack

The protocol stack is an ordered collection of protocols organized in layers that are placed on top of each other and where each protocol implements an abstraction framed by the abstraction provided by the layer on which it is framed.

Related categories: 2.2

protracted emergency

An environment in which a significant proportion of the population is acutely vulnerable to death, disease and disruption of livelihoods over a prolonged period of time.

Governance in these settings is often weak, with limited State capacity to respond to, and mitigate, the threats to the population, or provide adequate levels of protection.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2017. ISBN: 9789241512299. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241512299>

proxy

An entity in a call path that is an intermediary, and not an endpoint. Most message contents are copies (proxied) from one side of the proxy to the other, but the proxy may modify some elements, make a routing decision, or reject the call.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

proxy consent

Process by which people give consent on behalf of someone else.

Related categories: 1.1

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

proxy or proxy server/policy and routing server

A policy and routing server in the context of SIP is a proxy server, an intermediary entity that acts as both a server and a client for the purpose of making requests on behalf of other clients. A proxy server primarily plays the role of routing, which means its job is to ensure that a request is sent to another entity “closer” to the targeted user. Proxies are also useful for enforcing policy (for example, making sure a user is allowed to make a call). A proxy interprets, and, if necessary, rewrites

specific parts of a request message before forwarding it.” (Refer to IETF RFC 3261[5].) It can be a policy/routing element in other protocols.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

proxy server

An intermediary server between a client and another server. It provides caching service, administrative control, and security. For example, a proxy server can be used to prevent access to certain web sites.

Related categories: 3.3

psychological critical incident

Event) or series of events that could cause significant emotional or physical distress, psychological impairment or disturbance in people’s usual functioning

Mental health professionals working in this field would normally refer to a “traumatic event” as a critical psychological incident. The term “critical psychological incident” is preferred as it implies an incident that may or may not be traumatic to the individual involved. Although there are several definitions of a traumatic event within the psychiatric and scientific world, “psychological critical incident” provides a more real-world definition.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.3

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

psychological education

Provision of advice and guidance relating to psychological well-being

It usually includes an overview of common reactions to distressing events) in order to normalize them, reduce anxiety, provide simple self-help strategies to facilitate recovery in the first few days, and provide advice on where and when to seek further support.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.3

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

psychological first aid

Temporary, supportive intervention comparable to the concept of physical first aid

Its goals include stabilizing the crisis situation, reducing emotional distress, providing advice on self-care and psychological education, identifying people who could need professional assistance and referring for further assistance, as necessary.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.3

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

public agency

A state or any unit of local government or special purpose district located in whole or in part within a country, which provides police, fire-fighting, medical or other emergency services or has authority to do so.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.6, 3.7, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

public awareness

The process of informing the community as to the nature of the hazard and actions needed to save lives and property prior to and in the event of disaster

The extent of common knowledge about disaster risks, the factors that lead to disasters and the actions that can be taken individually and collectively to reduce exposure and vulnerability to hazard. Community engagement is critical in order to raise public awareness, work for social mobilization, health promotion and risk communication.

Related categories: 4.4

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699%09> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

United Nations, Department of Humanitarian Affairs. Internationally agreed glossary of basic terms related to Disaster Management. Year of publication: 1992. Available from: <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/004DFD3E15B69A67C1256C4C006225C2-dha-glossary-1992.pdf>

public certificate

A public key certificate is a type of digital document signed by an entity called a Certification Authority that associates a public key with data representing the identity of an entity that holds the private key associated with that public key.

Related categories: 2.2

public communication

The discipline and process of providing public audiences with information that creates awareness and knowledge so that people can adjust their personal understanding of risks, and their reactions, decisions and responses to threats and crisis situations.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

public health

An organized effort by society, primarily through its public institutions, to improve, promote, protect and restore the health of the population through collective action.

It includes services such as health situation analysis, health surveillance, health promotion, prevention, infectious disease control, environmental protection and sanitation, disaster and health emergency preparedness and response, and occupational health, among others.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

public health emergency operations centre

An emergency operations centre specializing in the command, control and coordination requirements of responding to emergencies involving health consequences and threats to public health.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.6, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

public health event

1. Any event that may have negative consequences for human health. 2. A manifestation of disease or an occurrence that creates a potential for disease.

The term includes events that have not yet lead to disease and / or injury in humans but have the potential to cause disease and injury through exposure of humans to hazards or as a result of direct or indirect consequences of other hazardous events.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2017. ISBN: 9789241512299. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241512299>

public health measure

A procedure applied to prevent the spread of disease or contamination.

Often refers to non-medical or non-pharmaceutical actions to reduce the spread of disease. Examples include closing schools, limiting public gatherings, issuing travel restrictions and screening travellers.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

public health risk

A likelihood of an event that may affect adversely the health of human populations.

In the context of the International Health Regulations, there is an emphasis on an event which may spread internationally or may present a serious and direct danger.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

public health services

Health services targeted at the population as a whole. These include, among others, health situation analysis, health surveillance, health promotion, prevention services, infectious disease control, environmental protection and sanitation, disaster preparedness and response, and occupational health.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

public health surveillance

The ongoing systematic collection, analysis, and interpretation of data relating to public health.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

public information

Processes, procedures, and systems for communicating timely, accurate, and accessible information on an incident's cause, size, and current situation; resources committed; and other matters of general interest to the public, responders, and additional stakeholders (both directly affected and indirectly affected).

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3, 3.6, 3.8, 4.2

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

public information officer (PIO)

A member of the Command Staff who serves as the conduit for information to internal and external stakeholders, including the media or other organizations seeking information directly from the incident or event.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

public key infrastructure (PKI)

A system of digital certificates, CAs, and other registration authorities that verify and authenticate the validity of each party involved in an Internet transaction.

Related categories: 3.3

public safety agency

An entity that provides fire fighting, law enforcement, emergency medical or other emergency service.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

public safety answering point (PSAP)

Public Safety Answering Point (PSAP): A set of call takers authorized by a governing body and operating under common management which receives 112 calls and asynchronous event notifications for a defined geographic area and processes those calls and events according to a specified operational policy.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3, 3.8

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

public safety answering point (PSAP) operators

Operates the Public Safety Answering Points in a particular country, region, or other regional jurisdiction.

Related categories: 3.3

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

public switched telephone network (PSTN)

The network of equipment, lines, and controls assembled to establish communication paths between calling and called parties.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

public warning

Notification and alert messages disseminated as an incident response measure to enable responders and people at risk to take safety measures

Public warning can include information to raise public awareness and understanding or to provide advisory or compulsory instructions.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

public warning system

Set of protocols, processes and technologies based on the public warning policy to deliver notification and alert messages in a developing emergency situation to people at risk and to first responders

Related categories: 2.2, 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

pyroclastic flow

Extremely hot gases, ash, and other materials of more than 1,000 degrees Celsius that rapidly flow down the flank of a volcano (more than 700 km/h) during an eruption.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNi/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

qualified health worker

A formally trained clinical provider, such as a physician, nurse, clinical officer or medical assistant who has been recognized as such by a competent professional body.

Related categories: 5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

qualitative research

Scientific method of observation to gather non-numerical data (for example, to assess perceptions and beliefs).

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

quality assurance programme

System that facilitates review and evaluation of work product.

Related to training, information is used to validate effectiveness of training and evaluate need for additional training or other corrective action.

Related categories: 5

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

quality of service (QoS)

Description or measurement of the overall performance of a service, such as a telephone, a computer network or a cloud computing service, particularly the performance seen by the users of the network. To quantitatively measure quality of service, several related aspects of the network service are often considered, such as packet loss, bit rate, throughput, transmission delay, availability or jitter.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

quality-adjusted life expectancy (QALE)

A model of judgement in which a disability or disease is considered as a factor of reduced quality of life in calculating life expectancy.

Related categories: 5

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

quality-adjusted life-year (QALY)

Measure of additional life expectancy combined with the health-related quality of life.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

quantitative research

Scientific method of observation to gather numerical data.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

quarantine

The restriction of activities and / or separation from others of suspect persons who are not ill; or of suspect baggage, containers, conveyances or goods in such a manner as to prevent the possible spread of infection or contamination.

Related categories: 3.3

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

queue

A stored arrangement of calls or data waiting to be processed

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.3, 3.6

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

queuing

Queuing is an automated process by which call are presented in a predefined sequence to a call taker.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

radiation emergency

The term 'radiation emergency' is used in some cases when an explicit distinction between nuclear and radiological emergencies is not required (e.g. national radiation emergency plan).

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

radiation exposure risk

A dose of 100 mSv (millisieverts) results in risk of cancer; 20 mSv is the maximum annual dose allowable for nuclear workers; 10 mSv is the dose received at a whole body scan; 1 mSv is the annual tolerated dose for a person; 0.1 mSv is the dose received at thoracic X-ray examination.

Related categories: 3.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

radiation injury

Somatic and genetic damage to living organisms caused by ionizing radiation.

Related categories: 3.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

radiation sickness

Severe nausea, vomiting, lethargy are some of the earliest symptoms of acute radiation exposure, as seen after the Hiroshima nuclear bombing.

Related categories: 3.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

radiation toxicity

Toxicity and harmful effects due to radioactivity from a radionuclide present in the body.

Related categories: 3.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

radio disturbance

Triggered by x-ray emissions from the Sun hitting the Earth's atmosphere and causing disturbances in the ionosphere such as jamming of high and/or low frequency radio signals. This affects satellite radio communication and Global Positioning Systems (GPS).

Related categories: 2.2

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgLS5evtT8jBNi/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

radio electromagnetic spectrum

Energy distribution of electromagnetic waves as a whole.

Related categories: 3.3

radio frequency identification (RFID)

Storage and recovery data system that uses devices known as tags or RFID cards. The fundamental purpose of RFID technology is to transmit the identify of an object (similar to a unique serial number) using radio waves.

Related categories: 3.3

radiological emergency

An emergency in which there is, or is perceived to be, a hazard due to radiation exposure not involving a nuclear chain reaction.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

rain

Water vapour condenses in the atmosphere to form water droplets that fall to the Earth.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNi/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

randomized trial

Study in which patients are allocated randomly to one of the groups being compared.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

range

Distance between the highest and the lowest values in a distribution.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

ransomware

Ransomware is a type of malicious software (malware) that threatens to publish or blocks access to data or a computer system, usually by encrypting it, until the victim pays a ransom fee to the attacker.

Related categories: 3.3

rapelling

Descending down a rock face or ice wall with the help of rope is called rappelling. Rappelling is also known as abseiling.

Related categories: 3.4

Jawahar Institute of Mountaineering & Winter Sport. JIM&WS website. Available from: <https://www.jawaharinstitutepahalgam.com/mtn%20terminology1.php>

rapid deployment emergency hospital ERU

An IFRC Emergency Response Unit (ERU). First level mobile hospital or field hospital, its services include an OT, intensive observation, anaesthesia, x-ray, laboratory, maternal-child health, pharmacy, sterilization, outpatient clinics. Provides safe medical and surgical interventions, while offering limited medical/surgical care.

Capacity: 20–70 inpatient beds, essential medical and surgical care 300 people/day, 50–100 OPD/day.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

rapid needs assessment

Process conducted immediately after the onset of a disaster to assess the disaster-affected areas and needs of disaster victims.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

rapid response team

A group of trained individuals that is ready to responds quickly to an event. The composition and terms of reference are determined by the country concerned.

Multidisciplinary teams of experts that can be deployed on short notice by a health authority to locations of public health events to augment surveillance, risk assessment and response activities already being implemented, to control disease outbreaks and strengthen international public health security.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

raster

Grid of cells and pixels which can be stored as images.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

ratio data

Form of continuous data, which have the same properties as interval data and an absolute zero point.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

raw material

Any element, constituent or part of a material good

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.3, 3.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

readiness

Activities , programmes, and systems developed and implemented prior to an incident that can be used to support and enhance prevention, protection from, mitigation of, response to and recovery from disruptions, emergencies or disasters

Related categories: 2.2, 3.2, 3.3, 3.8, 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

real time protocol (RTP)

An IP protocol used to transport media (voice, video, text) which has a real time constraint.

Related categories: 2.2

NENA (USA National Emergency Number Association). NENA Glossary of 9-1-1 Terminology. Year of publication: 2021. Available from: https://nenawiki.org/wiki/NENA_Glossary_of_9-1-1_Terminology (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

real-time

The availability of information at the exact time it is occurring.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

real-time transport control protocol (RTCP)

RTCP is a sister protocol of RTP and provides out-of-band control information for an RTP flow. It partners RTP in the delivery and packaging of multimedia data, but does not transport any data itself. It is used periodically to transmit control packets to participants in a streaming multimedia session. The primary function of RTCP is to provide feedback on the quality of service being provided by RTP.

It gathers statistics on a media connection and information such as bytes sent, packets sent, lost packets, jitter, feedback and round trip delay. An application may use this information to increase the quality of service perhaps by limiting flow, or maybe using a low compression codec instead of a high compression codec. RTCP is used for Quality of Service (QoS) reporting.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

real-time transport protocol

A network protocol used to carry packetized audio and video traffic over an IP network that helps ensure that packets get delivered in a timely way.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

real-time-kinematic (RTK)

Positioning support system through ground stations.

Related categories: 3.3

realist evaluation

A theory-driven evaluation method which emphasizes the interaction of the context and mechanism to produce an outcome.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

reCAPTCHA

It is a CAPTCHA system that enables web hosts to distinguish between human and automated access to websites.

Related categories: 3.3

receipt

Date and time stamp when document either entered into an electronic tracking system by the jurisdiction or service provider.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

receiver

Entity that receives the message and interprets it. If the message is correctly processed by the receiver, the communication is successful.

Related categories: 3.3

reconstruction

The medium and long-term rebuilding and sustainable restoration of resilient critical infrastructures, services, housing, facilities, and livelihoods required for the full functioning of a community or a society affected by a disaster, aligning with the principles of sustainable development and building and 'build back better', to avoid or reduce future disaster risk.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

record

Document stating results achieved or providing evidence of activities performed

Related categories: 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

record review

Technique used to obtain retrospective data from a series of records.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

recovery

Restoration and improvement, where appropriate, of operations, facilities, livelihoods or living conditions of affected organizations, including efforts to reduce risk factors

Related categories: 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

recovery plan

A plan developed to restore an affected area or community.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

recovery point objective (RPO)

Point to which information used by an activity is restored to enable the activity to operate on resumption

Can also be referred to as “maximum data loss”.

Related categories: 2.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

recovery time objective (RTO)

Period of time following an incident within which a product and service or an activity is resumed, or resources are recovered

For products, services and activities, the RTO is less than the time it would take for the adverse impacts that would arise as a result of not providing a product/service or performing an activity to become unacceptable.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.4, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

recurrent expenditures - costs

Costs that refer to inputs which last less than one year and are regularly purchased for continuing an activity, such as salaries, drugs and supplies, repair maintenance, and others.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

redundancy

Duplication of components, running in parallel, to increase reliability; A backup system (either a device or a connection) that serves in the event of primary system failure.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

referral hospital ERU

An IFRC Emergency Response Unit (ERU). Referral level multidisciplinary care; covers the fields of surgery, limited Traumatology, anaesthesia, internal medicine, gynaecology, obstetrics and paediatrics.

Capacity: Surgical and Medical care for 250.000 people, 120–150 inpatient beds

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

reflection

Reflection occurs when an electromagnetic wave propagates through the airstrikes of an object of large dimensions compared to the wavelength of the signal. The result may be that the signal is absorbed, reflected, or a combination of both.

Related categories: 3.3

refraction

The change in direction and slowness of a wave passes from one medium to another with a different refractive index.

Related categories: 3.3

refugee

A person who cannot return to his / her country of origin owing to a well-founded fear of persecution or serious and indiscriminate threats to life, physical integrity or freedom.

Related categories: 4.4

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

registry

A single place for keeping valid data values associated with a specific data element.

Related categories: 2.2

NENA (USA National Emergency Number Association). NENA Glossary of 9-1-1 Terminology. Year of publication: 2021. Available from: https://nenawiki.org/wiki/NENA_Glossary_of_9-1-1_Terminology (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

rehabilitation

1. The restoration of basic services and facilities for the functioning of a community or a society affected by a disaster.

2. The restoration of normal functioning of people and communities.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

rejected

Date and time stamp a request is denied by the recipient.

Related categories: 5

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

relief

Assistance and/or intervention during or after disaster to meet the life preservation and basic subsistence needs. It can be of emergency or protracted duration.

Related categories: 3.5, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

United Nations, Department of Humanitarian Affairs. Internationally agreed glossary of basic terms related to Disaster Management. Year of publication: 1992. Available from: <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/004DFD3E15B69A67C1256C4C006225C2-dha-glossary-1992.pdf>

remote procedure call (RPC)

When a computer program causes a procedure (subroutine) to execute in a different address space (commonly on another computer on a shared network), which is coded as if it were a normal (local) procedure call, without the programmer explicitly coding the details for the remote interaction.

Related categories: 2.2

replay attack

A network attack in which a packet is captured by an intruder during data transmission. The captured packet is either replaced with a fraudulent packet or repeated later. To protect against such attacks, a packet can contain a field that increments during the lifetime of the secret key that is protecting the packet.

Related categories: 3.3

reporting guideline

Document providing guidance on how to report a particular type of study.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

representational state transfer (REST)

Is a software architectural style that was created to guide the design and development of the architecture for the World Wide Web. REST defines a set of constraints for how the architecture of an Internet-scale distributed hypermedia system, such as the Web, should behave.

Related categories: 2.2

requester of assistance

The Member State or a third country affected by a disaster or imminent disaster or expecting to be affected by an imminent disaster, as well as the United Nations and its agencies and other specified relevant international organisations.

As referred in Annex VII of Decision N° 2014/762/EU, the Union civil protection assistance may be requested through or by any of these relevant international organisations. International Organization for Migration (IOM), International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC), and Organisation for the Prohibition of Chemical Weapons (OPCW)

Related categories: 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

requirement

Need or expectation that is stated, generally implied or obligatory

“Generally implied” means that it is custom or common practice for the organization and interested parties that the need or expectation under consideration is implied.

A specified requirement is one that is stated, e.g. in documented information.

This constitutes one of the common terms and core definitions of the high level structure for ISO management system standards.

Related categories: 1.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

rescue

An operation to retrieve persons in distress, provide for their initial medical or other needs, and deliver them to a place of safety

Related categories: 3.4

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icssc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

rescue action plan

A plan for rescue operations normally prepared by the SMC for implementation by the OSC and facilities on-scene

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icssc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

rescue coordination centre (RCC)

A unit responsible for promoting efficient organization of search and rescue services and for coordinating the conduct of search and rescue operations within a search and rescue region

Related categories: 3.4

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icssc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

rescuer

A person who helps someone out of a dangerous or unpleasant situation, in this context every person involved in rescue activities

Related categories: 3.4

research protocol

Document describing the background, rationale, objectives, design, methodology, statistical considerations, and organization of a research study.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

residual risk

Retained risk, risk remaining after risk treatment

Residual risk can contain unidentified risk.

The presence of residual risk implies a continuing need to develop and support effective capacities for emergency services, preparedness, response and recovery, together with socioeconomic policies such as safety nets and risk transfer mechanisms, as part of a holistic approach.

Related categories: 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

resilience

Ability to absorb and adapt in a changing environment

In the context of urban resilience the ability to absorb and adapt to a changing environment is determined by the collective capacity to anticipate, prepare and respond to threats and opportunities by each individual component of an urban system.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.3

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

resource

1. All assets (including plant and equipment), people, skills, technology, premises, and supplies and information (whether electronic or not) that an organization has to have available to use, when needed, in order to operate and meet its objective. 2. Personnel and major items of equipment, supplies, and facilities available or potentially available for assignment to incident operations and for which status is maintained. Resources are described by kind and type and may be used in operational support or supervisory capacities at an incident or at an Emergency Operations Center.

Related categories: 3.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

resource management

Systems for identifying available resources at all jurisdictional levels to enable timely, efficient, and unimpeded access to resources needed to prepare for, respond to, or recover from an incident.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

resource planning

The estimation of resource inputs (human resources, medical devices, medical equipment, pharmaceuticals and facilities) necessary to provide expected services.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

resource team

A set number of resources of the same kind and type that have an established minimum number of personnel, common communications, and a leader. In the law enforcement community, strike teams are sometimes referred to as resource teams.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

resource tracking

The process that all incident personnel and staff from associated organizations use to maintain information regarding the location and status of resources ordered for, deployed to, or assigned to an incident.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

response

1. The provision of emergency services and public assistance during or immediately after a disaster in order to save lives, reduce health impacts, ensure public safety and meet the basic subsistence needs of the people affected. 2. Any public health action triggered by the detection of a public health risk (e.g. monitoring of the event, information of the public, triggering field investigation and / or implementation of any control or mitigation measures). 3. Any action taken upon request for assistance under the Union Mechanism in the event of an imminent disaster, or during or after a disaster, to address its immediate adverse consequences.

Disaster response is predominantly focused on immediate and short-term needs and is sometimes called disaster relief. Effective, efficient and timely response relies on disaster risk-informed preparedness measures, including the development of the response capacities of individuals, communities, organizations, countries and the international community. The institutional elements of response often include the provision of emergency services and public assistance by public and private sectors and community sectors, as well as community and volunteer participation. "Emergency services" are a critical set of specialized agencies that have specific responsibilities in serving and protecting people and property in emergency and disaster situations. They include civil protection authorities and police and fire services, among many others. The division between the response stage and the subsequent recovery stage is not clear-cut. Some response actions, such as the supply of temporary housing and water supplies, may extend well into the recovery stage.

The nature of the response will have to be adapted according to the nature of the public health risk.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 4.4

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 1313/2013/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32013D1313&from=EN>

response agency

The public safety agency having legal or consensual obligation to respond to a call for service.

Related categories: 1.1, 3.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

response capacity

Means assistance that may be provided through the Union Mechanism upon request.

Related categories: 3.5, 4.4, 4.5

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 1313/2013/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32013D1313&from=EN>

response plan

Documented collection of procedures and information that is developed, compiled and maintained in preparedness for use in an incident

Related categories: 1.1, 3.2, 3.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

response programme

Plan, processes, and resources to perform the activities and services necessary to preserve and protect life, property, operations and critical assets

Response steps generally include incident recognition, notification, assessment, declaration, plan execution, communications, and resources management.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

response team

Group of individuals responsible for developing, executing, rehearsing, and maintaining the response plan, including the processes and procedures

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

resuscitation

The scientific techniques and manoeuvres applied to reverse acute terminal states and reanimate victims in clinical death, by using intensive care and intensive therapy methods.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

retained risk

Residual risk

Related categories: 3.1, 3.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

retrieval key

A 10-digit number that is used to uniquely identify an emergency call for the purpose of retrieving the ALI record by the PSAP.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

retrofitting

Reinforcement or upgrading of existing structures to become more resistant and resilient to the damaging effects of hazards.

Retrofitting requires consideration of the design and function of the structure, the stresses that the structure may be subject to from particular hazards or hazard scenarios and the practicality and costs of different retrofitting options. Examples of retrofitting include adding bracing to stiffen walls, reinforcing pillars, adding steel ties between walls and roofs, installing shutters on windows and improving the protection of important facilities and equipment.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

retrospective study

A type of study design that identifies an outcome and examines information that already occurred, it does not follow study participants into the future. Also known as a “historic cohort”.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

return on investment analysis

Analysis that calculates the size of the difference between positive consequences and costs, calculated by subtracting costs from benefits and expressing this figure as a proportion of overall costs.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

reverse evacuation

A common procedure implemented when conditions inside the building are safer than outside the building.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

review

Activity undertaken to determine the suitability, adequacy and effectiveness of the management system and its component elements to achieve established objectives

Related categories: 3.2, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

review visit

Participation by reviewers in peer review activities at the host location(s)

Review visit activities include presentations, individual interviews, focus groups, site visits, and the observation of live and table-top exercises.

Related categories: 3.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

reviewer

Entity that provides feedback as part of a peer review with expert knowledge and experience in the analysis area

The entity may be an organization, partnership, community, city, region, country or other body.

Related categories: 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

richter scale

Logarithmic scale, 1 to 8, indicating the magnitude or “size” of an earthquake, calculated on the amplitude of the seismic waves. All tremors 4, 5 or over are internationally recorded. An earthquake of amplitude 3 corresponds to a tremor felt over a limited area. 4.5 can cause light destruction. 6.6 causes considerable destruction. 7–8 causes very great destruction. Over 8, total destruction.

Related categories: 3.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

right to health

Right to health, wellbeing and adequate standard of living. Proclaimed by Article 25 of UDHR and the Constitution of WHO.

Related categories: 1.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

rights holder

Legal entity either holding or authorised to use one or more intellectual property rights

Related categories: 1.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

rigid hull craft

Rigid hulled boats come in a huge variety of shapes and sizes - they can have flat bottoms or deep Vs. They can be made of a wide variety of durable materials, such as aluminum, wood or plastic.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.5

Rescue 3 Europe Ltd. Rescue 3 International - Water and Flood Rescue Manual v6.2020. Available from: <https://www.rescue3europe.com/student-downloads/water-and-flood-rescue-manual/>

rigid inflatable boat (RIB)

A combination of the rigid hull for speed and directional stability, with the forgiving nature and stability of the inflated side tubes. very stable, seaworthy and very durable making them the perfect tool for any commercial work

Related categories: 3.4, 3.5

Rescue 3 Europe Ltd. Rescue 3 International - Water and Flood Rescue Manual v6.2020. Available from: <https://www.rescue3europe.com/student-downloads/water-and-flood-rescue-manual/>

ring vaccination

Strategy to inhibit the spread of an infectious disease by vaccinating only those who are most likely to be infected because they are (or have been) in close contact with an infected individual.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

risk

1. Effect of uncertainty on objectives. 2. The potential loss of life, injury, or destroyed or damaged assets which could occur to a system, society or a community in a specific period of time, determined probabilistically as a function of hazard, exposure, vulnerability and capacity.

An effect is a deviation from the expected. It can be positive, negative or both, and can address, create or result in opportunities and threats.

Objectives can have different aspects and categories, and can be applied at different levels.

Risk is usually expressed in terms of risk sources, potential events), their consequences and their likelihood.

This constitutes one of the common terms and core definitions of the high level structure for ISO management system standards.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

risk acceptance

Informed decision to take a particular risk

Risk acceptance can occur without risk treatment or during the process of risk treatment.

Accepted risks are subject to monitoring and review.

Related categories: 3.6, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

risk analysis

Process to comprehend the nature of risk and to determine the level of risk

Risk analysis provides the basis for risk evaluation and decisions about risk treatment.

Risk analysis includes risk estimation.

Related categories: 3.6, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

risk appetite

Amount and type of risk that an organization is willing to pursue or retain

Related categories: 3.1, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

risk assessment

Overall process of risk identification, risk analysis and risk evaluation

Risk assessment involves the process of identifying internal and external threats and vulnerabilities, identifying the likelihood and impact of an event arising from such threats or vulnerabilities, defining critical functions necessary to continue the organization's operations, defining the controls in place necessary to reduce exposure, and evaluating the cost of such controls.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.4, 3.6, 3.8, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 1313/2013/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32013D1313&from=EN>

risk communication

Exchange or sharing of information about risk between the decision maker and other interested parties

The information can relate to the existence, nature, form, probability, severity, acceptability, treatment or other aspects of risk.

Related categories: 3.6, 4.2, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

risk criteria

Terms of reference against which the significance of a risk is evaluated

Risk criteria are based on organizational objectives, and external and internal context.

Risk criteria can be derived from standards, laws, policies and other requirements.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.3, 3.6, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

risk evaluation

Process of comparing the results of risk analysis with risk criteria to determine whether the risk and/or its magnitude is acceptable or tolerable

Risk evaluation assists in the decision about risk treatment.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 3.1, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

risk identification

Process of finding, recognizing and describing risks

Risk identification involves the identification of risk sources, events), their causes and their potential consequences.

Risk identification can involve historical data, theoretical analysis, informed and expert opinions, and interested parties' needs.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 3.1, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

risk management

Coordinated activities to direct and control an organization with regard to risk

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 3.1, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

risk management capability

Ability of a Member State or its regions to reduce, adapt to or mitigate risks (impacts and likelihood of a disaster), identified in its risk assessments to levels that are acceptable in that Member State.

Risk management capability is assessed in terms of the technical, financial and administrative capacity to carry out adequate:

1. *risk assessments.*
2. *risk management planning for prevention and preparedness.*
3. *risk prevention and preparedness measures.*

Related categories: 3.6, 4.4, 4.5

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 1313/2013/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32013D1313&from=EN>

risk map

Cartographic representation of the types and degrees of hazard and of natural phenomena that may cause or contribute to a disaster.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.7

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

risk mitigation

Lessening or minimizing of the adverse impacts of a hazardous event

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

risk owner

Entity with the accountability and authority to manage a risk

Related categories: 1.1, 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

risk ratio

The ratio of the incidence of a disease among exposed people to the incidence of the disease among unexposed people.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

risk reduction

Actions taken to lessen the probability or negative consequences, or both, associated with a risk

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

risk register

Record of information about identified risks

Compilation for all risks identified, analysed and evaluated in the risk assessment process, including information on the risk register includes information on likelihood, consequences, treatments and risk owners.

Related categories: 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

risk sharing

Form of risk treatment involving the agreed distribution of risk with other parties

Legal or regulatory requirements can limit, prohibit or mandate risk sharing.

Risk sharing can be carried out through insurance or other forms of contract.

The extent to which risk is distributed can depend on the reliability and clarity of the sharing arrangements.

Risk transfer is a form of risk sharing.

Related categories: 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

risk source

Element that alone or in combination has the potential to give rise to risk

Related categories: 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

risk tolerance

Organization's or interested party's readiness to bear the risk after risk treatment in order to achieve its objectives

Risk tolerance can be influenced by client, stakeholder, legal, or regulatory requirements.

Related categories: 1.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

risk transfer

The process of formally or informally shifting the financial consequences of particular risks from one party to another, whereby a household, community, enterprise or State authority will obtain resources from the other party after a disaster occurs, in exchange for ongoing or compensatory social or financial benefits provided to that other party.

Insurance is a well-known form of risk transfer, where coverage of a risk is obtained from an insurer in exchange for ongoing premiums paid to the insurer. Risk transfer can occur informally within family and community networks where there are reciprocal expectations of mutual aid by means of gifts or credit, as well as formally, wherein governments, insurers, multilateral banks and other large risk-bearing entities establish mechanisms to help cope with losses in major events. Such mechanisms include insurance and reinsurance contracts, catastrophe bonds, contingent credit facilities and reserve funds,

where the costs are covered by premiums, investor contributions, interest rates and past savings, respectively.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

risk treatment

Process to modify risk

Risk treatment can involve:

- *avoiding the risk by deciding not to start or continue with the activity that gives rise to the risk;*
- *taking or increasing risk in order to pursue an opportunity;*
- *removing the risk source;*
- *changing the likelihood;*
- *changing the consequences;*
- *sharing the risk with another party or parties (including contracts and risk financing); and*
- *retaining the risk by informed decision.*

Risk treatments that deal with negative consequences are sometimes referred to as “risk mitigation”, “risk elimination”, “risk prevention” and risk reduction.

Risk treatment can create new risks or modify existing risks.

Related categories: 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

river left

The left side of the channel when looking downstream

Related categories: 3.4

Rescue 3 Europe Ltd. Rescue 3 International - Water and Flood Rescue Manual v6.2020. Available from: <https://www.rescue3europe.com/student-downloads/water-and-flood-rescue-manual/>

river orientation

The orientation of the river flow

Related categories: 3.4

Rescue 3 Europe Ltd. Rescue 3 International - Water and Flood Rescue Manual v6.2020. Available from: <https://www.rescue3europe.com/student-downloads/water-and-flood-rescue-manual/>

river right

The right side of the channel when looking downstream

Related categories: 3.4

Rescue 3 Europe Ltd. Rescue 3 International - Water and Flood Rescue Manual v6.2020. Available from: <https://www.rescue3europe.com/student-downloads/water-and-flood-rescue-manual/>

riverine flood

A type of flooding resulting from the overflow of water from a stream or river channel onto normally dry land in the floodplain adjacent to the channel.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

roaming

Roaming: means gaining network access through a service provider other than the one that the subscriber purchases service from, or outside the subscriber's home service territory.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

robustness

Ability of a system to resist virtual or physical, internal or external attacks

Particularly, the ability to resist attempted imitation, copy, intrusion or bypassing.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

rock fall

Type of landslide that occur when heavy rain or rapid snow/ice melt send large amounts of rock downslope by gravitational forces.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

rogue wave

An unusual single crest of an ocean wave far out at sea that is much higher and/or steeper than other waves in the prevailing swell system.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

role 1

A NATO medical support module which is integral or allocated to a small unit and will include the capabilities for providing first aid, immediate life saving measures, and triage. Additionally it will contribute to the health and well being of the unit through provision of guidance in prevention of disease, non battle injuries and operational stress. Normally, routine sick call and the management of minor sick and injured personnel for immediate return to duty are function of this level of care.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.3, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

role 2

A NATO medical support module, normally provided at larger unit level, usually of Brigade or larger size, though it may be provided farther forward, depending upon the operational requirements. In general, it will be prepared to provide evacuation from Role 1 facilities, triage and resuscitation, treatment and holding of patients until they can be returned to duty or evacuated, and emergency dental treatment. Though normally this level will not include surgical capabilities, certain operations may require their augmentation with the capabilities to perform emergency surgery and essential post-operative management. In this case, they will be often referred to as Role 2+. In the maritime forces, Echelon 2 is equivalent to the land forces' Role 2+, as a surgical team is integral to this echelon. Maritime echelon 2 support is normally found on major war vessels and some larger logistics or support vessels, and at some Forward Logistics Sites (FLS).

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.3, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

role 3

A NATO medical support module, normally provided at Division level and above. It includes additional capabilities, including specialist diagnostic resources, specialist surgical and medical capabilities, preventive medicine, food inspection, dentistry, and operational stress management teams when not provided at level 2. The holding capacity of a level 3 facility will be sufficient to allow diagnosis, treatment, and holding of those patients who can receive total treatment and be returned to duty within the evacuation policy laid down by the Force Surgeon for the theatre. Classically, this support will be provided by field hospitals of various types. Maritime Echelon 3 is equivalent to land/air forces Role 3, though it will normally have increased specialty capabilities. Echelon 3 is normally found on some major amphibious ships, on hospital ships, at Fleet Hospitals, at some FLS, and at a few Advanced

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.3, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

role 4

A NATO medical support module providing definitive care of patients for whom the treatment required is longer than the theatre evacuation policy or for whom the capabilities usually found at role/echelon 3 are inadequate. This would normally comprise specialist surgical and medical procedures, reconstruction, rehabilitation, and convalescence. This level of care is usually highly specialised, time consuming, and normally provided in the country of origin. Under unusual circumstances, this level of care may be established in a theatre of operations.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.3, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

role-player

A person who simulates a specific pre-scripted role in the exercise, actor.

Related categories: 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

router

A router is a device that allows interconnecting networks with different IP address prefixes. Its function is to establish the best route for each data packet to reach the network and the destination device.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

routing information protocol (RIP)

Protocol used to share information between routers to discover new networks. It is one of the oldest distance-vector routing protocols which employs the hop count as a routing metric.

Related categories: 2.2

RSA

A method for obtaining digital signatures and public key cryptosystems.

Related categories: 3.3

safe hospital

A facility whose services remain accessible and functioning at maximum capacity, and with the same infrastructure before, during and immediately after the impact of emergencies and disasters.

Related categories: 3.5, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

safety at sea

The international laws and regulations enacted for the security of maritime navigation and the safety of life at sea.

Related categories: 1.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

safety officer

A member of the Command Staff responsible for monitoring incident operations and advising the Incident Commander on all matters relating to operational safety, including the health and safety of emergency responder personnel.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

sandstorm

Large amount of sand particles carried aloft by strong winds.

Strong winds carry particles of sand aloft, but generally confined to less than 50 feet (15 m), especially common in arid and semi-arid environments.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

sanitation

The provision of facilities and services for the safe management of human excreta from the toilet to containment and storage and treatment onsite or conveyance, treatment and eventual safe end use or disposal.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

SAR

Search and Rescue

Related categories: 3.4

Rescue 3 Europe Ltd. Rescue 3 International - Water and Flood Rescue Manual v6.2020. Available from: <https://www.rescue3europe.com/student-downloads/water-and-flood-rescue-manual/>

scenario

1. An account or synopsis of a possible course of events that could occur, which forms the basis for planning assumptions (for example, a river floods, covering a nearby town and wiping out the local population's crop).

2. Pre-planned storyline that drives an exercise, as well as the stimuli used to achieve exercise project performance objectives.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.7, 3.8, 4.1, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

scene location

Collection of geo-locations that defines the perimeter of the viewable scene of a camera

The coordinate system is the same for each geo-location in the collection. There is at least one geo-location in the scene location. The geo-locations are ordered in either clockwise or counter clockwise order. Single geo-location scenes interpret the geo-location as the centre of the scene.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

scope of exercise

Magnitude, resources and extent that reflects the needs and objectives

Related categories: 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

scope of service

Function(s) that an organization in the supply chain performs, and where it performs this/these functions

Related categories: 3.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

scoping review

Research synthesis that maps the existing literature on a particular topic or research area.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

script

Story of the exercises it develops, which allows directing staff to understand how events should develop during exercise play as the various elements of the master events list are introduced

The script is often written as a narrative of simulated events.

Related categories: 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

sea conditions

An assessment of the agitation of the surface of the sea. The state of the sea is expressed numerically by the Douglas scale or by the height of the waves.

Related categories: 3.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

search action plan

Message, normally developed by the SMC, for passing instructions to SAR facilities and agencies participating in a SAR mission

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icsc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

search and rescue (SAR)

The extensive system using air, sea, land and other means employed to look for, locate, rescue and recover disaster victims and apply the necessary emergency aid and treatment. INSARAG, the International Rescue Advisory Group, coordinates these efforts worldwide.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

search and rescue mission coordinator (SMC)

The official temporarily assigned to coordinate response to an actual or apparent distress situation

Related categories: 3.4

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icsc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

search and rescue unit (SRU)

A unit composed of trained personnel and provided with equipment suitable for the expeditious conduct of search and rescue operations

Related categories: 3.1

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icsc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

secondary data

Data collected by someone other than the user.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

secondary healthcare facility

Diseases that cannot be managed at the peripheral primary health-care level are referred to a secondary health-care facility which is more specialized and can meet more advanced diagnostic and therapeutic needs, such as radiography, general surgery, complicated pregnancy, etc., by trained staff. More complicated and specialized conditions are referred to a tertiary health-care centre.

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

secondary prevention

Strategies to prevent a disease from worsening or recurring.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

secret

Data and/or knowledge that are protected against disclosure to unauthorised entities

Related categories: 1.1, 3.3

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

section

The Incident Command System organizational level having responsibility for a major functional area of incident management (e.g., Operations, Planning, Logistics, Finance/Administration, and Intelligence/Investigations (if established)). The Section is organizationally situated between the Branch and the Incident Command.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

sector budget support

A subcategory of direct budget support co-funding the national budget of a particular sector. The support is thus nominally earmarked, for the sector and used according to the national public expenditure management rules and procedures.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

secure sockets layer (SSL)

A form of secure low-level encryption that is used by protocols like HTTP and FTP. The SSL protocol includes provisions for server authentication, encryption of data in transit, and optional client authentication.

Related categories: 3.3

security

State of being free from danger or threat where procedures are followed or after taking appropriate measures

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

security aspect

Characteristic, element, or property that reduces the risk of unintentionally-, intentionally- and naturally-caused crises and disasters that disrupt and have consequences on the products and services, operation, critical assets and continuity of an organization and its interested parties

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

security cleared

Process of verifying the trustworthiness of people who will have access to security sensitive information

Related categories: 5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

security declaration

Documented commitment by a business partner, which specifies security measures implemented by that business partner, including, at a minimum, how goods and physical instruments of international trade are safeguarded, associated information is protected and security measures are demonstrated and verified

It will be used by the organization in the supply chain to evaluate the adequacy of security measures related to the security of goods.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

security incident

Any act or circumstance that produces a consequence

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

security management

Coordinated activities to direct and control an organization with regard to security and resilience

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.3, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

security management objective

Specific outcome or achievement required of security in order to meet the security management policy

It is essential that such outcomes are linked either directly or indirectly to providing the products, supply or services delivered by the total business to its customers or end users.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.3, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

security management policy

Overall intentions and direction of an organization, related to the security and the framework for the control of security-related processes and activities that are derived from and consistent with its policy and regulatory requirements

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.3

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

security management programme

Process by which a security management objective is achieved

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.2, 3.3

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

security management target

Specific level of performance required to achieve a security management objective

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

security operation

Activity and function related to the protection of people, and tangible and intangible assets

Security operations can require the carrying and operating a weapon in the performance of their duties.

The concept includes the International Code of Conduct (ICoC) definition of security services: guarding and protection of people and objects, such as convoys, facilities, designated sites, property or other places (whether armed or unarmed) or any other activity for which the personnel of companies are required to carry or operate a weapon in the performance of their duties.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

security operations management

Coordinated activities to direct and control an organization with regard to security operations

Direction and control with regard to security operations management generally includes establishment of the policy, planning and objectives directing operational processes and continual improvement.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

security operations objective

Objective sought, or aimed for, related to security operations

Security operations objectives are generally based on the organization's security operations policy.

Security operations objectives are generally specified for relevant functions and levels in the organization.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

security operations personnel

People working on behalf of an organization who are engaged directly or indirectly in security operations

Related categories: 3.4, 3.6, 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

security operations policy

Overall intentions and direction of an organization related to security operations as formally expressed by top management

Generally, the security operations policy is consistent with the overall policy of the organization and provides a framework for the setting of security operations objectives.

Security operations management principles presented in this document can form a basis for the establishment of a security operations policy consistent with the principles and obligations outlined in the International Code of Conduct (ICoC) and the Montreux Document.

Related categories: 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

security operations programme

Ongoing management and governance process supported by top management and resourced to ensure that the necessary steps are taken to coordinate the efforts to achieve the objectives of the security operations management system

Related categories: 1.1, 3.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

security personnel

People in an organization in the supply chain who have been assigned security related duties

These people can be employees of the organization.

Related categories: 1.1, 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 4.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

security plan

Planned arrangements for ensuring that security is adequately managed

It is designed to ensure the application of measures that protect the organization from a security incident.

The plan can be incorporated into other operational plans.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

security sensitive information

Security sensitive material, information or material, produced by or incorporated into the supply chain security process, that contains information about the security processes, shipments or government directives that would not be readily available to the public and would be useful to someone wishing to initiate a security incident

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.3, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

security threat scenario

Means by which a potential security incident can occur

Related categories: 3.1, 3.7, 4.3

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

seiche

A standing wave of water in a large semi- or fully-enclosed body of water (lakes or bays) created by strong winds and/or a large barometric pressure gradient,

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgLS55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

self-defence

Protection of one's person or property against some injury attempted by another

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

self-efficacy

A person's belief in their capacity to do a given task or achieve a specific level of performance. Self-efficacy consists of both confidence and perceived control; it is linked to motivation and behavioural perseverance in the face of obstacles.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

self-organization

An emergent property of complex adaptive systems where actors within the system make adjustments to adapt to changing context; in social systems it is often behavioural adjustments made by people within a system.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

self-reliance

The social and economic ability of an individual, a household or a community to meet their own essential needs (including food, water, shelter, personal safety, health and education) in a sustainable manner and with dignity.

Related categories: 3.5, 4.4

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

semantic interoperability

Ability of two or more systems or services to automatically interpret and use information that has been exchanged accurately

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

semi-structured interview

A method of research in which the interviewer uses a framework but allows new topics to be discussed depending on what is said by the interviewee.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

seminar

A discussion-based exercise designed to orient participants to new or updated plans, policies, or procedures through informal discussions.

Related categories: 4.1

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030

Voluntary, non-binding agreement covering the period 2015-2030 which recognizes that the State has the primary role of reducing disaster risk but that responsibility should be shared with other stakeholders, including local government, the private sector and other stakeholders.

It aims for the substantial reduction of disaster risk and losses in lives, livelihoods and health and in the economic, physical, social, cultural and environmental assets of persons, businesses, communities and countries.

Related categories: 1.1, 3.2, 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

Sendai Framework monitor (SFM)

Management tool to help countries to develop disaster risk reduction strategies, make risk-informed policy decisions and allocate resources to prevent new disaster risks.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.2, 3.5, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

sender

Person, company or machine in charge of initiating the communication and sending the message.

Related categories: 3.3

sensitive information

Information that is protected from public disclosure only because it would have an adverse effect on an organization, national security or public safety

Related categories: 1.1, 2.2, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

sensor

An entity/device capable of observing a phenomenon and returning an observed value.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

server

In information technology, a server is a computer program that provides services to other computer programs (and their users) in the same or other computers. The computer that a

server program runs in is also frequently referred to as a server (though it may be used for other purposes as well).

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

service access points

Specifies the network address of the processing entity that exposes the service interface.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

service composition

Used to bring together multiple services to satisfy more complex or higher-level needs.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

service set identifier (SSID)

The SSID is a sequence of up to 32 octets included in all packets of a wireless network to identify them as part of that network. The code consists of up to 32 characters, most often alphanumeric.

Related categories: 2.2

session initiation protocol (SIP)

An IETF defined protocol (RFC3261) that defines a method for establishing multimedia sessions over the Internet. Used as the call signalling protocol in VoIP, i2 and i3

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

setting approach

An approach that considers the interaction of multiple components which form an entire system.

Interventions integrating these components are established to reduce the risk factors contributing to diseases

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

shelter in place

Remain or take immediate refuge in a protected location relevant to the risk

Action to move people to predetermined areas inside the building / site in order to protect them from external dangers during an incident.

This may be referred to as "invacuation".

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 3.6, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

sheltering

Action that consists of providing asylum or provisional lodgings to an individual or group.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 3.6

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

shock

1. An acute condition in which the flow of blood to the tissues and the output of the heart are not adequate to sustain the body's normal functions and may lead to death unless emergency measures are taken. 2. Uncertain, abrupt or long-onset event), that has potential to impact upon the purpose or objectives of an urban system

Related categories: 3.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

shockwave

A shockwave carries energy from a disturbance through a medium (solid, liquid, gas) similar to a wave though it travels at much higher speed. It can be a type of extraterrestrial hazard caused by the explosion (airburst) or impact of meteorites that generate energy shockwaves capable of shattering glass, collapsing walls, etc.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgLS5evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

short message service (SMS)

A service typically provided by mobile carriers that sends short (160 characters or fewer) messages to an endpoint. SMS is often fast, but is not real time.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

simple mail transfer protocol (SMTP)

An internet standard communication protocol for electronic mail transmission. Mail servers and other message transfer agents use SMTP to send and receive mail messages.

Related categories: 2.2

simple network management protocol (SNMP)

An Internet Standard protocol for collecting and organizing information about managed devices on IP networks and for modifying that information to change device behaviour.

Related categories: 2.2

simulation

Imitative representation of the functioning of one system or process by means of the functioning of another

Related categories: 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

simulation optimization (SIMOP)

Process of finding the best input variable values from among all possibilities without explicitly evaluating each possibility.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

single point of failure

A failure of a hardware or software component or sub-system which causes a system to fail.

Related categories: 2.2

NENA (USA National Emergency Number Association). NENA Glossary of 9-1-1 Terminology. Year of publication: 2021. Available from: https://nenawiki.org/wiki/NENA_Glossary_of_9-1-1_Terminology (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

single resource

An individual, a piece of equipment and its personnel complement, or a crew/team of individuals with an identified work supervisor that can be used on an incident.

Related categories: 3.5

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

sinkhole

Collapse of the land surface due to the dissolving of the subsurface rocks such as limestone or carbonate rock by water.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

situation report (SITREP)

A routinely produced report that provides current information about an emergency response and immediate and future response actions, an analysis of the impact of the emergency, and related management issues.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from:

<https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

situational awareness

Being aware of and attentive to what is happening in a given environment at a particular time, with particular emphasis on the effect of changes in the environment; in effect, knowing how an incident or event is evolving.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 3.6, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

slow-onset disaster

A disaster that emerges gradually over time. Note: Slow-onset disasters could be associated with, for example, drought, desertification, sea-level rise, epidemic disease.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

Small-scale Tool

One of the 4 tools within the EU Emergency Toolbox. It is used to assist a limited number of people (below 100,000) affected by a natural or human-induced disaster. The maximum allocation per action is €500,000.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Commission, European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations ECHO. European Commission official website. Available from: https://ec.europa.eu/echo/emergency-toolbox-eu-funding-sudden-onset-humanitarian-crises_en (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

smurf attack

The process of creating severe network congestion or outages by using ICMP echo request packets directed to an IP broadcast address or multiple broadcast addresses from remote locations.

Related categories: 3.3

sniff

To eavesdrop on computer network, frequently used as part of automated programs to sift information, such as clear-text passwords, off the wire.

Related categories: 3.3

SNOMED-CT

Collection of medical terms providing codes, terms, synonyms and definitions used in clinical documentation and reporting.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

snow

Precipitation in the form of ice crystals/snowflakes or ice pellets (sleet) formed directly from freezing water vapour in the air.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

snow avalanche

Rapid downslope movement of a mix of snow and ice.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

social media

Websites and other applications that enable users to create and share content or to participate in social networking online.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

social network analysis

Process for investigating social structures through the use of networks and graph theory.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

social norms

Collective representations of acceptable group conduct as well as individual perceptions of particular group conduct.

Related categories: 1.1

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

social protection

Preventing, managing and overcoming situations that adversely affect people's well-being

It consists of policies and programmes designed to reduce poverty and vulnerability by promoting efficient labour markets, diminishing people's exposure to risks, and enhancing their capacity to manage economic and social risks, such as unemployment, exclusion, sickness, disability and old age.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.3, 3.8, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

socionatural hazards

Hazards that are associated with a combination of natural and anthropogenic factors, including environmental degradation and climate change.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

sockets

A method for communication between two applications in a network. The socket is defined as “the endpoint in a connection”.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

software development kit (SDK)

A software development kit (SDK) is a collection of software development tools in one installable package. They facilitate the creation of applications by having a compiler, debugger and perhaps a software framework.

Related categories: 2.2

software platform

A software platform is a framework of software that is curated to allow applications to work together seamlessly, without workarounds or integrations.

Related categories: 3.3

somatic symptom

Health-related symptoms that cause significant distress or disruption in daily living.

Related categories: 3.4

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

source

Anything which alone or in combination has the intrinsic potential to give rise to risk

Adapted from ISO/Guide 73:2009.

A risk source can be tangible or intangible.

Related categories: 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

space weather

A general term for extraterrestrial weather conditions driven by solar eruptions such as geomagnetic storms, radio disturbances, and solar energetic particles.

Related categories: 5

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

span of control

The number of subordinates for which a supervisor is responsible, usually expressed as the ratio of supervisors to individuals.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

spatial interface (SI)

A standardized interface between the GIS data and the functional elements that consume GIS data, such as the ECRF, LVF, Map Database Services, etc

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.6, 3.7

NENA (USA National Emergency Number Association). NENA Glossary of 9-1-1 Terminology. Year of publication: 2021. Available from: https://nenawiki.org/wiki/NENA_Glossary_of_9-1-1_Terminology (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

SPICE framework

Framework for specifying research questions, which includes Setting, Perspective, Intervention, Comparison and Evaluation.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

spontaneous volunteer (SV)

Individual who is not affiliated with an existing incident response organization or voluntary organization but who, without extensive preplanning, offers support to the response to, and recovery from, an incident

A spontaneous volunteer can also be referred to as a convergent volunteer, a walk-in volunteer, an occasional volunteer, an episodic volunteer or a non-affiliated volunteer.

Related categories: 3.5, 4.2, 4.3, 4.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

spyware

Software that is secretly or surreptitiously installed into an information system to gather information on individuals or organizations without their knowledge; a type of malicious code.

Related categories: 3.3

staging area

A temporary location for available resources in which personnel, supplies, and equipment await operational assignment.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

stakeholder

Interested party

Related categories: 1.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

standard

An established, accepted and evidence-based technical specification or basis for comparison. An object or quality or measure serving as a basis for example or principle to which others conform or by which others conform or should conform or by which the accuracy or quality of

others is judged. Document, established by consensus and approved by a recognized body, that provides, for common and repeated use, rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results, aimed at the achievement of the optimum degree of order in a given context.

Standards should be based on the consolidated results of science, technology and experience, and aimed at the promotion of optimum community benefits.

Related categories: 1.1, 3.2

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO/IEC 20944-1:2013(en) Information technology - Metadata Registries Interoperability and Bindings (MDR-IB) - Part 1: Framework, common vocabulary, and common provisions for conformance. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui#iso:std:iso-iec:20944:-1:ed-1:v1:en:term:3.14.4.12> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

standard case definition

An agreed set of criteria used to describe if a person has a particular disease or was exposed to a particular pathogen.

Case definitions are used to label a case, such as suspected, probable, confirmed. Standard definitions ensure that every case is detected and reported in the same way. Once a case meets the standard case definition for notification, it is labelled as a suspect case. Sometimes a broader syndromic case definition is used to improve the likelihood of finding cases of interest, although other similar diseases might also be detected. During case investigation, clinical criteria, laboratory testing and epidemiological information are used to confirm the case.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

standard operating procedure (SOP)

Document describing how to perform a procedure. A reference document or an operations manual that provides the purpose, authorities, duration, and details for the preferred method of performing a single function or several interrelated functions in a uniform manner.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

standard precautions

The basic level of infection control precautions which are to be used, as a minimum, in the care of all patients.

Standard precautions are meant to reduce the risk of transmission of bloodborne and other pathogens from both recognized and unrecognized sources. They include: hand hygiene, personal protective equipment, and respiratory hygiene and cough etiquette, waste disposal and environmental cleaning.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

standards development organization (SDO)

An entity whose primary activities are developing, coordinating, promulgating, revising, amending, reissuing, interpreting, or otherwise maintaining standards that address the interests of a wide base of users outside the standards development organization.

Related categories: 5

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

START

Simple Triage And Rapid Treatment: a procedure for quickly classifying injured patients according to the severity of their injuries and for treating those who are most severely injured first

A standard procedure to do triage

Related categories: 3.4

start bit

In asynchronous transmission, the first element in each character that prepares the receiving device to recognize the incoming information.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

static metadata

Data associated with a digital image aside from the pixel values that does not change over time (or at least does not change over the addressed sequence)

Related categories: 2.2, 3.2, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

status report

Reports, such as spot reports, that include vital and/or time-sensitive information. Status reports are typically function-specific, less formal than situation reports, and are not always issued on a specific schedule.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.3, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

stockpile

A reserve of supplies and equipment to meet emergency needs.

For example, a medical stockpile includes essential medicines, vaccines, protective equipment and other supplies and equipment for use in response to a health emergency.

Related categories: 3.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

stop bit

In asynchronous transmission, the last transmitted element in each character, which permits the receiver to come to an idle condition before accepting another character.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

storm surge

An abnormal rise in sea level generated by a tropical cyclone or other intense storms.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgLS55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

strategic exercise

Exercise involving top management at a strategic level

Strategic-level top management typically includes inter-ministerial crisis personnel, political-administrative personnel, cross-sector and cross-departmental management personnel, and the crisis management organization of the corporate management team.

Strategic exercises are designed to assess reactions to crisis in extreme situations.

Strategic exercises are designed to develop a comprehensive coordination and decision-making culture in organizations in the public, private and not-for-profit sectors.

Related categories: 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

strategy

A series of broad lines of action intended to achieve a set of goals and targets set out within a policy or programme.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

stream control transmission protocol (SCTP)

A computer networking communications protocol in the transport layer of the Internet protocol suite. The protocol provides the message-oriented feature of the User Datagram Protocol (UDP), while ensuring reliable, in-sequence transport of messages with congestion control like the Transmission Control Protocol (TCP). Unlike UDP and TCP, the protocol supports multihoming and redundant paths to increase resilience and reliability.

Related categories: 2.2

strengths-based approach

A collaborative approach that identifies and builds on existing capabilities of individuals, groups, organizations, or systems within the community to address a problem (see also asset-based approach).

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

stress

1. Chronic and ongoing dynamic pressure originated within an urban system, with the potential for cumulative impacts on the ability and capacity of the system to achieve its objectives. 2. Body's reaction to a change that requires a physical, mental or emotional adjustment or response; a psychological and physical response of the body that occurs whenever we must adapt to changing conditions, whether those conditions be real or perceived; the non-specific response of the body to any demand for change.

Related categories: 1.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

stress management

Encompasses techniques intended to equip a person with effective coping mechanisms for dealing with psychological stress, with stress defined as a person's physiological response to an internal or external stimulus that triggers the fight-or-flight response. Stress management is effective when a person uses strategies to cope with or alter stressful situations.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.6

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

structural

Any component of the building whose primary function is to support the dead load (e.g., building, roof).

Related categories: 5

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

structural analysis

An analytic strategy in narrative research that focuses on exploring how a story was told (that is to say structured) by the research participant.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

structural measures

Any physical construction to reduce or avoid possible impacts of hazards, or the application of engineering techniques or technology to achieve hazard resistance and resilience in structures or systems.

Common structural measures for disaster risk reduction include dams, flood levies, ocean wave barriers, earthquake-resistant construction and evacuation shelters. Note that in civil and structural engineering, the term “structural” is used in a more restricted sense to mean just the load-bearing structure, and other parts such as wall cladding and interior fittings are termed ‘non-structural’.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

structured interview matrix

Technique used for conducting large focus groups and promoting consultation with a variety of stakeholders.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

subcontracting

Contracting with an external party to fulfil an obligation arising out of an existing contract

When a party is contracted to perform a range of services, it may subcontract one or more of those services to a “subcontractor” or local forces.

Subsidiaries of a parent company may be considered a subcontracting organization.

Related categories: 3.2, 4.2, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

subsidence

Sinking of the ground due to groundwater removal, mining, dissolution of limestone (e.g., karst, sinkholes), extraction of natural gas, and earthquakes.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNi/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

sudden onset disaster

A disaster that is triggered by a hazardous event that emerges quickly or unexpectedly. Disasters that occur with little or no warning, meaning there is insufficient time for the complete evacuation of the at risk populations.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.8

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

summative evaluation

Evaluations conducted after the conclusion of a programme, or examining the impact of the programme.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

supervisor

The Incident Command System title for an individual responsible for a Division or Group.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

supply chain

Two-way relationship of organizations, people, processes, logistics, information, technology and resources engaged in activities and creating value from the sourcing of materials through the delivery of products or services

The supply chain may include vendors, subcontractors, manufacturing facilities, logistics providers, internal distribution centres, distributors, wholesalers and other entities that lead to the end user.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

supply chain continuity management (SCCM)

Application of business continuity management to a supply chain

Business continuity management should be applied to all the tiers of an organization's supply chain.

In practice, an organization usually would only apply it to the first tier of their suppliers and influence critical suppliers to apply SCCM to their suppliers.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 3.5, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

supporting agency

An agency that provides essential services, personnel, or material to support or assist a lead agency (i.e. the supported agency).

Supporting agencies may support either by assisting (i.e. contributing their own operational resources) or cooperating (providing indirect assistance).

Related categories: 3.5, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

surge

Sudden demand for health services in a mass casualty incident where additional capacities (in terms of the amount of personnel, equipment or supplies) and / or capabilities (in terms of specialized expertise) are required.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 4.2

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

surge capacity

Ability of institutions such as clinics, hospitals, or public health laboratories to respond to increased demand for their services during a public health emergency.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 4.2

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

surveillance

The systematic ongoing collection, collation and analysis of data for public health purposes and the timely dissemination of public health information for assessment and public health response as necessary.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

surveillance in post extreme emergency and disaster (SPEED)

Surveillance system developed by WHO and the Ministry of Health of the Philippines to collect data following a disaster.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.8, 4.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

survival chain

In emergency and critical medicine, the four links in the chain essential for the survival of the victim are (1) early access, to get help, immediate response and call for EMS; (2) early CPR to buy time; cardiopulmonary resuscitation to keep oxygenated blood flowing to the brain until additional help arrives; (3) early defibrillation, to “restart” the heart with an automatic defibrillator and (4) early ACLS, providing advanced cardiac life support with airway clearance, lung ventilation cardiac therapy and necessary monitoring-

Related categories: 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

suspect

Those persons, baggage, cargo, containers, conveyances, goods or postal parcels considered by a State Party as having been exposed to a public health risk and that could be a possible source of spread of disease.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

sustainability

The potential for sustaining beneficial outcomes for an agreed period at an acceptable level of resource commitment within acceptable organizational and community contingencies.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

swiftwater

Fast moving water, flowing down a steeper gradient, e.g., steep rivers, drainage channels, flash flood conditions

Related categories: 3.1

Rescue 3 Europe Ltd. Rescue 3 International - Water and Flood Rescue Manual v6.2020. Available from: <https://www.rescue3europe.com/student-downloads/water-and-flood-rescue-manual/>

symmetric cryptographic key

An encryption system in which the sender and receiver of a message share a single common key. This common key is used to encrypt and decrypt the message.

Related categories: 3.3

sync

Abbreviation for synchronized or synchronization.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.7

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

synchronization

In the context of timing, synchronization means to bring clocks or data streams into phase.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.7

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

syndromic surveillance

A method of surveillance that uses health-related data based on clinical observations rather than laboratory confirmation of diagnoses.

Syndromic surveillance is used in order to detect outbreaks earlier than would otherwise be possible with laboratory diagnosis-based methods. Case definitions used for syndromic surveillance are based on clinical signs and symptoms, rather than on specific laboratory criteria for confirmation of the causative agent.

Related categories: 3.8

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

syntactic interoperability

Ability of two or more systems or services to exchange structured information

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.6, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

system

Any combination of processes, facilities, equipment, personnel, procedures, and communications integrated for a specific purpose.

Related categories: 5

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from:

<https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

systematic review

Method for knowledge synthesis that collects and critically analyses multiple research studies on a specific topic.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

systematic sampling

Sampling of people from an ordered sampling frame.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

systems lens

Similar to systems thinking, a way of looking at a problem or situation in terms of the relationships between interconnected components of a complex system.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

systems thinking

An approach to research which views the dynamic and complex context surrounding a problem, including multi-level influences on different interrelated components.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

tabletop exercise (TTX)

A discussion-based exercise intended to stimulate discussion of various issues regarding a hypothetical situation, generally in an informal, low-stress environment.

Tabletop exercises can be used to assess plans, policies, and procedures or to assess types of systems needed to guide the prevention of, response to, or recovery from a defined incident. TTXs are typically aimed at facilitating understanding of concepts, identifying strengths and shortfalls, and/or achieving a change in attitude. Participants are encouraged to discuss issues in depth and develop decisions through slow-paced problem-solving rather than the rapid, spontaneous decision-making that occurs under actual or simulated emergency conditions. TTXs can be breakout (i.e., groups split into functional areas) or plenary (i.e., one large group).

Related categories: 4.1

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

tactics

The deployment and directing of resources on an incident to accomplish the objectives.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

tag

A unique label that precedes the data for the data element associated with the tag.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

tag data

A method of identifying data elements of varying lengths within a data record.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

tag data record

A record of varying length comprised of pre-defined tag labels and their associated data elements.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

tampering

An intentional but unauthorized act resulting in the modification of a system, components of systems, its intended behavior, or data.

Related categories: 3.3

target

1. Detailed performance requirement, applicable to the organization or parts thereof, that arises from the objectives, and that needs to be set and met in order to achieve those objectives. 2. An intermediate result towards an objective that a programme seeks to achieve, within a specified time frame, a target is more specific than an objective and lends itself more readily to being expressed in quantitative terms.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.6, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

target group

Individuals or organizations subject to exercise

Related categories: 5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

target team

In simulation exercises: teams or organizations subject to the exercise. See also “participant”.

Related categories: 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

task force (TF)

Any combination of resources of different kinds and/or types assembled to support a specific mission or operational need.

Related categories: 4.2

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

team leader

EU Civil Protection Mechanism category of expert referred in article 41 of Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014, who shall be responsible for leading the assessment and coordination team during an intervention. The team leader shall assume proper liaison with the authorities of the affected country, with the ERCC, including ERCC liaison officer, with other international organisations and, in case of any assistance interventions under the Union Mechanism outside Member States, also with the Union delegation in that country.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.2, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 4.4

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

technical assistance and support team (TAST)

EU Civil Protection Mechanism human and material resources set-up by one or more Member States to fulfil support tasks, as referred to in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams). Their tasks are provide or arrange for: 1) support for set-up and running of office, 2) ICT support, 3) logistics and subsistence support, 4) transport support on site.

Related categories: 3.4, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

technical expert

A category of expert referred in article 41 of Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014, who shall be able to provide advice on specific, highly technical topics and on risks involved and be available for missions.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.2, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 4.4

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

technical specialist

Individual with special skills that can be used anywhere within the Incident Command System organization. No minimum qualifications are prescribed, as technical specialists normally

perform the same duties during an incident that they perform in their everyday jobs, and they are typically certified in their fields or professions.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.2, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 4.4

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

technological hazards

Hazards that originate from technological or industrial conditions, dangerous procedures, infrastructure failures or specific human activities.

Examples include industrial pollution, nuclear radiation, toxic wastes, dam failures, transport accidents, factory explosions, fires and chemical spills. Technological hazards also may arise directly as a result of the impacts of a natural hazard event.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

telecommunications device for the deaf (TDD)

Teletypewriter.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

telematics

The mechanisms that support the acquisition of telemetry data and action based upon it.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

telemedicine

Telemedicine is the use of telecommunication and information technologies in order to provide clinical health care at a distance. It helps eliminate distance barriers and can improve access to medical services that would often not be consistently available in distant rural communities. It is also used to save lives in critical care and emergency situations.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.5, 3.4

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

telemetry

Telemetry is a technology that allows the remote measurement and reporting of information of interest to a system designer or operator; e.g., doctor

monitoring pacemaker functionality.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.5, 3.4

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

telephone service priority (TSP)

A procedure used by a telephone company to establish priorities in deciding which lines and trunks to restore subsequent to an outage.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

telephone tree

A list of staff, their phone numbers, and their role in the Incident Command System (if applicable). The first person on the list (usually the principal or Incident Commander) calls his or her pre-assigned staff members to relay what is and is not known and what steps should be taken. These staff members continue passing along the principal's message to their pre-assigned contacts until everyone has been contacted.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.6, 3.8, 4.2

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

telesurgery

The use of telematic technology for on-site computer aided surgery, remote operations and robotic surgery. Also e-Surgery.

Related categories: 2.2, 2.5, 3.4

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

teletypewriter (TTY)

Also known as TDD. A device capable of information interchange between compatible units using a dial up or private-line telephone network connections as the transmission medium. ASCII or Baudot codes are used by these units.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

term harmonization

Activity leading to the selection of designations for a harmonized concept either in different languages or within the same language

Harmonized terms between different languages are equivalent terms; harmonized terms within the same language are either synonyms or term variants.

Related categories: 3.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 860:2007(en) Terminology work - Harmonization of concepts and terms. Year of publication: 2007. Available from: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:860:ed-3:v1:en> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

terrorism

As defined in the Homeland Security Act of 2002, activity that involves an act that is dangerous to human life or potentially destructive of critical infrastructure or key resources; is a violation of the criminal laws of the United States or of any State or other subdivision of the United States; and appears to be intended to intimidate or coerce a civilian population, to influence the policy of a government by intimidation or coercion, or to affect the conduct of a government by mass destruction, assassination, or kidnapping.

Related categories: 3.1

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

tertiary health care

The superior level of health-care facilities where highly complicated and specialized conditions that cannot be treated at the general secondary health-care level are referred to for study and treatment.

Related categories: 5

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

tertiary prevention

Strategies to reduce the complications of a disease.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

test

Unique and particular type of exercise, which incorporates an expectation of a pass or fail element within the aim or objectives of the exercise being planned

The terms “test” and testing are not the same as “exercise” and “exercising”.

Related categories: 2.2, 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

testing

Procedure for evaluation, which provides a means of determining the presence, quality or veracity of something

Testing may be referred to as a “trial”.

Testing is often applied to supporting plans.

Related categories: 4.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

TETRA

The TETRA network, based on the trunking system, is widely used in Europe for voice communication in emergency situations. This network allows communication through antennas, as well as direct communication between nearby devices. In addition, it allows short data transmission, although with a very low transfer rate.

Related categories: 3.3

thematic analysis

Technique used to identify, analyse and interpret patterns of meaning in qualitative data.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

threat

Potential cause of an unwanted incident, which could result in harm to individuals, assets, a system or organization, the environment or the community

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.7, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

threat analysis

Process of identifying, qualifying and quantifying the potential cause of an unwanted incident, which could result in harm to individuals, assets, a system or organization, the environment or the community

Related categories: 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

tier 1 supplier

Provider of products and services directly to an organization usually through a contractual arrangement

Related categories: 2.1, 3.1, 3.2, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

tier 2 supplier

Provider of products and services indirectly to an organization through a tier 1 supplier

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

time difference of arrival (TDOA)

A terrestrial Location Determination Technology (LDT) that computes a transmitter's location based upon the times a signal is received at multiple receivers.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.1

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

time division duplex mode (TDD)

This is using TDM access to separate outward and return signals in which the bandwidth used can be variable based on the requirements of the data being transmitted.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

time division multiple access (TDMA)

A digital radio interface.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

time series analysis

Statistical technique for analysing data that is spaced out over time.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

time-jump

In simulation exercises: jumps in time are used to compress the timescale of the simulated emergency.

Related categories: 4.1

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

token ring

Local area network architecture originally developed by IBM. Later standardized by ISSS as 802.5. Transmission on the network is governed by the possession of a “token” or specific octet of data. A station may only transmit when it receives the token.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

tools

Instruments and capabilities that allow the professional performance of tasks, such as information systems, agreements, doctrine, capabilities, and legislative authorities.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

top management

Person or group of people who directs and controls an organization at the highest level

Top management has the power to delegate authority and provide resources within the organization.

If the scope of the management system covers only part of an organization, then top management refers to those who direct and control that part of the organization.

This constitutes one of the common terms and core definitions of the high level structure for ISO management system standards.

Related categories: 2.1, 3.1, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

topology

Spatial relationships between connecting or adjacent features in a geographic information system data layer.

Related categories: 3.7

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

tornado

A violently rotating column of air that reaches the ground or open water (waterspout).

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

toxicity

The capacity of a substance to cause injury to a living organism. A highly toxic substance will cause damage in small quantities, while a substance of low toxicity will need large quantities to produce an effect. Toxicity is also dependent on the portal of entry, the time frame of exposure and the latent period.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

track and trace

Means of identifying every individual material good or lot(s) or batch in order to know where it is at a given time (track) and where it has been (trace) in the supply chain

Related categories: 1.1, 3.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

training

Activities designed to facilitate the learning and development of knowledge, skills and abilities, and to improve the performance of specific tasks or roles

Related categories: 3.2, 4.1, 4.2

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Simulation Exercise Manual. Year of publication: 2017. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

transaction costs

Any use of resources required to negotiate and enforce agreements, including the cost of information needed to facilitate a bargaining strategy, the time spent haggling, and the costs of preventing cheating by the parties to the bargain.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

transfer of command

The process of moving the responsibility for incident command from one Incident Commander to another. Transfer of command must include a transfer of command briefing, which may be oral, written, or a combination of both.

Related categories: 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

translation

Spoken word or text which is translated or the process of translating from one language to another.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

transmission control protocol (TCP)

The Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) is one of the main protocols of the Internet protocol suite. It originated in the initial network implementation in which it complemented the Internet Protocol (IP). Therefore, the entire suite is commonly referred to as TCP/IP. TCP provides reliable, ordered, and error-checked delivery of a stream of bytes between applications running on hosts communicating via an IP network.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

transmission control protocol / internet protocol (TCP/IP)

A layered set of protocols used to connect dissimilar computers together. The TCP part of this provides the transport service required by the application layer.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

transmission delay

In a network based on packet switching, transmission delay is the amount of time required to push all the packet's bits into the wire.

Related categories: 2.2

transport control protocol (TCP)

The end to end reliability protocol that recognizes and corrects lower layer errors caused by connectionless networks.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

trauma

Injury of any nature

Related categories: 3.3

United Nations, Department of Humanitarian Affairs. Internationally agreed glossary of basic terms related to Disaster Management. Year of publication: 1992. Available from: <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/004DFD3E15B69A67C1256C4C006225C2-dha-glossary-1992.pdf>

trauma and injury severity score (TRISS)

A physiological and anatomical formula to evaluate the likelihood of survival following severe injuries, marking the probability from 0 to 100%.

Related categories: 3.3

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

trauma score

The trauma score is a numerical grading system for estimating the severity of injury, each parameter receiving a number (high for normal and low for impaired function). The severity of injury is estimated as the sum total of the numbers, the lowest score being 1 and the highest 16.

Related categories: 3.3

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

treaty

An international contract in writing between two or more States, negotiated, signed, ratified and binding to the States parties. Some terms used interchangeably for the same are covenant, pact, convention, agreement, protocol, international treaty.

Related categories: 1.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

triage

The process of deciding which patients should be treated first based on how sick or seriously injured they are

Refers to categorization and prioritization of patients according to the severity of symptoms and the availability of aid.

Related categories: 3.3

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

triangulation

A method for determining positions on the Earth based on measurements of distances or areas of figures. In contrast to the Trilateration method, this locates the position based on the angle of each of the three signals received by the satellites involved with respect to the measurement point.

Related categories: 3.3

trilateration

A method of measuring distances to accurately determine your exact position on the Earth's surface.

Related categories: 3.3

trojan horse

A Trojan horse, or Trojan, is a type of malicious code or software that looks legitimate but can take control of your computer. A Trojan is designed to damage, disrupt, steal, or in general inflict some other harmful action on your data or network.

Related categories: 3.3

tropical cyclone

A tropical cyclone originates over tropical or subtropical waters. It is characterised by a warm-core, non-frontal synoptic-scale cyclone with a low pressure centre, spiral rain bands and strong winds. Depending on their location, tropical cyclones are referred to as hurricanes (Atlantic, Northeast Pacific), typhoons (Northwest Pacific), or cyclones (South Pacific and Indian Ocean).

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

trunk

Typically, a communication path between central office switches, or between the 112 Control Office and the PSAP.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

trunk group

One or more trunks terminated at the same two points.

Related categories: 5

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

trunking radio system

Bidirectional radio system that uses a control channel to automatically assign frequency channels to groups of users' radio terminals.

Related categories: 2.2

tsunami

A series of waves (with long wavelengths when traveling across the deep ocean) that are generated by a displacement of massive amounts of water through underwater earthquakes, volcanic eruptions or landslides. Tsunami waves travel at very high speed across the ocean but as they begin to reach shallow water they slow down and the wave grows steeper.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

type 1 WHO FMT

Outpatient emergency care FMT

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from:

<https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

type 2 WHO FMT

Inpatient surgical emergency care FMT

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from:

<https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

type 3 WHO FMT

Inpatient referral care FMT

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from:

<https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

UN advanced field hospital

UN Level 3 medical care. It is the highest level of medical care deployed within a mission area. At this level all capabilities of a level 1, 1+, 2 and 2+ medical facility are provided as are capabilities for multidisciplinary surgical services, specialist services and specialist diagnostic services, increased high dependency care capacity, extended intensive care services and specialist outpatient services.

Capacity: up to 10 surgeries per day, hospitalization of 50 patients at one time for up to 30 days, 50–60 OPD per day, 10 dental consultations per day, 20 X-rays and 40 laboratory tests per day, medical supplies for 60 days, 2 OT, 2 wards with 25 beds each, 1–4 ICU beds

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from:

<https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

UN basic field hospital

UN Level 2 medical care. Is the first level where basic surgical expertise is available, and life support services and hospital and ancillary services are provided within mission area. It has the capabilities of a Level 1 plus emergency surgery, damage control surgery, post operative services and high

dependency care, intensive care resuscitation, inpatient services, also basic imagistic services, laboratory, pharmaceutical, preventive medicine

and dental services, patient record maintenance and tracking of evacuated patients. Level 2+: level 2 with additional capabilities like:

orthopaedic, gynaecology, internal medicine, diagnostic imaging (CT scan).

Capacity: 3–4 operations per day, hospitalization of 10–20 sick/wounded for up to 7 days, 40 OPD per day, 1 OT, 1 or 2 ward with 10 bed each, 1–2 intensive care beds, consumables for 60 days.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from:

<https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

UN hazard classification

9 Classes: (1) explosive, mass explosion hazard, very insensitive substances; (2) flammable gases, non-flammable non-toxic gases, toxic gases; (3) flammable liquids; (4) flammable solids, spontaneously combustible substances, substances dangerous when wet; (5) oxidizing substances other than organic peroxides, organic peroxides; (6) poisonous (toxic) substances, infectious substances; (7) radioactive substances; (8) corrosive substances and (9) other dangerous substances.

Related categories: 3.1

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

UN Level 1 medical care

Primary health and emergency care.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

UN Level 2 medical care

Basic field hospital.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

UN Level 3 medical care

Advanced field hospital.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

UN primary health and emergency care

UN Level 1 medical care. It is the first level of medical care that provides primary health care, and immediate lifesaving and resuscitation services. Normally included within basic level 1 capabilities are: routine sick call and the management of minor sick and injured personnel for immediate return to duty, as well as casualty collection from the point of injury/wounding and limited triage; stabilization of casualties; preparation of casualties for

evacuation to the next level of medical capability or the appropriate level of medical facility depending on the type and gravity of the injuries;

limited in-patient services; advice on disease prevention, medical risk assessment and force protection within the area of responsibility. A level

1 medical facility is the first level of medical care where a doctor/physician is available. Level 1+: Level 1 medical facility can be enhanced by the

addition of supplementary capabilities: primary dental care, basic laboratory testing, preventive medicine, surgical capability (forward surgical module; only in exceptional situations), aeromedical evacuation team.

Capacity: treatment of 20 OPD/day, holding capacity of 5 patients for up to 2 days, Medical supplies for 60 days.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

underlying disaster risk drivers

Processes or conditions, often development-related, that influence the level of disaster risk by increasing levels of exposure and vulnerability or reducing capacity.

Underlying disaster risk drivers - also referred to as underlying disaster risk factors - include poverty and inequality, climate change and variability, unplanned and rapid urbanization and the lack of disaster risk considerations in land management and environmental and natural resource management, as well as compounding factors such as demographic change, non-disaster risk-informed policies, the lack of regulations and incentives for private disaster risk reduction investment, complex supply chains, the limited availability of technology, unsustainable uses of natural resources, declining ecosystems, pandemics and epidemics.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

undesirable event

Occurrence or change that has the potential to cause loss of life, harm to tangible or intangible assets, or negatively impact the human rights and fundamental freedoms of internal or external interested parties

Related categories: 2.3, 3.1, 3.6, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

unicast

A one-to-one transmission from one point in the network to another point; that is, one sender and one receiver, each identified by a network address.

Related categories: 2.2

unified area command

Version of command established when incidents under an Area Command are multijurisdictional. See Area Command.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

unified command (UC)

In incidents involving multiple jurisdictions, a single jurisdiction with multiagency involvement, or multiple jurisdictions with multiagency involvement, unified command allows agencies with

different legal, geographic, and functional authorities and responsibilities to work together effectively without affecting individual agency authority, responsibility, or accountability.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.6, 3.7

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

uniform resource identifier (URI)

1. A predictable formatting of text used to identify a resource on a network (usually the Internet). 2. A string of characters that must follow prescribed syntaxes such as URL, URN...

Version 1.1 of the XML namespaces recommendation uses IRIs (Internationalized Resource Identifiers) instead of URIs. However, because version 1.1 is not yet a full recommendation [February, 2003] and because the IRI RFC [11] is not yet complete, this document continues to refer to URIs instead of IRIs.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

uniform resource indicator (URI)

A Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) is a unique sequence of characters that identifies a logical or physical resource used by web technologies. URIs may be used to identify anything, including real-world objects, such as people and places, concepts, or information resources such as web pages and books.

Related categories: 2.2

uniform resource locator (URL)

Is a reference to a web resource that specifies its location on a computer network and a mechanism for retrieving it. A URL is a specific type of Uniform Resource Identifier (URI), although many people use the two terms interchangeably.

Related categories: 2.2

uninterruptible power supply (UPS)

A backup system designed to provide continuous power in the event of a commercial power failure or fluctuation.

Related categories: 3.5

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

Union Mechanism

EU Civil Protection Mechanism

Related categories: 1.1, 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 1313/2013/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32013D1313&from=EN>

unit

The organizational element with functional responsibility for a specific activity within the Planning, Logistics, and Finance/Administration Sections in ICS.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.4, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

unit leader

The individual in charge of a unit in ICS.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.4, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

unity of command

Principles clarifying the reporting relationships and eliminating the confusion caused by multiple, conflicting directives. Incident managers at all levels must be able to control the actions of all personnel under their supervision.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.4, 3.6

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. CIS resources: Glossary of Related Terms. Year of publication: 2018. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/emiweb/is/icsresource/assets/glossary%20of%20related%20terms.pdf> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

universal coordinated time (UTC)

Also known as Zulu or GMT. Time provided by National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) and United States Naval Observatory (USNC).

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

universal terrestrial radio access (UTRA)

UTRA is a standard for 3G mobile communications services being specified by 3GPP. The radio access components of UTRA are based on direct-spread wideband code-division multiple access (WCDMA) and hybrid time-division (TDCDMA) access methods that have been designed for 3G frequency

efficiency, mobility, and QoS requirements.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

upstream

Handling, processing and movement of goods that occurs before the organization in the supply chain takes custody of the goods

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

urban agglomeration

Physical structure and composition of an urban area or continuity of large urban clusters where the built-up zone or population density of an extended city or town area or central place and any suburbs are linked by continuous, connected urban development

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.4, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

urban open area

Vacant areas, public or private, within urban boundaries

Urban open areas are all fringe open spaces and captured open spaces associated within the scope and parameters (3.1.170) of the urban system.

State parks, national parks or open areas in the countryside outside the parameters of the urban area are not considered as urban open areas in this document.

Related categories: 3.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

urban resilience

Ability of any urban system, with its inhabitants, in a changing environment, to anticipate, prepare, respond to and absorb shocks, positively adapt and transform in the face of stresses and challenges, while facilitating inclusive and sustainable development

A more resilient urban system is characterized by its ability to continue through disruption in the short-to medium-term, combined with a capacity to reduce pressures and adapt to changes, risks and opportunities. Urban resilience, therefore, is dependent upon the ability of an urban systems not just to deal with shocks, but also with chronic stresses and challenges.

Urban resilience is dependent upon the individual and collective resilience of the separate components of a complex urban system. Although a city, town or community within an urban area can individually demonstrate enhanced resilience within its respective boundaries, urban resilience encompasses the broader geographic scope of urban agglomeration. Resilience of an urban system is measured by the capacity for resilience of each individual system component and dependent upon the resilience of the weakest performer among the urban agglomeration within the system scope.

In order to assess, plan and act accordingly in the face of shocks, stresses and challenges, an urban system's capability for resilience should be measured and analysed through qualitative and quantitative data.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.6, 3.7, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

urban system

Human settlement, integrated and complex set of system components, characterized by universal and interdependent dimensions: physical, functional, organizational and spatial; comprised of people, processes and assets managed through effective governance mechanisms

Being dynamic, the composition and elements of an urban system changes with time.

Every urban area has characteristics of an urban system, regardless of its size, culture, location, economy and/or political environment.

Characterized as urban systems, urban areas have the objectives of managing the complex interactions and interdependencies among its multiple components, with the purpose of fulfilling a variety of functionalities including social, economic, cultural and environmental.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

USAR

Urban Search and Rescue

Related categories: 3.4

USAR Heavy

Heavy urban search and rescue (HUSAR)

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

USAR in CBRN conditions (CBRNUSAR)

EU Civil Protection Mechanism module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks is: Special search and rescue operation in a contaminated environment, using protective suits, in accordance with the requirements of the medium and heavy urban search and rescue modules as appropriate.

Related categories: 2.1, 3.4, 3.5, 4.4, 4.5

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

USAR Light

Assistance with surface search and rescue in the

INSARAG: immediate aftermath of the disaster. Usually come from the affected or neighbouring countries. Its deployment to international emergencies is normally not recommended.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

USAR Medium

Medium urban search and rescue (MUSAR)

Related categories: 3.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.5

Norton I, von Schreeb J, Aitken P, Lajolo C. World Health Organization, Health Cluster. WHO Classification and minimum standards for foreign medical teams in sudden onset of disasters. Year of publication: 2013. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/classification-and-minimum-standards-for-foreign-medical-teams-in-sudden-onset-of-disasters>

use of force continuum

Increasing or decreasing the level of force applied as a continuum relative to the response of the adversary, using the amount of force reasonable and necessary

The amount of force used should be the minimum reasonable amount needed to eliminate the threat presented, thereby minimizing the risk and severity of any injury that can occur.

Escalation/de-escalation of force response with a level of force should be appropriate to the situation at hand, acknowledging that the response can move from one part of the continuum to another in a matter of seconds.

Related categories: 2.2, 3.5, 4.2, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

user datagram protocol (UDP)

User Datagram Protocol (UDP) is one of the core members of the Internet protocol suite. With UDP, computer applications can send messages, in this case referred to as datagrams, to other hosts on an Internet Protocol (IP) network. Prior communications are not required in order to set up communication channels or data paths. UDP provides checksums for data integrity, and port numbers for addressing different functions at the source and destination of the datagram. It has no handshaking dialogues, and thus exposes the user's program to any unreliability of the underlying network; there is no guarantee of delivery, ordering, or duplicate protection. If error-correction facilities are needed at the network interface level, an application may instead use Transmission Control Protocol (TCP).

Related categories: 2.2

Utstein standards

Named after a centre of study, research, contemplation and conference in Norway, where standardization templates and quality control systems are formulated and proposed, particularly concerning the quality of management in RCP (cardiopulmonary resuscitation) and other various emergencies.

Related categories: 5

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

validation

Confirmation of the accuracy of a measure or design.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

value

What people consider to be desirable ways of living as individuals and as members of societies.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

values

Beliefs an organization adheres to and the standards that it seeks to observe

Related categories: 2.3, 3.6, 3.7

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

Vancouver style

Citation style used in documents, in which numbers are embedded in the text and the citations are listed in numerical order.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

vector

1. An insect or other animal that normally transports an infectious agent that constitutes a public health risk; 2. An insect or any living carrier that transports an infectious agent from an infected individual to a susceptible individual or its food or immediate surroundings.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

verification

Confirmation, through the provision of objective evidence, that specified requirements have been fulfilled

Related categories: 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

vertical integration

The coordination of the functions, activities or operational units that are in different phases of the service production process. Examples of this type of integration are the links between hospitals and medical groups, outpatient surgery centres and home-based care agencies.

Related categories: 3.2, 3.6

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

vessel

A maritime craft

Related categories: 3.4, 3.5

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icssc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

vicious cycle

Sequence of reciprocal cause and effect leading to a worsening of the situation.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

video relay service (VRS)

A service provided by common carriers and other vendors that provides third party communication relay between video telephone users using Internet

connections and videophone or webcam and voice telephone users.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

video-surveillance

Surveillance by video means

Related categories: 2.1, 2.3, 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

violence

An act that intentionally threatens, attempts, or actually inflicts harm on another person or group of others.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

virtual function (VF)

A virtual function is a member function that you expect to be redefined in derived classes. When you refer to a derived class object using a pointer or a reference to the base class, you can call a virtual function for that object and execute the derived class's version of the function.

Related categories: 2.2

virtual LAN (VLAN)

Any broadcast domain that is partitioned and isolated in a computer network at the data link layer. VLANs work by applying tags to network frames and handling these tags in networking systems, creating the appearance and functionality of network traffic that is physically on a single network but acts as if it is split between separate networks. In this way, VLANs can keep network applications separate despite being connected to the same physical network, and without requiring multiple sets of cabling and networking devices to be deployed.

Related categories: 2.2

International Organisation within the EU. European Emergency Number Association (EENA). Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

virtual private network (VPN)

It is a digital tool that allows you to redirect traffic through a secure tunnel, hiding your IP address and encrypting the exchanged data. A virtual private network (VPN) is a network that uses a public telecommunication infrastructure, such as the Internet, to provide remote offices or individual users with secure access to their organization's network

Related categories: 2.2, 3.3

International Organisation within the EU. European Emergency Number Association (EENA). Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

vision

An inspirational statement that articulates main prioritized goals as well as values for what government wants to achieve for its population, both in public health and healthcare system terms.

Related categories: 5

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2011. Available from: https://www.who.int/healthsystems/Glossary_January2011.pdf

visualization

Spatial analysis method, resulting in maps that describe spatial patterns.

Related categories: 3.7

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

VMAX

Flash storage systems with high performance

Related categories: 3.3

voice over internet protocol (VOIP)

Provides distinct packetized voice information in digital format using the Internet Protocol. The IP address assigned to the user's telephone number may be static or dynamic.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

voice service provider (VSP)

Operates the network equipment that provides call processing for Voice over Internet Protocol subscribers.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

volcanic activity

A type of volcanic event near an opening/vent in the Earth's surface including volcanic eruptions of lava, ash, hot vapour, gas, and pyroclastic material.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

volunteer

An unpaid person who is trained to assist in implementing ongoing program activities on a regular basis under the supervision of a staff person in areas including health, education, transportation, nutrition, and management.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.4, 4.5

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

VPN Tunnel

A VPN tunnel (often simply called VPN, or virtual private network) is an encrypted connection between your computer or mobile device and the Internet in general. In this sense, it prevents third party users or potential attackers from accessing sensitive patient data or intercepting communications made, hijacking or interfering with them.

Related categories: 3.3

vulnerability

1. Something that creates susceptibility to a source of risk that can lead to a consequence. 2. The conditions determined by physical, social, economic and environmental factors or processes which increase the susceptibility of an individual, a community, assets or systems to the impacts of hazards.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

vulnerability assessment

Process of identifying and quantifying vulnerabilities

Related categories: 2.1, 2.3, 2.5, 3.1, 3.2, 3.7, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

vulnerable group

Individuals who share one or several characteristics that are the basis of discrimination or adverse social, economic, cultural, political or health circumstances and that cause them to lack the means to achieve their rights or, otherwise, enjoy equal opportunities

Related categories: 2.3, 3.1, 3.2, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

vulnerable person

Individual who might be less able to anticipate, cope with, resist or recover from the impacts of an emergency

In this document, a vulnerable person is not defined by the nature of the vulnerability but by their personal circumstances at the time of the emergency.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.3, 3.1, 3.2, 3.6

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

walkie-talkie

A portable device that allows communication between users at short distances, consisting of a transmitter and receiver system of radiofrequency waves. It can be used for long distances if an intermediate base station is involved.

Related categories: 2.4, 3.3

warning

The alerting of emergency response personnel and the public to the threat of extraordinary danger and the related effects that specific hazards may cause.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.8

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

warning dissemination function

Activities to issue appropriate messages for people at risk based on evidence-based information received from the hazard monitoring function

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6, 3.8

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

wash

Acronym for water, sanitation and hygiene.

Related categories: 3.5

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

water purification (WP)

EU Civil Protection Mechanism module referenced in Annex II of Decision N° 2014/762/EU (General requirements for modules and technical assistance and support teams) whose tasks are: 1) Provide drinkable water, from surface water sources, according to the applicable standards and at least to the level of the WHO standards. 2) Perform water quality control at the outtake point of the purification equipment.

Related categories: 2.1, 3.5, 4.4, 4.5

European Parliament and the Council of the European Union. Decision no 2014/762/EU of the European Commission of 16 October 2014. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32014D0762&from=EN>

wave action

Wind-generated surface waves that can occur on the surface of any open body of water such as oceans, rivers and lakes, etc. The size of the wave depends on the strength of the wind and the traveled distance (fetch).

Related categories: 3.5

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

wearables

An everyday device (e.g., a bracelet) worn by the patient that stores information relevant to the patient's identification and treatment.

Related categories: 2.5

web 2.0 technologies

A website or application that enables enhanced user engagement through creation or sharing of online user-developed content, and allows users to create, share, collaborate, and communicate.

Related categories: 2.2

World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. Year of publication: 2021. ISBN: 9789240032286. Available from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

web service

A self-contained, self-describing, modular application that can be published, located, and invoked across the Web. Web services perform functions that can be anything from simple requests to complicated business processes

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

whitewater

Fast moving water, flowing down a steeper gradient, used for recreational purposes, eg steep rivers for kayaking, canoeing, and whitewater rafting

Related categories: 3.1

Rescue 3 Europe Ltd. Rescue 3 International - Water and Flood Rescue Manual v6.2020. Available from: <https://www.rescue3europe.com/student-downloads/water-and-flood-rescue-manual/>

WHO Emergency Risk Management and Humanitarian Response (ERM)

Department at WHO for emergency humanitarian management, now expanded to include Health Action in Crises (HAC), Polio Eradication and Country Collaboration (PEC) clusters.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.5

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

WHO graded emergency

An acute public health event or emergency that requires an operational response by WHO. There are three WHO grades for emergencies, signifying the level of operational response by the Organization: Grade 1 (limited response), Grade 2 (moderate response), Grade 3 (major/maximal response). If a graded emergency persists for more than six months it may transition to a protracted emergency.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.8, 4.2

World Health Organization. WHO Health Systems Strengthening Glossary. Year of publication: 2017. ISBN: 9789241512299. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241512299>

wide area network (WAN)

Is a large network of information that is not tied to a single location. WANs can facilitate communication, the sharing of information and much more between devices from around the world through a WAN provider.

Related categories: 2.2

wide area network (WAN)

Network using common carrier-provided lines that covers and extended geographical area.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

wifi (IEEE 802.11 a/b/g/n/ac)

A WiFi network is simply an internet connection that's shared with multiple devices in a home or business via a wireless router. The router is connected directly to your internet modem and acts as a hub to broadcast the internet signal to all your Wi-Fi enabled devices.

Related categories: 2.2

wildfire

Any uncontrolled and non-prescribed combustion or burning of plants in a natural setting such as a forest, grassland, brush land or tundra, which consumes the natural fuels and spreads based on environmental conditions (e.g., wind, topography). Wildfires can be triggered by lightning or human actions.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

wind

Differences in air pressure resulting in the horizontal motion of air. The greater the difference in pressure, the stronger the wind. Wind moves from high pressure toward low pressure.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

wind current

The water current generated by wind acting upon the surface of water over a period of time

Related categories: 3.1, 3.4, 3.7, 3.8

International Maritime Organization/International Civil Aviation Organization (IMO/ICAO). International Aeronautical and Maritime Search and Rescue Manual. Year of publication: 2016. ISBN 978-92-9258-059-9. Available from: <http://www.icsc.org.cn/upload/file/20190102/Doc.9731-EN%20IAMSAR%20Manual%20-%20International%20Aeronautical%20and%20Maritime%20Search%20and%20Rescue%20Manual%20Volume%20III%20-%20Mobile%20Facilities.pdf>

winter storm

A low pressure system in winter months with significant accumulations of snow, freezing rain, sleet or ice.

Related categories: 3.1

Integrated Research on Disaster Risk. IRDR Peril Classification and Hazard Glossary. Year of publication: 2014. Available from: https://www.irdrinternational.org/uploads/files/2020/08/2h6G5J59fs7nFgoj2zt7hNAQgLCgL55evtT8jBNI/IRDR_DATA-Project-Report-No.-1.pdf

wired equivalent privacy (WEP)

A standard protocol that establishes connections with a secure Wi-Fi network.

Related categories: 3.3

wireless

Operating by means of transmitted electromagnetic waves a wireless remote

Related categories: 2.2

wireless application protocol (WAP)

A standard protocol to access information over a mobile wireless network.

Related categories: 3.3

wireless fidelity (WiFi)

A common name for IEEE 802.11 wireless broadband access networks.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012.
Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

wireless telecommunications

The family of Telecommunications services under the heading of Commercial Mobile Radio Service. Includes Cellular, Personal Communications Services (PCS), Mobile Satellite Services (MSS) and Enhanced Specialized Mobile Radio (ESMR).

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012.
Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

work environment

Set of conditions under which work is performed

Conditions include physical, social, psychological and environmental factors (such as temperature, lighting, recognition schemes, occupational stress, ergonomics and atmospheric composition).

Related categories: 3.1

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

workforce

Anyone engaged in the delivery of the organization's objectives, including direct employees, agency staff, contractors and volunteers

Related categories: 4.1, 4.2, 4.5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

working group (WG)

A group of people formed to discuss and develop a response to a particular issue. The response may result in a Standard, an Information Document, Technical Requirements Document or Liaison.

Related categories: 5

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012.
Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

workload

The hypothetical relationship between a group or individual and task demands.

Related categories: 5

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012.
Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

workshop

A type of discussion-based exercise focused on increased participant interaction and focusing on achieving or building a product (e.g., plans, policies)

A workshop is typically used to test new ideas, processes, or procedures; train groups in coordinated activities; and obtain consensus. Workshops often use breakout sessions to explore parts of an issue with smaller groups.

Related categories: 4.1

USA Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), Emergency Management Institute. EMI School Program Glossary. Available from: <https://training.fema.gov/programs/emischool/el361toolkit/glossary.htm> (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

worksite

Any site where significant rescue operations are carried out

Related categories: 3.4, 3.7

World Association for Disaster and Emergency Medicine (WADEM)

Major worldwide organization of professionals from a wide range of health disciplines engaged in or promoting better knowledge and practice of all aspects of emergency medicine and disaster management. Publisher of "Prehospital and Disaster Medicine".

Related categories: 4.2, 4.5

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

World Customs Organization (WCO)

Independent intergovernmental body whose mission is to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of customs administrations

It is the only intergovernmental worldwide organization competent in customs matters.

Related categories: 5

International Organization for Standardization (ISO). International Organization for Standardization (ISO). ISO 22300:2021(E) Security and resilience - Vocabulary. Year of publication: 2021.

World Health Organization (WHO)

The health arm of the United Nations aiming at "the attainment by all peoples of the highest possible level of health" as a human right.

Related categories: 4.2, 4.5

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

world health organization graded emergency

An acute public health event or emergency that requires an operational response by WHO. There are three WHO grades for emergencies, signifying the level of operational response by the Organization: Grade 1 (limited response); Grade 2 (moderate response); Grade 3 (major / maximal response). If a graded emergency persists for more than six months it may transition to a protracted emergency.

Related categories: 3.1, 3.2

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

world wide web (www)

The public internet.

Related categories: 2.2

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

x,y

Shorthand expression for coordinates that identify a specific location in two dimensions representing latitude and longitude.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 3.7

European Emergency Number Association (EENA). EENA Operations Document: 112 Terminology. Year of publication: 2012. Available from: <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/112-terminology/>

XABCDE

Mnemonic acronym for eXsanguinating hemorrhage, Airway, Breathing, Circulation, Disability, and Expose/Environment. A primary extended but rapid survey in case of grave multiple injury to be performed in no more than 2–5 min.

It takes 2 minutes or less for a patient to exsanguinate. No other intervention prehospital care providers perform is more important than stopping that level of bleeding in trauma patients.

Related categories: 3.4

National Association of Emergency Medical Technicians (NAEMT). PHTLS: Prehospital Trauma Life Support. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9781284171426.

years lost due to disability (YLDs)

Years lost due to disability are calculated as the number of incident cases × average duration of the diseases × weight factor to account for severity.

Related categories: 5

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

zero-day

"Zero-day" is a broad term that describes recently discovered security vulnerabilities that hackers can use to attack systems.

Related categories: 3.3

Zigbee

Zigbee is the name of the specification for a set of high-level wireless communication protocols for use with low-power digital broadcasting, based on the IEEE 802.15.4 Wireless Personal Area Network (WPAN) standard. It targets applications requiring secure communications with low data rate and maximized battery life.

Related categories: 3.3

zonation

The division and subdivision of a geographical area (country, region, etc.) and mapping into sectors that are homogeneous with respect to given criteria.

EXAMPLE: according to population density, or a perceived use, resource, hazard, avalanche, seismic fault, flooding or other degrees of risk. It also includes regulations according to each zone or microzone.

Related categories: 2.3, 3.2, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

zone zero (ZZ)

In a disaster, area of great damage, but less than at the epicentre (or Ground Zero), surrounding this, with considerable but less destruction and where danger, search-and-rescue, exclusions and restrictions still apply.

Related categories: 2.1, 2.3, 2.4, 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.6, 3.7

Gunn SWA. International Association for Humanitarian Medicine Brock Chisholm. Dictionary of Disaster Medicine and Humanitarian Relief. Year of publication: 2012. ISBN: 978-1-4614-4445-9. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-4445-9_1 (Date of consultation: 01/03/2022)

zoonoses

Zoonotic disease. Any disease or infection that is naturally transmissible from vertebrate animals to humans.

Zoonotic diseases can be spread by food, water, fomites or vectors.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>

zoonotic event

A manifestation of a disease in animals that creates a potential for a disease in humans as result of human exposure to the animal source.

Related categories: 3.1

World Health Organization. WHO Glossary of Health Emergency and Disaster Risk Management Terminology. Year of publication: 2020. ISBN: 9789240003699. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240003699>